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D6.3 Climate-ready strategies for Nature Based solutions

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FutureMARES Project

FutureMARES - Climate Change and Future Marine Ecosystem Services and Biodiversity is an EU-funded research project examining the relations between climate change, marine biodiversity and ecosystem services. Our activities are designed around two Nature-based Solutions (NBS) and Nature-inclusive Harvesting (NIH):

Effective Restoration (NBS1)

Effective Conservation (NBS2)

Nature-inclusive (sustainable) Harvesting (NIH)

We are conducting our research and cooperating with marine organisations and the public in Case Study Regions across Europe and Central and South America. Our goal is to provide science-based policy advice on how best to use NBS and NIH to protect future biodiversity and ecosystem services in a future climate.

FutureMARES provides socially and economically viable actions and strategies in support of nature-based solutions for climate change adaptation and mitigation. We develop these solutions to safeguard future biodiversity and ecosystem functions to maximise natural capital and its delivery of services from marine and transitional ecosystems. To achieve this, the objectives of *FutureMARES* defined following goals:

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List of symbols and abbreviations

CC	Climate change
DoA	Description of Action, a part of the project Grant Agreement describing the project work plan
EC	European Commission
EC GA	European Commission Grant Agreement – a contract between the European Commission and FutureMARES consortium
GA	Grant Agreement
NGO	Non-governmental Organisation.
NBS	Nature-based Solutions
NBS1	Effective Restoration
NBS2	Effective Conservation
Tn.x	Task – an sub-component of a work package where “n” is a number of the work package and “x” is a number of the task within this work package
WP	Work Package

Glossary

Areas of interest: areas proposed in the *Revitalising Our Seas* report as priorities for the siting of new Marine Protected Areas. These areas were defined as those where a species or habitat of interest was present and in high densities. The species and habitats of interest include seabed habitats, commercially exploited species, cetaceans, elasmobranchs, and breeding and non-breeding birds.

Bright-spot: a site where multiple environmental conditions are improved, and the ecosystem enters a new ecosystem state beyond its natural, historical variability, or its variability in a reference period (*sensu*^{1,2}). In this case, the new state is defined by trends that are inconsistent with expected mean

¹ E. Hawkins and R. Sutton (2012). Time of emergence of climate signals. *Geophysical Research Letters* 2012 Vol. 39 Issue 1

² Queirós et al. (2021) Bright spots as climate-smart marine spatial planning tools for conservation and blue growth. *Global Change Biology*. 27: 5514-5531.

long-term climate change trends for the surrounding region. E.g. cooling where the long-term trend is warming; increased dissolved oxygen where the long-term trend is deoxygenation². Such conditions are linked to climate cycles and oscillations, and changes in circulation patterns, and tend to be short- to medium-term events (i.e. they do not persist in the long term).

Climate change hotspot: a site where a climate signal emerges. That is, a site where climate pressures drive an ecosystem into a new mean ecosystem state, beyond its natural, historical variability, or its variability in a reference period (*sensu*^{1,2}).

Climate change refuge: a site where the mean ecosystem state remains within the range of its natural, historical variability, or that in a reference period (i.e. within its 95% confidence interval in that period).

Climate change resilient habitats: where climate change refugia are observed (*sensu*²).

Climate signal: when the mean state of the ecosystem exceeds the range of its natural, historical variability or that in a reference period (i.e. its 95% confidence interval in that period). In this chapter, the reference period is the period of 2006-2025 (hereafter “the present”).

Executive summary

Extreme weather events and long-term changes in our coasts and our seas are a present reminder of the breakdown of the global climate system. As efforts to limit the pace of climate change take shape, and climate action unfolds, it is likely that excess greenhouse gas emissions presently in our atmosphere may continue to impact our marine ecosystems, as part of our natural world, for decades and centuries to come. The need to introduce immediate action to preserve areas of our ecosystems that may, in the meantime, be less sensitive to those changes – climate change refugia - is thus widely recognized. Such sites may serve as the seed banks where our marine biodiversity may be preserved in the interim, until such a time when the global pressure of climate change has been reduced. To this end, modelling projections that estimate the degree of climate change experienced by marine species and habitats under different possible futures are, thus, invaluable tools with which to inform the design of conservation and restoration mechanisms to protect such “climate resilient” sites, including well-managed marine protected area networks; as well as climate-smart and nature inclusive harvesting strategies.

In this report, we employ state of the art methods for the analyses of climate modelling projections for ocean species and habitats generated by the FutureMARES project WP4, to identify the locations of climate change refugia across European waters, from Portugal to the Archipelago Sea, that could support climate-smart conservation, restoration and nature-inclusive harvesting strategies.

We find that in several cases, even under emissions scenarios that only moderately exceed the Paris Agreement, extensive declines of species may be observed in many areas. In those areas, simulated restrictions linked to protected areas and fisheries closures often led to climate change refugia emerging across the foodweb, and at the ecosystem level, including species of conservation and commercial value, which sometimes spilled over to adjoining areas (e.g. in the Western Mediterranean Sea basin analysis, Storyline group 30, 31,33). This was particularly the case in the North Sea analysis (Storyline group 12,13,14), and in the Portuguese coast analysis (Storyline group 21, 23), highlighting the importance of such measures in helping deliver effective a sustainable ocean, even under very high emissions (RCP8.5). In other cases, extensive climate change refugia emerged across tested scenarios (e.g. in the Western Mediterranean Sea, Storyline group 30, 31,33; in Ireland, Call for Knowledge Needs report; in the analyses of migratory estuarine opportunistic fish across Europe (Storyline group 16, 17); and in fish assemblages dependent on coastal vegetated habitats in the Balearic Islands (Storyline 25), the Tuscan Archipelago (Storyline 28), and the Archipelago Sea (Storyline 7). In some cases, those refugia resulted from complex foodweb interactions, resulting from the concerted pressures of fisheries and climate change. Those results suggest that even in areas at the forefront of European climate change (such as the Mediterranean Sea), sustainable conservation, restoration and harvesting may still be possible when communities are considered as a whole, given appropriate anchoring of marine spatial policies in ecosystem-based approaches. This was particularly clear when climate change refugia and bright spots emerged within conservation areas or in other sites affected at present by human activities incompatible with the high levels of restrictions

simulated in scenarios, such as sewage discharge and dredging (North Sea and Western Mediterranean Sea). Such results, found across most storylines we investigated here, make the case for a holistic approach to marine spatial management supported by mechanisms such as Marine Spatial Planning (MSP). Indeed, our study strongly suggests that meeting the objectives of the EU 2030 Biodiversity strategy will require integrative approaches to policy delivery, including integration with the EU Marine Spatial Planning Directive.

The role of species interactions in driving many of our findings also highlighted that projecting the response of marine ecosystems to climate change can scarcely be done by considering only climate-driven physical and biogeochemical changes in the ocean (e.g. temperature, pH, O₂) more often considered in policy design. As found here, those changes can have complex repercussions, especially at the sub-national and local level, difficult to estimate from broadscale analysis of physical and biogeochemical patterns, or from single species studies. Partnerships between policy and science, to support the uptake of evidence such as the analysis and datasets made available here, could thus represent a key step toward promoting a sustainable and healthy ocean in the EU, that protects its biodiversity and resources into the future. A climate-resilient path for conservation is possible for European waters, for its species and habitats. Studies such as this one may support that route into the future.

1 Introduction

It is widely accepted that, to be effective in a changing ocean, protected areas, restoration programmes and harvesting activities (e.g. wild capture fisheries and aquaculture) need to be planned and managed to consider climate-driven shifts in species and habitat distributions (Gaines, White et al. 2010). Recent peer-reviewed research from the team working in FutureMARES has already highlighted how ocean modelling projections indicate that the sensitivity of European waters to climate change varies over space and time, and that this in turn depends on the magnitude of increased future greenhouse gas emissions we come to experience (Queirós, Talbot et al. 2021). That work has also shown how area-based interventions, such as MPAs and other area based conservations measures, can be spatially configured to accommodate those changes, to maximise their resilience under climate change, and reap benefits for a growing blue economy.

Similarly, numerical modelling tools developed in WP2 and WP4 of FutureMARES, allow for the projection of the potential impacts of climate change on the coastal and marine environment, its species and habitats, over space and time, in parallel to other human impacts such as fishing (Coll, Lynam et al. 2024). Climate-signal detection, in turn, is a statistical analysis framework that can be applied to those types of data to help objectively understand the strength of climate-driven changes. A climate signal is defined as when a change in an ocean variable (i.e. the 'signal') becomes larger than the amplitude of natural or internal variation in that variable (defining the 'noise'), the latter representing the dynamics of these ecosystems in a reference or historical period (Hawkins and Sutton 2012, IPCC 2021). Detecting the time of emergence of this climate signal is widely used within the climate sciences, including within reporting by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, to help understand how different areas of the (planet and the) ocean vary in climate sensitivity, to inform policy development (IPCC 2021). This approach is widely seen as a necessary step in the analysis of global climate modelling data because climate patterns vary (i.e. are noisy) due to natural sources of variation (including periodic forcing, non-linear feedbacks, and random fluctuations, Mann, Steinman et al. 2021); as well as due to human-driven excess greenhouse gas emissions (IPCC 2021). Understanding and attributing causality between the known trend in excess greenhouse gas emissions and climate and associated ecosystem change thus necessitates key trends in ocean climate variables (such as temperature, dissolved oxygen, ocean pH), and the resulting changes in species and habitat distributions, to be estimated against their natural variability.

Climate change causes multi-faceted alterations in marine ecosystems, represented by a multiple-stressor ocean (IPCC 2019). However, climate signal detection has been predominantly used to assess changes in single stressors individually, limiting the ability to inform ecosystem-based policy development. Recent work by this team provided a solution to this challenge, allowing for ecosystem-wide climate signal detection, in line with how marine species, habitats and the food web, experience climate change (Queirós, Talbot et al. 2021). Climate signal detection has been widely applied to the ocean's physical and biochemical properties (IPCC 2021), and the same approach can further be used to study natural populations, communities and ecosystems (Queirós, Huebert et al. 2016, Queirós, Talbot et al. 2021, Jenouvrier, Long et al. 2022). This approach allows for an understanding of how natural marine systems, including their biota, are responding to the pace of climate change (Pecl, Araújo et al. 2017, Lenoir, Bertrand et al. 2020), beyond other sources of natural variability (Queirós, Talbot et al. 2021). As a result, when applied to broadscale datasets on species and habitat distributions, this approach can be used to help inform on policies that seek to deliver on ecosystem-wide outcomes, such as the EU 2030 Biodiversity Strategy, the EU Marine Spatial Planning Directive, and/or the EU Nature Restoration Law. Such analyses can help establish

where ocean ecosystem-dependant human activities and interventions, such as protected areas, may have the best chance of being sustainable (i.e. climate change refugia and bright-spots), despite potentially large effects of climate change on species and habitats underpinning those maritime sectors elsewhere (i.e. climate change hotspots, Queirós, Talbot et al. 2021, Queirós, Kay et al. 2024). In this way, it is possible to estimate how marine planning and other area-based management mechanisms may help provide routes for climate change adaptation for coastal species and habitats, as well as for dependent activity sectors.

Consideration of climate signal detection evidence in planning, and associated ecosystem-wide processes, can therefore help steer local and national policy to allow for maritime sectors to redistribute over space, as organisms underpinning their activity or that of other sectors also redistribute, in response to climate-driven shifts in their habitats. This type of evidence can also be used in the scientific advice to individual maritime activity sectors, such as conservation and fisheries, to help design sectorial climate-smart spatial management strategies (Queirós, Talbot et al. 2024, Talbot, Jontila et al. 2024). By building and capitalising on the natural climate-change resilience distribution of marine ecosystems, such approaches to spatial management can therefore be seen as a **nature-based solution (NBS) that support climate change adaptation** for nature and people (Queirós, Talbot et al. 2021, O'Leary, Fonseca et al. 2023). Such approaches are especially well aligned with delivering ambition set out in the European Green Deal to enhance the delivery of climate adaptation through nature-based solutions focused on healthy and resilient seas and ocean (EC 2019, O'Leary, Fonseca et al. 2023). Furthermore, by helping enhance the climate-resilience of protection measures for species of commercial and conservation value, such an approach is likely to have benefits not only for marine biodiversity, but also for the blue economy (Hermoso, Carvalho et al. 2022).

1.1 Objectives

In this report, we aimed to **help inform on how nature-based solutions (NBS) explored within the FutureMARES storylines could become adaptive and responsive to climate change, that is, climate-smart**. FutureMARES explores two types of NBS:

- **NBS1:** Effective Restoration Strategies of habitat-forming species, that can also serve as 'climate rescuers' (*sensu* Bulleri, Eiksson et al. 2018). Targeted habitats include seagrasses, salt marshes, mangroves, kelp forests, coral reefs and shellfish reefs, which can buffer species from negative effects of warming and ocean acidification. These habitats are also key nursery areas supporting biodiversity (including commercially important species), provide natural refuges and feeding grounds, improve seawater quality, reduce coastal erosion and flood risk, function as carbon sinks (regulating climate), and sustain tourism and cultural activities.
- **NBS2:** Effective Conservation Strategies explicitly considering the range of impacts of CC and other hazards on habitat suitability for flora and fauna. Strategies explored include preserving the integrity of food webs and sustaining population connectivity across networks of climate refugia (where biogeophysical conditions are stable or changing slowly over multiple spatial and temporal scales, e.g. from site-specific marine protected areas to conservation strategies for highly-migratory charismatic megafauna).

In upstream tasks, new modelling tools were developed to help drive forward the European Union's capability to project the climate-driven and management-driven changes in the distribution of key

species and habitats at the helm of European conservation and restoration programs. Specifically, through a new generation of mechanistic species distribution and food web models (Wilson, Maar et al. 2023, Coll, Lynam et al. 2024). Here, we apply community-level climate-signal detection to that set of modelling projections to estimate how climate change will affect the species and habitats underpinning NBS1 and NBS2 within different FutureMARES Storylines. Specifically, **we aimed to help uncover how the spatial design of Marine Protected areas and Other Effective Area-Based Conservation Measures (“OECMs”) across European waters could be optimised to enable effective marine conservation and restoration in these regions, under different scenarios of climate change and management of other human activities.** We aimed to deliver on 3 objectives:

Objective 1) Estimate whether the current spatial configuration of nature-based solutions explored within the FutureMARES Storylines is effective into the coming decades, given the projected effects of climate change in the underpinning species and habitats.

Objective 2) Identify what other areas could be used withing those nature-based solutions, to improve the resilience of those programmes to climate change.

Objective 3) Translate the evidence uncovered into data and visualisation formats that are accessible to a non-scientific audience, to support public and stakeholder consultation during conservation and restoration policy design.

This last objective is especially important, since the development of ocean conservation and planning policy has not kept in line with advances in predictive marine climate change modelling (Tittensor, Beger et al. 2019). A fundamental step enabling that change is the delivery of more recent co-production approaches, whereby research is delivered as a collaboration between academics and non-academics (e.g. policy practitioners) in a participatory setting that is context-based (e.g. FutureMARES storylines), pluralistic (recognising the needs and knowledge of multiple actors and users), interactive and goal-oriented (Norström, Cvitanovic et al. 2020). As a key aim of FutureMARES is to enable the development of EU policy that enables the conservation of its marine biodiversity into the future, FutureMARES built here on such co-production approaches and wider initiatives. The results of analyses undertaken in this report are therefore presented in a format to enable such engagement.

1.2 Contribution to the project

This work helps meet the FutureMARES program goals:

- 2) Ecological Knowledge needed for planning effective NBS;
- 5) Improved projections of ecological impact of climate change (long-term climate, extreme climate & management scenarios);
- (8) Use Powerful tools to integrate, display and discuss our results.

2 Methodology

2.1 Analyses structure

This report builds on storylines, real-world case-studies from across Europe around which FutureMARES research was developed (<https://www.futuremares.eu/regions-storylines>). Here, we apply climate signal detection (viz IPCC 2013, Queirós, Talbot et al. 2021) to a wealth of ocean climate modelling data generated within the FutureMARES project (WP4), to help address our research questions. Where particular gaps were identified in the modelling portfolio from FutureMARES for particular Storylines, additional modelling data were sought out. Those data came from the UK Research and Innovation, Natural Environmental Research Council National Capability, and European research framework modelling projects. The datasets used in each section of the report are detailed in the tables listed withing sub-chapter, below.

It is noted that Chapter 3 of this report includes the results of one of the program’s response to a Call for Knowledge Needs launched by FutureMARES in March to July 2022, which followed the Eclipse approach (Garcia Rodrigues, Bueno-Pardo et al. 2014), inviting interested stakeholders, that is, any group that may be affected by marine climate change, to identify their needs related to the implementation of NBS and Nature Inclusive Harvesting, to safeguard marine biodiversity and ecosystems in a future climate . The remaining chapters of the report result from activities undertaken as part of the original workplan of the FutureMARES program Task 6.1.

2.2 What scenarios and modelling datasets were used?

With the exceptions of Chapters 3 and 5, within which specific detail on data used is provided, the ocean climate change modelling datasets analysed are spatial-temporal datasets which represent results from ecosystem models (Ecopath with Ecosim) described in detail in Coll, Lynam et al. (2024). Those models were forced using scenarios reflecting Representative Concentration Pathways (“RCP”), as described in Butenschön and Kristiansen (2023). RCP are global greenhouse gas concentration trajectories (Van Vuuren, Edmonds et al. 2011) used by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. In FutureMARES, RCP2.6 and RCP8.5 were contrasted because they were seen to represent a likely range of future global greenhouse gas and aerosol concentrations (Bindoff, Cheung et al. 2019, Hausfather and Peters 2020, Schwalm, Glendon and Duffy 2020, Masson-Delmotte, Zhai et al. 2022). Based on these RCPs, we considered the following scenarios:

- *RCP2.6 status quo scenario* (RCP2.6): the “low emissions” scenario, assumes a mitigation scenario aiming to limit the increase of global mean temperature to around $\sim 1.6^{\circ}\text{C}$ above preindustrial levels for mid-range model climate sensitivity. This scenario corresponds to a mean warming of sea surface temperature in the analysed European waters of about 1°C by the end of the 21st century (Butenschön and Kristiansen 2023). This scenario does not include any other measures with regard to the management of the marine environment.
- *RCP8.5 status quo scenario* (RCP8.5): the “growing emissions” scenario, considers that global greenhouse gas emissions continue to rise steadily throughout the 21st century, leading to mean global warming $\sim 4.3^{\circ}\text{C}$. This scenario corresponds to a mean warming of sea surface temperature in the analysed European waters of about $3\text{-}4^{\circ}\text{C}$ by the end of the 21st century

(Butenschön and Kristiansen 2023). This scenario does not include any other measures with regard to the management of the marine environment.

Beyond the two RCP status quo scenarios, three more scenarios were developed, combining the emissions trajectories with general views about climate change mitigation and environmental concerns into a type of scenario termed Shared Socio-economic Pathways (“SSP”), as also used by the IPCC (O’Neill, Kriegler et al. 2014):

- *Global Sustainability scenario (SSP1-2.6)*: considers RCP2.6 alongside SSP1 which simulates low challenges to climate change mitigation and adaptation. EU & international legal regulations and targets for restoration and conservation are met. EU fisheries directives, Regional Seas Conventions and Ecosystem-based fisheries management are fully implemented.
- *National Enterprise Scenario (SSP3-8.5)*: RCP8.5 is considered alongside SSP3 which simulates high challenges to mitigation and adaptation. Restoration focuses on species of commercial value or providing coastal protection. Small MPAs are established, with national focus and no additional connectivity. Fisheries landings are maximised to ensure national food security, with support from fisheries subsidies.
- *World Markets scenario (SSP5-8.5)*: RCP8.5 is considered alongside SSP5 which simulates high challenges to mitigation, but low challenges to adaptation (Butenschön and Kristiansen 2023). There is limited investment in ecosystem restoration, and this is focused on species with high commercial value. Small MPAs are established to support species with economic value, with no focus on connectivity. Landings value is maximised through large-scale fisheries (and smaller fleets decline).

These scenarios were employed in modelling outputs analysed in all but Chapter 3 and 5 of this report, and were generated using the Ecospace temporal-dynamic approach of the Ecopath with Ecosim (EwE) model, as described in Coll, Lynam et al. (2024). Those models simulated the impacts of scenarios on the structure of food webs across the regional seas explored in FutureMARES, from low trophic levels to apex predators and megafauna, and from the seabed to the surface of the ocean and seabirds. The scenarios employed by those models simulated the ecological effects of species conservation and restoration programs, and changes to human uses including Fisheries Closures and Marine Protected Areas, to represent the effects of FutureMARES NBS1 and NBS2. The scenarios also included changes to activities related to fishing practices. These scenarios represent the regional downscaling of the FutureMARES program scenarios (FutureMARES 2021) considering the specific ecological, social, political, economic, technological and legal contexts of each storyline group.

Summary tables for the model simulations analysed here are provided alongside a summary of each storyline group, in each section of this report. More detail about the species scenarios employed can be found in Coll, Lynam et al. (2024).

2.3 Temporal and spatial resolution of analyses

We co-designed analyses described here with the ambition to provide the best ocean climate change evidence for each storyline assessed. With the exception of Chapters 3 and 5 (within which detail on data used is provided), all modelling data analysed in this report was produced in FutureMARES WP4 and those used within each chapter are further detailed within it. Those modelling datasets

have a spatial horizontal resolution of 0.25 x 0.25 decimal degrees and are produced in 2D, so no depth profiles are considered.

2.4 Climate signal detection methodology for modelling analysis

For each FutureMARES storyline explored in this report, we sought numerical modelling datasets (from FutureMARES, with the exception of Chapter 3) that as best as possible represent the species and habitat conditions that compose the ecosystem underpinning the specific NBS explored. In basin-scaled storylines (Chapter 4) we focused on the whole ecosystem to derive ecosystem-level sensitivity and resilience of that particular region to climate change, and how that affected the outcomes of the NBS explored in each specific storyline. In all chapters, we worked with storyline leaders, which in turn worked with local actors, to ensure the evidence captured reflected well local and regional concerns.

For each NBS in a storyline, and each of the future scenarios explored (2.2) we analysed all modelling time-series selected using spatial meta-analysis to detect the emergence of an ecosystem-level climate signal³. This method of analysis has already been deployed in globally distributed research programmes informing on climate resilient conservation in Ireland (Queirós, Talbot et al. 2021, Queirós, Talbot et al. 2024), the United Kingdom (Queirós, Kay et al. 2024), Philippines (Talbot, Jontila et al. 2024), Tanzania (Queirós, Talbot et al. 2024b) and Vietnam (Queirós, Talbot et al. 2022).

Each analysis contrasts a present time-period (2006-2025) with all subsequent 20 year time periods, to the end of the 21st century. The first stage of the analysis algorithm defined the expected mean climate-driven trend for each modelling dataset in the group of datasets selected for analysis in that storyline. We therefore began by reviewing the scientific literature to identify the expected mean climate change-driven trend for each species or habitat variable of interest to each storyline. To this end, regionally relevant peer-reviewed evidence was used. Trends identified through this review of literature are documented within each subsequent chapter, alongside the dataset analysed. In cases when modelling datasets were identified as being of interest to a storyline, but no consistent climate change-driven trend could be established for that specific habitat condition or species of interest, then this modelling dataset was removed from subsequent analyses. For instance, horse mackerel species (*Trachurus trachurus*, *Trachurus mediterraneus*, *Trachurus picturatus*) were modelled in FutureMARES in the Western Mediterranean and are important species in the region. However, as there is no consensus in the literature about whether this species group is increasing or decreasing in that region due to climate change, subsequent analyses (e.g. Chapter 4) did not include modelling projections for their distribution. For all species distribution modelling datasets considered, all modelling data used simulate that, as different species exhibit different degrees of sensitivity to climate change pressures, compensatory mechanisms may take place, at least temporarily, as the more sensitive species perish locally to the benefit of less sensitive species, for which more resource may become available (Wilson, Salliey et al. 2021).

Once expected mean climate-driven trends had been established for all modelling datasets in our final selection in each storyline, we undertook NBS specific climate signal detection analysis in each chapter. That analysis is delivered through the spatial meta-analysis algorithm described in Queirós,

³ A. M. Queirós, E. Talbot, N. J. Beaumont, P. Somerfield, S. Kay, C. Pascoe, et al. (2021) Bright spots as climate-smart marine spatial planning tools for conservation and blue growth *Global Change Biology* 2021 Vol. 27 Pages 5514-5531

Talbot et al. 2021, which is written in R language using author led scripts. The algorithm estimates the overall change in the mean of the family of distributions composed of all modelling datasets selected in each storyline in each future 20 year period, relative to the present period (2006-2025), and this defines the summary effect. The variance of the summary effect is calculated considering within dataset variability and across dataset variability. The analysis design employed, for each storyline, thus compares the current state of the marine ecosystem underpinning the NBS with that in all future 20 year periods, from the present to the end of the 21st century. For each grid cell of the common model domain (in all chapters but Chapter 3, the regional EwE model grid, Coll, Lynam et al. (2024)), a random-effects meta-analysis model was then built, testing each time the null hypothesis that change across that ecosystem (described by all modelling layers considered in each analysis, in that grid cell) was zero. Three outcomes were possible for each analysis, in each grid cell:

- 1) Climate change refugia: a site was identified as a climate change refuge if the mean change between time periods was small and/or variability (i.e. variance) high, suggesting the ecosystem has a high probability of remaining within the bounds of its variability observed in the present period. These are the areas where the ecosystem underpinning each NBS may be resilient to climate change in the period of analysis and, overall, to support each sector in a similar way to that in the present time.
- 2) Climate change hotspots: a site was identified as a climate change hotspot if a large mean change in analysed modelling layers was estimated, exceeding present time variability, that was consistent with expected climate change trends for many datasets considered. These are climate-vulnerable sites, where a climate signal emerged within the time-frame of analysis.
- 3) Bright-spots: if a site was identified as a climate change bright-spot, a large mean change in the ecosystem, beyond present time variability, was estimated, but the trends in the modelling datasets considered were predominantly contrary to expected long term climate change trends. These are areas where new opportunities for sustainable blue growth and conservation may emerge, at least in the time-frame of analysis (Queirós, Talbot et al. 2021).

The mathematical definition of each category is based on estimation of the variance based confidence interval of the summary effect (M), which quantifies change between the two time periods considered in each analysis (present and future), and is detailed in Queirós, Talbot et al. 2021. M has a normal distribution: a climate change hotspot is identified when M is less than 0 and its confidence interval does not contain zero; a climate change refuge is identified when M 's confidence interval contains 0; and a bright-spot is identified when M is greater than 0 and its confidence interval does not contain 0. The results for each temporal contrast, for each NBS in a storyline and scenario, was then processed to estimate the long-term location of climate change refugia, where there was agreement between scenarios, as follows.

2.5 Long-term classification of sites and shapefile creation

To facilitate the use of information contained in this report, we summarise the patterns that emerge from the spatial-meta analysis of modelling data in each of possible future 20 year periods (to the end of the century), providing a regional, long-term overview of the distribution of climate change refugia, bright-spots and hotspots for each storyline and NBS explored. To this end, we further processed the outputs of storyline climate-signal detection analyses, in all scenarios explored. Briefly, results from analysis contrasting each future 20 year period with the present 20 year period

were saved in the form of matrices containing values of -1 (representing a climate change hotspot), 0 (representing a climate change refugia) or 1 (representing a climate change bright-spot) for each cell in the model domain. Each matrix contrasted each possible 20-year future period with the present, for each of the scenarios considered, per NBS considered. These matrices were summed to create a single master matrix from which threshold values could be defined. We classified a cell as a long-term climate change hotspot, refuge or bright spot if it was categorised as so in at least 80% of the individual time-slice analyses. We used the “terra” package in R to convert all cells that met the threshold for long term classification to polygons, which were then exported as shapefiles. These shapefiles (providing the long-term classification of sites based on the climate signal emergence) are available with this report.

2.6 Other spatial data used

The results from the climate signal detection analyses were then interpreted in the context of the current structure of the blue economy and conservation measures in each storyline. The overlay of modelling data with this GIS information allowed us to identify opportunities for the location of new MPAs and restoration programmes, and their possible expansion, into areas harbouring climate change refugia and bright spots. GIS datasets used are detailed in within annexes to each chapter, below.

3 A climate-resilient path for Ireland’s Marine Protected Areas network

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We report here on the work undertaken as part of the request to the FutureMARES Call for Knowledge Needs, submitted by the Irish Wildlife Trust and Fair Seas. A public report of that work is available here:

https://fairseas.ie/wp-content/uploads/2024/03/FS_climate_report_V4.pdf. The resulting spatial data, identifying long-term climate change refugia and hotspots in Irish waters, is freely available in Talbot and Queirós (2024).

This work is an *addendum* chapter to *Revitalising Our Seas report: Identifying Areas of Interest for Marine Protected Area Designation in Irish Waters* produced by the Fair Seas NGO coalition:

[fairseas.ie/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/Revitalising Our Seas Report Marine Protected Areas Fair Seas.pdf](https://fairseas.ie/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/Revitalising_Our_Seas_Report_Marine_Protected_Areas_Fair_Seas.pdf).

3.1 Regional context and ambition

The Irish government wants to meet its commitment to support the EU Biodiversity Strategy target and protect at least 30% of the Irish Maritime Area by 2030. At present, marine and coastal nature protected areas (in the form of Special Areas of Conservation, SACs and Special Protection Areas, SPAs, together known as the Natura 2000 Network) cover only 9% of Irish waters⁴. Meeting this 2030 target thus represents the ambition to at least triple the Irish marine conservation area network. The *Revitalising Our Seas Report* has suggested that the current state of marine conservation protection in Ireland is not sufficient to provide the necessary levels of protection and restoration recommended in the Irish Government's Marine Protected Area (MPA) Advisory Group report³, and that the health of many marine habitats and species within protected areas is declining or unknown. This decline has been linked, at least partially (e.g. in Lough Hyne⁵), to ongoing changes in the global climate system, as observed around the world. Indeed, climate change, enhanced harvesting of ocean resources, and increased use of coastal areas towards economic growth, are together contributing to the deterioration of coastal and marine ecosystems globally⁶. Addressing climate change will thus be a key part of ensuring that the expansion to Ireland's marine protected area network delivers effectively on its ambitions¹.

It is widely accepted that, to be effective in a changing ocean, protected areas need to be planned and managed to consider climate-driven shifts in designation features such as species and habitat distributions⁷. Recent peer-reviewed research from this team has already highlighted how the sensitivity of Irish waters to these and other climate change driven pressures varies over space and time, and this in turn depends on the magnitude of increased future greenhouse gas emissions we come to experience⁷. Indeed, some habitats and species are sensitive to climate change, but in other areas they are resilient, at least for some time^{1,7}. This heterogeneity in sensitivity can be capitalised upon in the designation of new marine protected areas to ensure effective protection of species and habitats in climate resilient sites, not just now but into the future^{4,8}. In this chapter, we update and expand that evidence base, identifying the location and extent of Irish waters representing key habitats for species of conservation value which exhibit climate change resilience. We then further assess whether Areas of Interest proposed for the siting of new Irish MPAs in the *Revitalising Our Seas Report* could also be used to harness that natural climate resilience within these marine ecosystems. Specifically, we identify areas of Ireland's marine area which may be climate-resilient throughout the 21st century, with regard to habitat conditions and prey availability required for the persistence of key species groups of conservation value highlighted in the *Revitalising Our Seas Report*. Section 3.2 details how we assess spatial and temporal patterns in the distribution of climate

⁴ Marine Protected Area Advisory Group (2020). Expanding Ireland's Marine Protected Area Network: A report by the Marine Protected Area Advisory Group. Report for the Department of Housing, Local Government and Heritage. 59pp.

⁵ Trowbridge et al. (2019) No 'silver bullet': Multiple factors control population dynamics of European purple sea urchins in Lough Hyne Marine Reserve, Ireland. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science* 226:106-271.

⁶ Pörtner et al. (2019). IPCC special report on the ocean and cryosphere in a changing climate Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change: Geneva, Switzerland. 755 pp.

⁷ Gaines et al. (2010). Designing marine reserve networks for both conservation and fisheries management. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 107:18286-18293.

⁸ Queirós et al. (2021) Bright spots as climate-smart marine spatial planning tools for conservation and blue growth. *Global Change Biology*. 27: 5514-5531.

resilient areas and provides summary maps conveying where such sites occur in the long term and with high agreement between different possible greenhouse emissions futures. This new chapter of the report is thus expected to help inform a more climate-resilient path for a new MPA network in Ireland.

3.2 Identifying biologically meaningful and climate resilient sites

Methodology

Marine ecosystems are highly dynamic so determining whether climate change is a driver of changes in habitat conditions, or of species distributions, requires careful assessment of both environmental and species mean trends over time, as well as their variability⁹. In this context, ocean climate modelling (i.e. physical and biogeochemical modelling; species distribution modelling; ecosystem modelling) is an essential decision-support tool for decision-makers designing spatial policy interventions that are adaptive to the effects of climate change, such as the siting of marine protected areas, i.e. climate-smart¹⁰. There is a rich evidence basis that has explored different methodologies with which to support this process. Nevertheless, the implementation of climate-resilient MPAs remains infrequent, and when this does occur, consideration is due primarily to the (long-term) velocity of ocean warming and of species response to this¹¹. Long-term warming is indeed a key driver of marine biodiversity re-distribution³. However, climate change is experienced by marine organisms through changes in many more ecosystem attributes simultaneously, including extreme weather events such as heatwaves and cold snaps, ocean acidification, deoxygenation, and changes in productivity and circulation patterns, all occurring over space and time at different speeds and with different magnitudes¹². One way to assess when and where those changes present significant ecosystem shifts affecting ecosystem conditions required by species and habitats of conservation value (and where and when they do not) is to undertake spatial meta-analysis of ocean climate modelling time-series to detect the time of emergence of an ecosystem-level climate change signal⁷. In contrast with other techniques, this approach allows for the investigation of the effects of climate change as a multiple stressor process experienced by multiple species and habitats⁷. Spatial meta-analysis (of those many modelling time-series simultaneously) then allows for the objective classification of sites as: i) climate-resilient (i.e. climate change refugia); ii) climate sensitive (i.e. climate change hotspots); or iii) temporarily improving in condition despite long-term regional climate trends (i.e. bright-spots)⁷. The detection of climate sensitive sites identifies an area entering a new ecosystem state that may not be able sustain the number of species or level of ecosystem function it has in the present, consistently with expected climate change trends in the region⁷. Conversely, the detection of climate resilient sites (or refugia) identifies when and where it will likely do so⁷, in line with the definition of resilience used by the Irish Government's MPA Advisory Group report³. Bright-spots represent a third category, where a new ecosystem state also emerges, but when observed trends are not in line with the predominant climate change trends in the region (e.g. cooling when warming is expected; species increase when decline is expected⁷). These three different outcomes reflect local scale differences in the rate and direction of change in

⁹ E. Hawkins and R. Sutton (2012). Time of emergence of climate signals. *Geophysical Research Letters*. 39

¹⁰ McLeod et al. (2009). Designing marine protected area networks to address the impacts of climate change *Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment*. 7: 362-370.

¹¹ Tittensor et al. (2019) Integrating climate adaptation and biodiversity conservation in the global ocean." *Science Advances* 5: eaay9969.

¹²Pörtner et al. (2022). *Climate change 2022: Impacts, adaptation and vulnerability*. IPCC Geneva, Switzerland.

environmental conditions (as species respond to them) as a result of ocean circulation patterns and climate cycles or oscillations⁷. The location of climate change refugia and bright-spots thus offers the opportunity for policy makers and other stakeholders to design spatial policy interventions (such as MPA networks) that build on the natural resilience of ecosystems to climate change, creating the potential to deliver effective conservation of species and habitats into the future. Such mechanisms may thus serve as nature-based solutions to help deliver climate change adaptation for ocean biodiversity, and thus help deliver on ambition set out in the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030.

Based on analyses in the Revitalising our Seas report, we sought numerical modelling datasets that represented, as best as possible, habitat conditions required by species listed in that report, as well as species distribution modelling for prey species. Specifically, we undertook dedicated modelling data analyses for: benthic (or seabed) and pelagic (or water column) species; megafauna species (considering birds, large fish species and mammals) focusing on whether they explore predominantly benthic or pelagic habitats; and forage fish (small pelagic fish preyed upon by many species of conservation value, as well as by the fishing industry). “Habitat conditions” were defined as the prevailing physical, biogeochemical conditions and food availability that species depend on, and the modelling dataset analysed is described in Queirós et al. 2024 ([Annex 1 Table A1](#)), for each group of species.

For each group of species, and each of two greenhouse gas emissions scenarios, we analysed all modelling time-series selected using spatial meta-analysis¹³. The analyses contrasted a present time-period (2006-2025) with all subsequent 20 year time periods, to the end of the 21st century. In each contrast, and for each species, each cell in the common model domain (Queirós et al. 2024, [Annex 1](#)) was then classified as a: climate change refuge, a climate change hotspot, or a bright-spot. The emissions scenarios considered are described in Queirós et al. 2024 ([Annex 1](#)), and represent a moderate global level of emissions (Representative Concentration Pathway (“RCP”) 4.5) or a high level of emissions (RCP8.5¹⁴), as used by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. The results for each temporal contrast, for each group of species and scenario was then processed to estimate the long-term location of climate change refugia, where there was agreement between scenarios. A more detailed description of the statistical methodology and datasets analysed is provided in Queirós et al. 2024 ([Annex 1](#)).

This method of analysis has already been deployed in globally distributed research programmes informing on climate resilient conservation in Ireland¹², the UK¹⁵, Tanzania¹⁶, Philippines¹⁷ and

¹³ A. M. Queirós, E. Talbot, N. J. Beaumont, P. Somerfield, S. Kay, C. Pascoe, et al. (2021) Bright spots as climate-smart marine spatial planning tools for conservation and blue growth *Global Change Biology* 2021 Vol. 27 Pages 5514-5531

¹⁴ D. P. Van Vuuren, J. Edmonds, M. Kainuma, K. Riahi, A. Thomson, K. Hibbard, et al. (2011) *Climatic Change* 2011 Vol. 109 Issue 1-2 Pages 5

¹⁵ A. M. Queirós, S. Kay, M. Sciberras et al. (2023) Early-warning system: Climate-smart spatial management of UK fisheries, aquaculture and conservation. A report of the NERC/ESRC Marine Spatial Planning Addressing Climate Effects project. DOI: 10.14465/2023.msp02.tec

¹⁶ A. M. Queirós, E. Talbot, F. E. Msuya et al. (*in review*) Long-term climate change and extreme weather limit marine ecosystem resilience and sustainable development in the Western Indian Ocean

¹⁷ E. Talbot, J.-B. S. Jontila, B. J. Gonzales et al. (*in review*). Incorporating “climate-readiness” into tropical spatial fisheries management strategies

Vietnam¹⁸, and is currently being deployed across 14 locations within the European Union (futuremares.eu). We now employ this approach in this chapter, to estimate what part of areas of interest proposed for the siting of new MPAs in Ireland may also be climate-resilient (i.e. climate refugia or bright-spots).

GIS datasets used

Dataset	Data provider	Available at
Special Area of Conservation	National Parks and Wildlife Service	https://www.npws.ie/maps-and-data/designated-site-data/download-boundary-data
Special Protected Area	National Parks and Wildlife Service	https://www.npws.ie/maps-and-data/designated-site-data/download-boundary-data
Candidate Special Protected Area	National Parks and Wildlife Service	https://www.npws.ie/maps-and-data/designated-site-data/download-boundary-data
FairSeas Area of Interest	FairSeas	by request

3.3 Climate resilient sites within the proposed Irish MPA network expansion

The modelling data analyses carried out in this section indicated that there are opportunities to ensure that the projected expansion of the Irish MPA network includes climate resilient sites, where species and habitats of conservation value may be protected into the future. Overall, 60% of Irish National Marine Planning Framework area (“NMPFa”) (which includes the Exclusive Economic Zone (“EEZ”) and the territorial seas) is thought to overlap with long-term climate change refugia for at least one group of species considered in this report (281, 501Km², equivalent to 67% of the Irish EEZ, Fig. 1). If we consider only sites presently designated, the extent of the NMPFa that is within marine Natura 2000 sites in long-term climate change refugia amounts to only 7% (33, 663 Km², equivalent to 8% of the Irish EEZ). Conversely, if areas proposed in the [Revitalising Our Seas report](#) were to become designated MPAs, then 26% of the Irish EEZ (121, 140 Km², equivalent to 29% of the Irish EEZ) would be in protected areas that are also located in long-term climate change refugia, representing 69% of the new areas proposed for conservation in the report (Fig.3.1). As we define long-term climate change refugia as areas emerging as such for at least 40 years into the future, with high agreement between scenarios (Queirós et al. 2024 , [Annex 1](#)), placing MPAs within these areas may thus represent a no regrets decision when it comes to conservation: an opportunity to support the effective conservation of marine species habitats for decades to come. The majority of these areas occur in offshore regions, and inshore areas to the East and North West coast of Ireland.

¹⁸ A. M. Queirós, H. Talbot, S. Kay, S. Saillely and T. le Vu Hoang (2022) Climate-smart spatial planning assessment in support of conservation and blue growth in Da Nang city’s marine environment. A report from the ACCORD project. DOI: 10.17031/dxfj-a468.

Figure 3.1. Total area of National Marine Planning Framework area covered by climate change refugia for at least one group of species considered in this chapter (i.e. refugia for pelagic habitats, pelagic megafauna, benthic habitats and benthic megafauna were merged). Identified refugia appeared consistently – for at least 40 years within the period of 2026 and 2069 – with high agreement between greenhouse gas emissions scenarios (RCP4.5 and RCP8.5).

With regard to specific species and habitat groups, long-term climate change refugia for megafauna reliant on pelagic habitats were identified primarily in deep offshore areas, which are in the majority of cases unprotected at present. Areas of interest (AOIs) identified in the *Revitalising Our Seas* report overlap with one of these refugia off the SW tip of Irish Waters, around the biologically important Porcupine Seabight (Fig. 3.2). Some of these areas overlap with fishing grounds and oil and gas lease areas, and detailed spatial and temporal patterns for these species can be found in Queirós et al. 2024 ([Annex 2](#), Figure A1).

Figure 3.2. Areas in which long-term climate change refugia were identified for megafauna reliant on pelagic species and habitats (green). Refugia appeared consistently (Annex 1) across both emissions scenarios (RCP4.5 and RCP8.5), between 2026 and 2069.

For megafauna reliant on benthic habitats, long-term climate change refugia were also identified in offshore areas around the Rockall Trough, Rockall Bank and Porcupine Seabight (Fig. 3.3), in some areas that are already protected by SACs, and overlapping with AOIs identified in the *Revitalising our Seas* report. In those areas, fishing and oil and gas license leases overlap with some of the refugia found (Queirós et al. 2024 [Annex 2](#), Figure A2). Smaller refugia were identified in inshore areas off the coasts of Sligo, Galway, Dublin and Waterford (Fig. 3.3), many of which are covered by AOIs identified in the *Revitalising our Seas* report. In these areas, a degree of fishing, wastewater discharges and light pollution co-occurs. Detailed spatial and temporal patterns for this group of species can be found in Queirós et al. 2024 [Annex 2](#), Figure A2.

Figure 3.3. Areas in which long-term climate change refugia were identified for megafauna reliant on benthic species and habitats (green). Refugia appeared consistently (Annex 1) across both emissions scenarios (RCP4.5 and RCP8.5), between 2026 and 2069. The grey line is the Irish National Marine Planning Framework boundary.

Long-term climate refugia for other pelagic species were found to concentrate in offshore areas to the W and SW of the Irish EEZ, around the Porcupine Seabight, and the NW around the Rockall (Fig. 3.4). Only one currently designated SPA is located in a climate refugia, but several of the offshore AOIs identified in the *Revitalising our Seas* report lie in areas that are projected to remain at least partly climate-resilient (Fig. 3.4). These areas also host fishing and oil and gas leases at present, with spatial and temporal patterns shown in Queirós et al. 2024 [Annex 2](#), Figure A3.

Figure 3.4. Areas in which long-term climate change refugia were identified for pelagic habitats (green). Refugia appeared consistently (Annex 1) across both emissions scenarios (RCP4.5 and RCP8.5), between 2026 and 2069. The grey line is the Irish National Marine Planning Framework boundary.

Long-term climate change refugia for other benthic species were found to be more extensive than for other groups. They were found in some inshore waters on the East coast (where the Dublin cSPA is located, Fig. 3.5). In these inshore areas, refugia overlap partially with areas where capital and maintenance dredging occur, and where light pollution can be extensive (Annex 2, Fig.4). The latter can be ecologically meaningful for nearshore benthic species¹⁹. Long-term climate change refugia for benthic species were, however, more generally distributed in deeper offshore areas beyond the continental shelf to the W and SW (Fig.3.5). In these areas, they overlap with the Southern Canyons SAC, where highly diverse deep-water seabed fauna occurs within the dead coral matrix²⁰. These

¹⁹ Davies, T. W., McKee, D., Fishwick, J. et al. (2020). Biologically important artificial light at night on the seafloor. *Scientific reports*, 10(1), 12545.

²⁰ Site synopsis: Southern Canyons SAC. (2023) . Department of Housing, Local Government and Heritage. 2pp. url: [SITE SYNOPSIS \(npws.ie\)](https://npws.ie/SITE_SYNOPSIS)

areas also experience extensive fishing activity, and host oil and gas wells and license leases. Detailed spatial and temporal patterns can be found in Queirós et al. 2024 ([Annex 2](#), Figure A4).

Figure 3.5. Areas in which long-term climate change refugia were identified for benthic species other than megafauna (green). Refugia appeared consistently ([Annex 1](#)) across both emissions scenarios (RCP4.5 and RCP8.5), between 2026 and 2069. The grey line is the Irish National Marine Planning Framework boundary.

Long-term climate refugia for the forage fish species we analysed (*Clupea harengus*, *Sardina pilchardus* and *Sprattus sprattus*) cover the whole of the NMPFa ([Fig. 3.6](#)). However, because such a small number of datasets was used in this spatial meta-analysis [Queirós et al. 2024 \(\[Annex 1\]\(#\)\)](#), this result may be unreliable. [Figure 3.7](#) thus illustrates results per species, exploring individual species abundance changes patterns. Those results suggest that herring and sprat are expected to decline across most of the NMPFa under both greenhouse gas emissions scenarios considered, whilst sardine remain stable in some areas, or increase, in most cases. These results are in line with previous analyses for the region²¹. They do however suggest that key offshore areas explored by birds as foraging grounds, and identified as potential sites for MPAs in the *Revitalising our Seas* report, may be at risk of climate change effects on key, cold-water prey such as herring and sprat.

²¹ Pinnegar, Wright et al. (2020) Impacts of climate change on fish, relevant to the coastal and marine environment around the UK. MCCIP Science Review. 456-481.

However, an increase in abundance of warm affiliated species such as sardine may limit some of that impact. This analysis overlooks effects of climate change on sand eel species that are also key forage fish species, for which no species distribution modelling could be found at the time of this report.

Figure 3.6. Areas in which long-term climate change refugia were identified for forage fish (green). Refugia appeared consistently (Annex 1) across both emissions scenarios (RCP4.5 and RCP8.5), between 2026 and 2069. The grey line is the Irish National Marine Planning Framework boundary.

Figure 3.7: Representative example of mean change in individual forage fish species abundance by mid-century (2041-2060), relative to the present (2006-2025), under RCP 4.5 (top) and RCP 8.5 (bottom). Change is measured using Hedges *g*, which is the standardized mean change estimator, centered around 0 (no change), and placing all species in the same scale to help comparison across species. Green shading shows where species abundances are projected to decrease in comparison to the present; pink shading shows areas where abundances are projected to increase. Herring: *Clupea harengus* (left). Sardine: *Sardina pilchardus* (middle). Sprat: *Sprattus sprattus* (right). The grey line is the Irish National Marine Planning Framework boundary.

3.4 Discussion

In this chapter, we used peer-reviewed methods for the analysis of marine climate change modelling (physical biogeochemical modelling and species distribution modelling)²² to assesses the spatial distribution of climate change resilience in Irish waters. These analyses allowed us to establish the location of long-term climate change refugia for marine species which may support effective

²² Queirós, A. M., E. Talbot, N. J. Beaumont et al. (2021). Bright spots as climate-smart marine spatial planning tools for conservation and blue growth. *Global Change Biology* 27: 5514-5531.

conservation into the future, despite climate change pressures in the broader region. More specifically, we were able to establish that a substantial proportion of areas proposed for the siting of new Marine Protected Areas in Ireland, in the *Revitalizing Our Seas* report, are indeed climate-resilient. The value of those sites is thus not only limited to what species occur there at present, as highlighted in the remainder of the report; it also extends into the ability to provide protection for species and habitats that may be effective in the long-term, as climate change unfolds. Protecting some of these sites would thus be in line with recommendations made in the recent Irish Government's Marine Protected Area Advisory Group report²³. The ambition to establish climate-resilient MPAs is not restricted to Ireland, it is a global one²⁴. With unprecedented climate-driven changes and extreme weather such as super heat-waves taking place in Irish waters as a result of climate change as recently as September 2023, as around the world²⁵, it is time we deliver on this ambition, and plan MPA networks that are climate-smart by design.

It is prudent to remember that there are different sources of uncertainty in ocean climate modelling²⁶. The results presented here were generated using models (Annex 1) that have been found to reproduce well observations in the North East Atlantic region²⁷, and which are thus suitable for analyses focused in Ireland. Many of the areas we identified here as climate change refuges are located in the SW of the Irish NMPFa. This is consistent with previous analyses for the region²⁶. Those analyses found a reduced expression of some long-term climate change trends, and in some cases, a temporary reversal of trends, potentially linked to climate cycles and basin-scale oceanographic processes, in this case the Atlantic Multidecadal Oscillation²⁸ and a changing Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation²⁹. Such effects are known to modify the regional expression of climate trends and to cause significant departure from expected long-term (century-scaled) mean climate change signals within the short and medium term (years to decades)³⁰. The results reported here estimate the location of long-term climate change refugia for different groups of species, for at least 40 years. Placing them under conservation mechanisms such as well-managed marine protected areas may thus represent a key time-buying strategy to support broader Irish marine biodiversity until such a time when we have globally reduced the pace of climate change.

²³ Marine Protected Area Advisory Group (2020). Expanding Ireland's Marine Protected Area Network: A report by the Marine Protected Area Advisory Group. Report for the Department of Housing, Local Government and Heritage. 59pp.

²⁴ D. P. Tittensor, M. Beger, K. Boerder et al.(2019). Integrating climate adaptation and biodiversity conservation in the global ocean. *Science Advances*. 5: eaay9969

²⁵ IPCC (2021). Climate Change 2021: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change..

²⁶ M. R. Payne, M. Barange, W. W. Cheung et al. (2016) Uncertainties in projecting climate change impacts in marine ecosystems. *ICES Journal of Marine Science* 2015 73: 1272-1282

²⁷ A. M. Queirós, S. Kay, M. Sciberras et al.(2023) Early-warning system: Climate-smart spatial management of UK fisheries, aquaculture and conservation. A report of the NERC/ESRC Marine Spatial Planning Addressing Climate Effects project. DOI: 10.14465/2023.msp02.tec

²⁸ G. McCarthy, E. Gleeson and S. Walsh. (2015) The influence of ocean variations on the climate of Ireland. *Weather*. 70: 242-245.

²⁹ G. D. McCarthy, D. A. Smeed, S. A. Cunningham et al. Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation, MCCIP Science Review. Marine Climate Change Impacts Partnership. DOI: 10.14465/2017.arc10.002-atl

³⁰ N. Bindoff, W. W. Cheung, J. Kairo et al. (2019) Changing Ocean, Marine Ecosystems, and Dependent Communities. In: IPCC Special Report on the Ocean and Cryosphere in a Changing Climate.

4 Basin-scale nature-based solutions for climate-resilient ecosystem-based management

4.1 The North Sea (Storyline group 12, 13, 14)

Ana M. Queirós, Elizabeth Talbot, Joana Nunes and Chris Lynam

4.1.1 Regional Context

The North Sea is projected to warm by about 2°C during the 21st century under RCP 8.5, albeit with great uncertainty, with a projected reduction of sea surface salinity of 0.5–0.7 psu (Butenschön and Kristiansen 2023). These effects are expected to lead to changes in primary production, which in turn are expected to cascade up to higher predators with implications for commercial fisheries and species of biodiversity concern, such as black-legged kittiwakes (*Rissa tridactyla*) and harbour porpoise (*Phocoena phocoena*).

There is a long history in the area of shipping, coastal construction, aggregate extraction, and oil and gas production, while investment in renewables (in particular wind turbines) has increased greatly in recent years. Since the Common Fisheries Policy reforms in 2002, the area has seen a reduction in demersal fishing effort, and a recovering trend in the demersal fish community has been observed (Engelhard, Lynam et al. 2015). The impacts of towed gears on seabed habitats has also been reduced. Restoration efforts in the area are pursuing the restoration of habitats previously depleted (such as the once extensive native oyster beds).

4.1.2 Modelling data used

The modelling datasets analysed in this storyline analysis (described in detail in Coll, Lynam et al. (2024)), as well as the expected climate-driven trend for each modelling variable analysed in the climate signal detection spatial meta-analysis algorithm (section 2.4), are summarised below in Table 4.1.1. This dataset includes future projections under all five scenarios (section 2.2) for 41 species or species groups for which clear climate-driven trends could be extracted from the peer review literature (necessary to setup the climate signal detection algorithm, please see 2.4). These projections derive from model runs for the regionally parameterised North Sea EwE food web model, described in Coll, Lynam et al. (2024), and which included a total of 65 functional groups.

Modelling projections were generated employing not only different degrees of possible climate change, in line with different greenhouse gas emissions trajectories, but also different degrees of spatial management measures (please see section 2.2). These scenarios included the implementation of new conservation sites with different degrees of restrictions, as well as fisheries closures (with restrictions imposed on different types of gears (Figure 4.1.2).

Scenarios further included differences in the fishing effort simulated. Both status quo scenarios (RCP2.6 and 8.5) employed baseline fishing mortality. Furthermore, under the Global Sustainability (SSP1.2.6) scenario, fishing effort was imposed to ensure mortality was consistent with Maximum Sustainable Yield for multiple species, and across multiple fleets when they targeted the same individual species. These effects then drive compensatory mechanisms between species across the food web, including predator prey dynamics (Coll, Lynam et al. 2024). In projections employing the National Enterprise and World Markets scenarios (SSP3.8.5 and SSP5.8.5 respectively), fishing effort increased annually by 0.44% and 0.88%, respectively, representing technological development.

In each cell of the common model domain, and for each scenario and each 20 year period between the present and the final part of the 21st century (section 2.4), the climate signal detection algorithm builds one spatial meta-analysis model that analyses all modelling layers together, testing the null hypothesis that change between the present 20 year period and the future 20 year period is zero. Please see section 2.4 for a detailed description of the analysis methodology employed.

Table 4.1.1: Description of modelling data analysed here for the North Sea storyline. "latmin": lowest value of latitude in the model domain; ."latmax": highest value of latitude in the model domain; ."lonmin": lowest value of longitude in the model domain; ."lonmax": highest value of longitude in the model domain. "CC" climate change

Variable	Scenarios	Model	Region	Spatial extent (latmin - latmax; lonmin-lonmax)	Resolution	Time slice	Data provider	Expected climate trend
<i>Amblyraja radiata</i> (starry ray) biomass	Status quo RCP2.6; Status quo RCP8.5; Global sustainability RCP2.6; National enterprise RCP8.5; World market RCP8.5	Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace	North Sea	49 to 62.5; -4 to 9	0.25*0.25	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Chris Lynam, CEFAS	Decrease (Sguotti, Lynam et al. 2016, Jones, Miethe et al. 2023, Thompson, Couce et al. 2023),
<i>Ammodytidae</i> (sandeels: <i>Ammodytes marinus</i>) biomass	Status quo RCP2.6; Status quo RCP8.5; Global sustainability RCP2.6; National enterprise RCP8.5; World market RCP8.5	Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace	North Sea	49 to 62.5; -4 to 9	0.25*0.25	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Chris Lynam, CEFAS	Decrease;(Lindegren, Van Deurs et al. 2018, Thompson, Couce et al. 2023)
<i>Anarhichas lupus</i> (Atlantic wolf fish) biomass	Status quo RCP2.6; Status quo RCP8.5; Global sustainability RCP2.6; National enterprise RCP8.5; World market RCP8.5	Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace	North Sea	49 to 62.5; -4 to 9	0.25*0.25	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Chris Lynam, CEFAS	Decrease (Gordó-Vilaseca, Pecuchet et al. 2023, Thompson, Couce et al. 2023)

<p><i>Balaenoptera acutorostrata</i> (Minke whale) biomass</p>	<p>Status quo RCP2.6; Status quo RCP8.5; Global sustainability RCP2.6; National enterprise RCP8.5; World market RCP8.5</p>	<p>Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace</p>	<p>North Sea</p>	<p>49 to 62.5; -4 to 9</p>	<p>0.25*0.25</p>	<p>2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)</p>	<p>Chris Lynam, CEFAS</p>	<p>Decrease based on CC effects on prey. Herring, sandeel, and mackerel key species in diet matrix. Other species include: whiting, Norway pout, sprat and zooplankton (EwE diet matrix). Herring, sandeel, whiting and Norway pout are all reported as forming a large part of the minke whale diet around the UK (Olsen and Holst 2023) all of which are projected to decrease with CC (see species entries in this table for refs)</p>
<p><i>Callionymidae</i> (dragonets, <i>Callionymus lyra</i>) biomass</p>	<p>Status quo RCP2.6; Status quo RCP8.5; Global sustainability RCP2.6; National enterprise RCP8.5; World market RCP8.5</p>	<p>Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace</p>	<p>North Sea</p>	<p>49 to 62.5; -4 to 9</p>	<p>0.25*0.25</p>	<p>2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)</p>	<p>Chris Lynam, CEFAS</p>	<p>Increase (Simpson, Jennings et al. 2011, Thompson, Couce et al. 2023)</p>
<p><i>Clupea harengus</i> (Atlantic herring) biomass</p>	<p>Status quo RCP2.6; Status quo RCP8.5; Global sustainability RCP2.6; National enterprise RCP8.5; World market RCP8.5</p>	<p>Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace</p>	<p>North Sea</p>	<p>49 to 62.5; -4 to 9</p>	<p>0.25*0.25</p>	<p>2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)</p>	<p>Chris Lynam, CEFAS</p>	<p>Decrease (Montero-Serra, Edwards and Genner 2015, Thompson, Couce et al. 2023)</p>

<p>Diving seabirds (gannet, guillemot, razorbill) biomass</p>	<p>Status quo RCP2.6; Status quo RCP8.5; Global sustainability RCP2.6; National enterprise RCP8.5; World market RCP8.5</p>	<p>Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace</p>	<p>North Sea</p>	<p>49 to 62.5; -4 to 9</p>	<p>0.25*0.25</p>	<p>2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)</p>	<p>Chris Lynam, CEFAS</p>	<p>Decrease, based on trends for prey species, which are all projected to decrease (see species entries in this table for refs). Guillemot key prey species: sandeel and sprat (Smout, Rindorf et al. 2013) Razorbill key prey species: Sprat and herring (St. John Glew, Wanless et al. 2019) Gannet key prey species: herring, sandeels (Hamer, Phillips et al. 2000) Key species in diet matrix are sandeels, infaunal macrobenthos, sessile epifauna, herring and sprat</p>
<p><i>Gadus morhua</i> (Cod) biomass</p>	<p>Status quo RCP2.6; Status quo RCP8.5; Global sustainability RCP2.6; National enterprise RCP8.5; World market RCP8.5</p>	<p>Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace</p>	<p>North Sea</p>	<p>49 to 62.5; -4 to 9</p>	<p>0.25*0.25</p>	<p>2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)</p>	<p>Chris Lynam, CEFAS</p>	<p>Decrease (Blöcker, Sguotti and Möllmann 2023, Thompson, Couce et al. 2023)</p>
<p><i>Galeorhinus galeus</i> (Tope) biomass</p>	<p>Status quo RCP2.6; Status quo RCP8.5; Global sustainability RCP2.6; National enterprise RCP8.5; World market RCP8.5</p>	<p>Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace</p>	<p>North Sea</p>	<p>49 to 62.5; -4 to 9</p>	<p>0.25*0.25</p>	<p>2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)</p>	<p>Chris Lynam, CEFAS</p>	<p>Increase. (Sguotti, Lynam et al. 2016, Jones, Miethe et al. 2023)</p>
<p><i>Glyptocephalus cynoglossus</i> (witch) biomass</p>	<p>Status quo RCP2.6; Status quo RCP8.5; Global sustainability RCP2.6; National enterprise RCP8.5; World market RCP8.5</p>	<p>Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace</p>	<p>North Sea</p>	<p>49 to 62.5; -4 to 9</p>	<p>0.25*0.25</p>	<p>2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)</p>	<p>Chris Lynam, CEFAS</p>	<p>Decrease (Jones, Miethe et al. 2023, Thompson, Couce et al. 2023)</p>

<p><i>Halichoerus grypus</i> (grey seal) biomass</p>	<p>Status quo RCP2.6; Status quo RCP8.5; Global sustainability RCP2.6; National enterprise RCP8.5; World market RCP8.5</p>	<p>Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace</p>	<p>North Sea</p>	<p>49 to 62.5; -4 to 9</p>	<p>0.25*0.25</p>	<p>2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)</p>	<p>Chris Lynam, CEFAS</p>	<p>Decrease based on CC effects on prey species. Key prey species in N. Sea are sandeel, haddock, cod and whiting, all of which are projected to decrease (see species entries in this table for refs). Popping and haul-out sites may be negatively affected by sea level rise (IPCC 2019). Key species in diet matrix : sandeels, cod, other large gadoids, haddock, blue whiting.</p>
<p><i>Hippoglossoides platessoides</i> (long rough dab or American plaice) biomass</p>	<p>Status quo RCP2.6; Status quo RCP8.5; Global sustainability RCP2.6; National enterprise RCP8.5; World market RCP8.5</p>	<p>Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace</p>	<p>North Sea</p>	<p>49 to 62.5; -4 to 9</p>	<p>0.25*0.25</p>	<p>2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)</p>	<p>Chris Lynam, CEFAS</p>	<p>Decrease (Gordó-Vilaseca, Pecuchet et al. 2023, Jones, Miethe et al. 2023, Thompson, Couce et al. 2023)</p>
<p><i>Hippoglossus hippoglossus</i> (Atlantic halibut) biomass</p>	<p>Status quo RCP2.6; Status quo RCP8.5; Global sustainability RCP2.6; National enterprise RCP8.5; World market RCP8.5</p>	<p>Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace</p>	<p>North Sea</p>	<p>49 to 62.5; -4 to 9</p>	<p>0.25*0.25</p>	<p>2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)</p>	<p>Chris Lynam, CEFAS</p>	<p>Decrease (Gordó-Vilaseca, Pecuchet et al. 2023, Jones, Miethe et al. 2023, Thompson, Couce et al. 2023)</p>
<p><i>Lepidorhombus whiffiagonis</i> (megrim) biomass</p>	<p>Status quo RCP2.6; Status quo RCP8.5; Global sustainability RCP2.6; National enterprise RCP8.5; World market RCP8.5</p>	<p>Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace</p>	<p>North Sea</p>	<p>49 to 62.5; -4 to 9</p>	<p>0.25*0.25</p>	<p>2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)</p>	<p>Chris Lynam, CEFAS</p>	<p>Increase (Jones, Miethe et al. 2023, Thompson, Couce et al. 2023)</p>

<i>Leucoraja naevus</i> (cuckoo ray) and skate (<i>Dipturus batis</i>) biomass	Status quo RCP2.6; Status quo RCP8.5; Global sustainability RCP2.6; National enterprise RCP8.5; World market RCP8.5	Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace	North Sea	49 to 62.5; -4 to 9	0.25*0.25	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Chris Lynam, CEFAS	Increase (Thompson, Couce et al. 2023)
<i>Limanda limanda</i> (common dab) biomass	Status quo RCP2.6; Status quo RCP8.5; Global sustainability RCP2.6; National enterprise RCP8.5; World market RCP8.5	Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace	North Sea	49 to 62.5; -4 to 9	0.25*0.25	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Chris Lynam, CEFAS	Decrease (Jones, Miethe et al. 2023, Thompson, Couce et al. 2023)
<i>Lophius piscatorius</i> (monkfish) biomass	Status quo RCP2.6; Status quo RCP8.5; Global sustainability RCP2.6; National enterprise RCP8.5; World market RCP8.5	Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace	North Sea	49 to 62.5; -4 to 9	0.25*0.25	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Chris Lynam, CEFAS	Increase. (Simpson, Jennings et al. 2011, Jones, Miethe et al. 2023)
<i>Melanogrammus aeglefinus</i> (haddock) biomass	Status quo RCP2.6; Status quo RCP8.5; Global sustainability RCP2.6; National enterprise RCP8.5; World market RCP8.5	Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace	North Sea	49 to 62.5; -4 to 9	0.25*0.25	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Chris Lynam, CEFAS	Decrease (Gordó-Vilaseca, Pecuchet et al. 2023, Jones, Miethe et al. 2023, Thompson, Couce et al. 2023)
<i>Merlangius merlangus</i> (whiting) biomass	Status quo RCP2.6; Status quo RCP8.5; Global sustainability RCP2.6; National enterprise RCP8.5; World market RCP8.5	Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace	North Sea	49 to 62.5; -4 to 9	0.25*0.25	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Chris Lynam, CEFAS	Decrease (Simpson, Jennings et al. 2011, Thompson, Couce et al. 2023)

<p><i>Merluccius merluccius</i> (hake) biomass</p>	<p>Status quo RCP2.6; Status quo RCP8.5; Global sustainability RCP2.6; National enterprise RCP8.5; World market RCP8.5</p>	<p>Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace</p>	<p>North Sea</p>	<p>49 to 62.5; -4 to 9</p>	<p>0.25*0.25</p>	<p>2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)</p>	<p>Chris Lynam, CEFAS</p>	<p>Increase (Simpson, Jennings et al. 2011)</p>
<p><i>Micromesistius poutassou</i> (Blue whiting) biomass</p>	<p>Status quo RCP2.6; Status quo RCP8.5; Global sustainability RCP2.6; National enterprise RCP8.5; World market RCP8.5</p>	<p>Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace</p>	<p>North Sea</p>	<p>49 to 62.5; -4 to 9</p>	<p>0.25*0.25</p>	<p>2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)</p>	<p>Chris Lynam, CEFAS</p>	<p>Increase (Wright, Pinnegar and Fox 2020, Thompson, Couce et al. 2023)</p>
<p><i>Microstomus kitt</i> (lemon sole) biomass</p>	<p>Status quo RCP2.6; Status quo RCP8.5; Global sustainability RCP2.6; National enterprise RCP8.5; World market RCP8.5</p>	<p>Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace</p>	<p>North Sea</p>	<p>49 to 62.5; -4 to 9</p>	<p>0.25*0.25</p>	<p>2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)</p>	<p>Chris Lynam, CEFAS</p>	<p>Decrease (Jones, Miethe et al. 2023, Thompson, Couce et al. 2023)</p>
<p><i>Phoca vitulina</i> (harbour seal) North biomass</p>	<p>Status quo RCP2.6; Status quo RCP8.5; Global sustainability RCP2.6; National enterprise RCP8.5; World market RCP8.5</p>	<p>Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace</p>	<p>North Sea</p>	<p>49 to 62.5; -4 to 9</p>	<p>0.25*0.25</p>	<p>2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)</p>	<p>Chris Lynam, CEFAS</p>	<p>Decrease based on CC effects on prey species. Key prey species in N. Sea are cod, whiting, haddock, saithe, plaice and sandeel (Wilson and Hammond 2019) all of which are projected to decrease (see species entries in this table for refs). Pupping and haul-out sites may be negatively affected by sea level rise. (IPCC 2019). Key species in diet matrix herring, sandeels, saithe, cod</p>

<p><i>Phocoena phocoena</i> (harbour porpoise) biomass</p>	<p>Status quo RCP2.6; Status quo RCP8.5; Global sustainability RCP2.6; National enterprise RCP8.5; World market RCP8.5</p>	<p>Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace</p>	<p>North Sea</p>	<p>49 to 62.5; -4 to 9</p>	<p>0.25*0.25</p>	<p>2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)</p>	<p>Chris Lynam, CEFAS</p>	<p>Decrease based on CC effects on prey species. Key prey species in N. Sea are whiting, sandeel, herring, sprat (Ransijn, Booth and Smout 2019), all of which are projected to decrease (see species entries in this table for refs). Key species in diet matrix: Sandeels, whiting, squid and cuttlefish, norway pout, small gadoids, saithe. Starvation in N. Sea porpoises linked to lower proportion of sandeels in diet in the spring (MacLeod, Santos et al. 2007)</p>
<p><i>Platichthys flesus</i> (European flounder) biomass</p>	<p>Status quo RCP2.6; Status quo RCP8.5; Global sustainability RCP2.6; National enterprise RCP8.5; World market RCP8.5</p>	<p>Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace</p>	<p>North Sea</p>	<p>49 to 62.5; -4 to 9</p>	<p>0.25*0.25</p>	<p>2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)</p>	<p>Chris Lynam, CEFAS</p>	<p>Decrease. (Nicolas, Chaalali et al. 2011)</p>
<p><i>Pleuronectes platessa</i> (European plaice) biomass</p>	<p>Status quo RCP2.6; Status quo RCP8.5; Global sustainability RCP2.6; National enterprise RCP8.5; World market RCP8.5</p>	<p>Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace</p>	<p>North Sea</p>	<p>49 to 62.5; -4 to 9</p>	<p>0.25*0.25</p>	<p>2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)</p>	<p>Chris Lynam, CEFAS</p>	<p>Decrease (Engelhard, Lynam et al. 2015, Thompson, Couce et al. 2023)</p>
<p><i>Pollachius virens</i> (saithe) biomass</p>	<p>Status quo RCP2.6; Status quo RCP8.5; Global sustainability RCP2.6; National enterprise RCP8.5; World market RCP8.5</p>	<p>Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace</p>	<p>North Sea</p>	<p>49 to 62.5; -4 to 9</p>	<p>0.25*0.25</p>	<p>2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)</p>	<p>Chris Lynam, CEFAS</p>	<p>Decrease (Gordó-Vilaseca, Pecuchet et al. 2023, Jones, Miethe et al. 2023, Thompson, Couce et al. 2023)</p>

<i>Raja clavata</i> (thornback ray) and <i>Raja montagui</i> (spotted ray) biomass	Status quo RCP2.6; Status quo RCP8.5; Global sustainability RCP2.6; National enterprise RCP8.5; World market RCP8.5	Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace	North Sea	49 to 62.5; -4 to 9	0.25*0.25	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Chris Lynam, CEFAS	Increase (Sguotti, Lynam et al. 2016, Jones, Miethe et al. 2023, Thompson, Couce et al. 2023),
<i>Rissa tridactyla</i> (black legged kittiwake) biomass	Status quo RCP2.6; Status quo RCP8.5; Global sustainability RCP2.6; National enterprise RCP8.5; World market RCP8.5	Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace	North Sea	49 to 62.5; -4 to 9	0.25*0.25	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Chris Lynam, CEFAS	Decrease. Sandeels, herring and sprat key prey species (Ruffino, Y. et al. 2023) which will likely decrease in N. Sea (see species entries in this table for references). Key species in diet matrix : Sandeels, sprat, herring
<i>Scomber scombrus</i> (Atlantic mackerel) biomass	Status quo RCP2.6; Status quo RCP8.5; Global sustainability RCP2.6; National enterprise RCP8.5; World market RCP8.5	Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace	North Sea	49 to 62.5; -4 to 9	0.25*0.25	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Chris Lynam, CEFAS	Increase (Montero-Serra, Edwards and Genner 2015, Thompson, Couce et al. 2023)
<i>Scophthalmus maximus</i> (turbot) biomass	Status quo RCP2.6; Status quo RCP8.5; Global sustainability RCP2.6; National enterprise RCP8.5; World market RCP8.5	Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace	North Sea	49 to 62.5; -4 to 9	0.25*0.25	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Chris Lynam, CEFAS	Increase (Jones, Miethe et al. 2023, Thompson, Couce et al. 2023)
Small sharks (<i>Scyliorhinus canicua</i> (Lesser-spotted dogfish), <i>Mustelus</i> spp. (Smooth-hounds), <i>Etmopterus spinax</i> (Velvet belly)) biomass	Status quo RCP2.6; Status quo RCP8.5; Global sustainability RCP2.6; National enterprise RCP8.5; World market RCP8.5	Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace	North Sea	49 to 62.5; -4 to 9	0.25*0.25	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Chris Lynam, CEFAS	Increase (Thompson, Couce et al. 2023) Scyliorhinus and Mustelus both considered Lusitanian species, with a preference for warmer waters (Jones, Miethe et al. 2023)

<i>Solea solea</i> (common sole) biomass	Status quo RCP2.6; Status quo RCP8.5; Global sustainability RCP2.6; National enterprise RCP8.5; World market RCP8.5	Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace	North Sea	49 to 62.5; -4 to 9	0.25*0.25	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Chris Lynam, CEFAS	Increase (Jones, Miethe et al. 2023, Thompson, Couce et al. 2023)
<i>Sprattus sprattus</i> (sprat) biomass	Status quo RCP2.6; Status quo RCP8.5; Global sustainability RCP2.6; National enterprise RCP8.5; World market RCP8.5	Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace	North Sea	49 to 62.5; -4 to 9	0.25*0.25	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Chris Lynam, CEFAS	Decrease (Montero-Serra, Edwards and Genner 2015, Thompson, Couce et al. 2023)
<i>Squalus acanthias</i> (Atlantic spurdog) biomass	Status quo RCP2.6; Status quo RCP8.5; Global sustainability RCP2.6; National enterprise RCP8.5; World market RCP8.5	Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace	North Sea	49 to 62.5; -4 to 9	0.25*0.25	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Chris Lynam, CEFAS	Decrease. (Sguotti, Lynam et al. 2016, Jones, Miethe et al. 2023)
<i>Trachurus trachurus</i> (Atlantic horse mackerel) biomass	Status quo RCP2.6; Status quo RCP8.5; Global sustainability RCP2.6; National enterprise RCP8.5; World market RCP8.5	Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace	North Sea	49 to 62.5; -4 to 9	0.25*0.25	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Chris Lynam, CEFAS	Increase (Montero-Serra, Edwards and Genner 2015, Thompson, Couce et al. 2023)

Triglidae (gurnards, <i>Eutriglia gurnardus</i>, grey gurnard) biomass	Status quo RCP2.6; Status quo RCP8.5; Global sustainability RCP2.6; National enterprise RCP8.5; World market RCP8.5	Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace	North Sea	49 to 62.5; -4 to 9	0.25*0.25	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Chris Lynam, CEFAS	Increase (Simpson, Jennings et al. 2011)
<i>Trisopterus esmarkii</i> (Norway pout) biomass	Status quo RCP2.6; Status quo RCP8.5; Global sustainability RCP2.6; National enterprise RCP8.5; World market RCP8.5	Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace	North Sea	49 to 62.5; -4 to 9	0.25*0.25	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Chris Lynam, CEFAS	Decrease (Simpson, Jennings et al. 2011, Thompson, Couce et al. 2023)
<i>Nephrops norvegicus</i> (Norway lobster) biomass	Status quo RCP2.6; Status quo RCP8.5; Global sustainability RCP2.6; National enterprise RCP8.5; World market RCP8.5	Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace	North Sea	49 to 62.5; -4 to 9	0.25*0.25	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Chris Lynam, CEFAS	Decrease. (Hernroth, Sköld et al. 2012, Pinnegar, Garrett et al. 2023)
Phytoplankton biomass	Status quo RCP2.6; Status quo RCP8.5; Global sustainability RCP2.6; National enterprise RCP8.5; World market RCP8.5	Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace	North Sea	49 to 62.5; -4 to 9	0.25*0.25	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Chris Lynam, CEFAS	Decrease (Capuzzo, Lynam et al. 2018).

<p>Ostreidae (oysters: <i>Ostrea edulis</i>) biomass</p>	<p>Status quo RCP2.6; Status quo RCP8.5; Global sustainability RCP2.6; National enterprise RCP8.5; World market RCP8.5</p>	<p>Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace</p>	<p>North Sea</p>	<p>49 to 62.5; -4 to 9</p>	<p>0.25*0.25</p>	<p>2006-2025 (reference); 2026- 2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)</p>	<p>Chris Lynam, CEFAS</p>	<p>Increase. (Lemasson, Hall-Spencer et al. 2018)</p>
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4.1.4 GIS datasets used

Table 4.1.2: GIS datasets used to frame the modelling analysis results in the context of the region's blue economy.

Dataset	Data provider	Available at
Designated marine conservation areas (Europe)	UNEP-WCMC and IUCN	https://www.protectedplanet.net/en/search-areas?geo_type=site
Designated marine conservation areas (England, UK)	Natural England	https://environment.data.gov.uk/DefraDataDownload/?mapService=NE/
Designated marine conservation areas (Scotland, UK)	Marine Scotland	https://cagmap.snh.gov.uk/natural-spaces/dataset.jsp?
Offshore fishing effort distribution – pelagic gears	Global Fishing Watch	https://globalfishingwatch.org/data-download/datasets/public-fishing-effort
Offshore fishing effort distribution – benthic/demersal gears	ICES for OSPAR	https://ices-library.figshare.com/articles/report/OSPAR_request_on_the_production_of_spatial_data_layers_of_fishing_intensity_pressure/18639182
Offshore oil and gas infrastructure	North Sea Transition Authority	https://opendata-nstauthority.hub.arcgis.com/datasets/NSTAUTHORITY::surface-points-wgs84/explore?location=55.460493%2C-2.660275%2C6.62
Offshore wind infrastructure (UK)	Crown Estate	https://opendata-thecrownestate.opendata.arcgis.com/datasets/thecrownestate::wind-site-agreements-england-wales-ni-the-crown-estate/explore
Offshore wind infrastructure (Europe)	EMODNet	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geoviewer/
Power and communication cables	EMODNet	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geoviewer/
Sewage discharge	EMODNet	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geoviewer/
Aggregate extraction	EMODNet	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geoviewer/
Capital/maintenance dredging	EMODNet	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geoviewer/
Spoil dumping	EMODNet	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geoviewer/

4.1.5 Results

In this section we present the long-term classification of North Sea waters with regard to the underlying ecosystem sensitivity to climate change. The resulting spatial data, identifying long-term climate change refugia and hotspots in the North Sea, is freely available in Talbot and Queirós (2024). The underlying analysis included species distribution modelling (biomass) for the commercially relevant species cod, sole, plaice, turbot, sprat and herring; as well as for the high conservation value species oyster, black legged kittiwake, harbour seal, harbour porpoise, tope, spurdog, spotted and thornback rays, sandeels, and minke whale among several others, from the base of the food web to top predators (41 species in total, Table 4.1.1).

The **results under decreasing emissions** (RCP2.6 Figure 4.1.1) suggest that extensive long-term climate change hotspots (blue, all panels) emerge in many areas including conservation sites and fishing grounds. These areas express the concerted impacts of climate change (as emissions decline) as well as those of extractive uses throughout the time series (Fig. 4.1.1 a and c, and trends listed in Table 4.1.1). However, extensive parts of these areas revert to climate change refugia where additional protected areas are put in place under the Global Sustainability scenario (RCP2.6 and SSP1; Figure 4.1.1 a cf. b, and c cf. d). Specifically, Fully Protected and Highly Protected Areas (Figure 4.1.2). Those new refugia occur where those new protected sites are present, with the exception of the east coast of Scotland and England. Because this analysis accounted for the response of 41 species and species groups across the food web (Table 4.1.1.) to simulated scenarios, those climate change refugia reflect an increase in the biomass of most species. Species increasing in biomass include several of high conservation value, such as spurdog (throughout), thornback and spotted ray, common skate and cuckoo ray, the southern population of harbour seals, remnant populations of oysters (most areas, data not shown) but this was not the case for other species such as harbour porpoise. Some high conservation status species, such as the endangered minke whale, and the vulnerable black-legged kittiwakes, struggled despite new protections and declining emissions, fairing better only in small isolated patches corresponding to conservation sites with a high level of restrictions in place (in the SW, SE, and the east of the North Sea, respectively; Figure 4.1.2). Where those ecosystem wide climate change refugia expand beyond conservation sites (Figure 4.1.1 b and d), they are likely to also create benefits for fisheries, and this is especially true in the NW of the North Sea, where species such as blue whiting, wolf-fish, Norway pout, dab, haddock and whiting (and their predators) thrive. Cod appears to thrive (not shown) long-term not in the areas closed specifically to protect spawning cod from fisheries (Fig.4.1.2b), but rather in areas immediately to the south, closed from 2030 as FPAs and HPAs under the Global Sustainability scenario (Figure 4.1.1 a cf. b, and Figure 4.1.2 d), possibly benefitting from concurrent local increases in prey species such as Norway pout and small fish (not shown). Several other areas transit from one classification to another (i.e. from hotspots to refugia) but these are shorter lived (white areas, Figure 4.1.1 b and d). However, in some cases, refugia emerge in areas heavily impacted, at present, by extractive and polluting sectors, the impacts of which are not captured by the model used to generate the data analysed (Table 4.1.1). Those impacts, if not managed into the future, hold the potential to limit the realisation the ecosystem benefits that emerge in this analysis, particularly along the British, Danish, German, Dutch and Belgian coasts (Figure 4.1.1 b and d), where new refugia emerge through the limitation of fisheries, and an investment in conservation and restoration.

Under RCP8.5 and no additional management measures, ecosystem-wide climate change hotspots are also widely distributed (blue, Figure 4.1.3) relative to RCP2.6 (Figure 4.1.1a), and there are more extensive climate impacts along the Shetland and Orkney isles of Scotland. There are strong reductions in the biomass of many species. However, in the Ling Bank there appears to be a reversal of trends, with a few climate resilient species declining (such as the critically endangered tope, and the

commercially valuable horse mackerel, oysters, and blue whiting) and climate sensitive species increasing (such as grey seal, the vulnerable spurdog, and the commercially valuable lemon sole, long rough dab, Norway pout, dab, halibut, whiting and witch). This suggests that there is a less pronounced long term seabed water temperature trend in this area under this scenario. Assessing the bottom seawater temperature and dissolved oxygen trends from the CMIP6 ensemble used to force this model (Figure 4.1.4) suggests indeed that the Ling Bank experiences near zero change in both variables or slight cooling and oxygenation during large periods of the year by the end of the century under RCP8.5, which may explain the projected reversal of expected climate-driven species trends

Figure 4.1.1. Long-term classification of the North Sea ecosystem with regard to climate change sensitivity, between 2026-2069, under the RCP 2.6 Status Quo scenario (a and c) and the Global Sustainability scenario (b and d, which has the same climate projection RCP2.6 but also includes low barriers to climate change adaptation and mitigation, additional fisheries management measures and new MPAs as shown in Figure 4.1.2). GIS data representing the current distribution of maritime activity sectors are overlaid on the above classifications (keys in figures), including those that may

provide some degree of protection from extractive uses (top, a and b) or those that represent additional sources of impacts (bottom, c and d).

Figure 4.1.2. Top: fisheries closures implemented in all North Sea scenarios, including year-round beam trawl closures to protect flatfish (a, red); November to April seasonal closures to protect cod (b, white); and year-round bottom trawling ban to protect sandeel (c, green and blue). Bottom: Highly Protected Areas (“HPA”, green) and Fully Protected Areas (“FPA”, blue) as implemented in the named FutureMARES scenarios (d, e, f). HPA allow for non-industrial artisanal fisheries to be carried out using gears (pots, hooks and lines) that do not damage the seabed and do not operate with large trawls, whilst FPA are no-take zones (all fisheries banned). Reprinted with permission, from Coll, Lynam et al. (2024).

Figure 4.1.3. Long-term classification of the North Sea marine ecosystem with regard to climate change sensitivity, between 2026-2069, under RCP 8.5: Status Quo scenario (left, a and d); National Enterprise scenario (middle, b and e); and World Markets scenario (right, c and f). GIS data representing the current distribution of maritime activity sectors overlaid (keys in figures), including those that may provide some degree of protection from extractive uses (top) or those that represent additional sources of impacts (bottom). Spatial interventions simulated in scenarios are also shown.

Figure 4.1.4. Contrast between 1995-2014 and 2081-2100 seasonal mean bottom seawater temperatures ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), based on the CMIP6 ensemble data used to force the North Sea food web model, from which projections are analysed here (Table 4.1.1). Positive values indicate warming. Source: Momme Butenschön, CMCC.

in the region, and the emergence of a climate change refuge (Figure 4.1.3a and c). This area currently holds a high density of oil and gas platforms which could limit the realisation of some ecosystem benefits (such as food provisioning) of these climate change refugia under higher emission.

The extent of this climate change refuge expands as species respond to additional restrictions to fisheries activity under the **National Enterprise scenario** when MPAs are introduced, although fishing effort gradually increases into the far future and reaches higher levels by 2070 than during the 2020s (Figure 4.1.3b and e; Figure 4.1.2f). This climate change refuge contracts again under **World Markets** despite a greater extent of spatial protection, since fishing effort increases more rapidly into the future, with higher levels by 2060 than during the 2020s (Figure 4.1.3 c and e; Figure 4.1.2e). These results suggest that even under very high emissions (RCP8.5) the establishment of fully protected areas has clear localised effects on the ecosystem, with new refugia emerging in these sites under National Enterprise, along the Scottish isles and off the east coast of Scotland (if not in the Dogger Bank). Species benefitting from those restrictions on fishing, and leading to the emergence of climate change refugia, are distributed across the food web and the water column, including commercially valuable Norway lobster (*Nephrops*), herring, whiting, several flatfish species (isles only) and sprat; as well as high conservation value species such as spurdog and tope; and bycatch species such as gurnards. Refugia are also observed under National Enterprise along the eastern North Sea, where new conservation sites are simulated in coastal areas. Indeed, refugia are extensive along the Norwegian coast, but only smaller, Fully Protected Areas (no take zones) lead to refugia emergence further south, along the Danish and Dutch coasts (Figures 4.1.2e, 4.1.3b,e). Herring, gurnards, sandeels and sprat increase along the Norwegian coast, leading to an increase in foraging seabirds (data not shown), and some flatfish species also increase. In the Danish coast, seals increase locally with herring, sprat and some commercially valuable demersal fish (data not shown). In the Dutch coast, refugia emerge with the increase in predominantly commercially valuable and by-catch demersal and benthic species like turbot, dragonets, flounder, but also vulnerable species such as

tope, skate, thornback and spotted rays. In the latter areas, sewage outfall and dredging may affect these climate-resilience benefits generated by fisheries restrictions (Dethlefsen and Tiews 1985, Todd, Todd et al. 2015, Wenger, Harvey et al. 2017).

Under the **World Markets scenario**, more extensive areas with restrictions on fisheries are simulated across the North Sea than in the other two RCP8.5 scenarios (Figure 4.1.3.e) and these conservation sites lead to the emergence of extensive climate change refugia (Figure 4.1.4c and f). Large conservation areas simulated in the northern North Sea (in the Viking bank region and the Norwegian Sea) and the central and southern North Sea (Figure 4.1.4 c and f) lead to a reversal of expected (climate-driven) trends for most species considered, across the food web and from pelagic to benthic species. Cold-affiliated species thriving in these refugia include cod, Norway lobster, sprat, diving seabirds, and harbour seals among others (Table 4.1.1, data not shown). **This likely indicates that the removal of fishing pressure from many species expected to decline due to climate change (Table 4.1.1) may be sufficient to allow them to persist under experienced climate conditions, with positive effects percolating across the food web.** Some warm-affiliated species (such as angler fish and horse mackerel) only thrive in these climate refugia within protected sites (data not shown), with declines elsewhere, despite their expected higher resilience to climate change (Table 4.1.1, and possibly also due to fishing pressure outside protected sites. Extensive oil and gas operations, as well as fishing and other extractive and polluting uses overlap with many sites identified in the World Markets Scenario as hosting climate change refugia (Figure 4.1.4f). Wind farms also operate in some of those areas, especially in the southern North Sea (Figure 4.1.4c). These activities may thus curb some of the potentially positive effects of protected areas in increasing the climate-resilience of the North Sea ecosystem under higher emissions, at least for some groups of species (Dethlefsen and Tiews 1985, Holdway 2002, Todd, Todd et al. 2015, Wenger, Harvey et al. 2017, Watson, Somerfield et al. 2024), without additional management measures.

4.1.6 Discussion

The key finding that emerges from the analysis of food web modelling projections is that fully protected areas and highly protected areas offer the potential to deliver climate-resilient conservation in the North Sea, for decades to come, for species sensitive to climate change, even under higher emissions that widely exceed the Paris Agreement target (i.e. RCP8.5, Secretariat of the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change 2015). The simulated scenarios analysed here express a wide range of possible futures for the North Sea ecosystem with regard to greenhouse gas emissions trajectories. This indicates that protected areas would, in the regions simulated, potentially represent no-regrets decisions that benefit the wild species and habitats, across the food web. As many of the species included in the analysis have high commercial value, the climate-resilience delivered by protected areas (illustrated by the presence of climate refugia) may also benefit the fishing sector, especially in areas where refugia were seen to over-spill beyond protected areas. However, even if the warming target for the Paris agreement is only moderately exceeded (i.e. RCP2.6), strongly negative declines were estimated across the food web in most areas of the North Sea. This is likely because direct and indirect mortality caused by fishing (reversed in simulated protected areas) has a synergistic effect with mortality and loss of habitat for climate sensitive species without additional conservation measures (i.e. RCP2.6 status quo scenario). Even species expected to be climate resilient declined in many areas as a result, leading to the emergence of climate change hotspots across vast areas of the North Sea under both emissions trajectories explored. Because new conservation sites simulated in the projections analysed here are introduced in 2030, this study offers important information to support the delivery of the EU Biodiversity

Strategy, and national policies implemented in the North Sea bordering nations in their response to it. However, it is noteworthy that many of the refugia areas emerged in sites that currently host human activities which will not be compatible with co-location of fully protected areas due to their negative effects on marine biota (Dethlefsen and Tiews 1985, Holdway 2002, Todd, Todd et al. 2015, Wenger, Harvey et al. 2017, Watson, Somerfield et al. 2024). Our results indicate that those effects may thus hamper the benefits of fisheries restrictions, at least for some of the species locally, and so it is possible that the ecosystem-wide climate resilience estimated here for those areas may be overly optimistic in some sites. This result highlights the importance of ecosystem-based approaches, delivered through marine spatial planning (“MSP”), especially with regard to enabling the climate resilience of species and habitats through NBS.

Previous studies explored the potential implications of climate change for effective marine spatial planning, conservation and fisheries in the North Sea (Queirós, Huebert et al. 2016), and projected effects of climate change on North Sea seabed and fish assemblages and food web (Lynam and Mackinson 2015, Queirós, Fernandes et al. 2018, Weinert, Mathis et al. 2021, Thompson, Couce et al. 2023). This updated study, using a regionally set up food web model (Coll, Lynam et al. 2024) may now better support the review phase of planning mechanisms for the North Sea bordering nations, in response to the EU Marine Spatial Planning Directive (2014/89/EU), as well as the United Kingdom’s Marine Policy Statement (e.g. HM Government 2011, DEFRA 2014). Climate change and the ambition to promote climate change resilience are now routinely considered as part of EU and UK marine planning (e.g. Wåhlstrom, Pålsson et al. 2020, DEFRA 2021). However, our findings indicate that individual species and communities can show complex responses to climate change and human activities, which are not necessarily evident from the analysis physical climate change modelling (e.g. temperature, pH), more often considered in MSP. This was particularly evident where climate sensitive species were found to thrive only when decreased fishing pressure and food web interactions allowed for, and when warm affiliated species were found to fair poorly under higher emissions, unless fishing restriction were also implemented.

Designing spatial management policies and interventions that benefit species of conservation and commercial value under climate change (i.e. MPAs, restoration, MSP) is thus likely to require the consideration of the type of species and food web modelling data we analysed here. The evidence provided here may therefore help inform on how best to implement climate-adaptive MSP, and climate-adaptive conservation mechanisms in the North Sea: specifically, by helping inform the design of spatially explicit policies that account for the joint responses, of a wide range of wild species and species groups of conservation and commercial value, to climate change and fisheries, in the context of other maritime activity sectors. Those policies and interventions are still lacking but are necessary to truly support a sustainable North Sea in the face of an uncertain, changing climate, and to help deliver ambitions set out in National Adaptation Plans of bordering nations. These policies will be necessary to help meet Europe’s delivery of its own biodiversity targets, those of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals 13 and 14, and the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework.

4.2 The Western Mediterranean Sea (Storyline group 30, 31, 33)

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4.2.1 Regional context

The Western Mediterranean Sea hosts high species and habitat diversity, with many endemic and at-risk species, including seabirds, marine turtles, marine mammals, chondrichthyans, finfish, invertebrates and primary producers (Coll, Steenbeek et al. 2015). However, marine protected areas (fully, highly, moderately or poorly protected) cover less than 1% of the region (Castro-Cadenas, Barreiros et al. *In review*).

Climate change in the Western Mediterranean Sea is projected to intensify more rapidly than the average global mean, and available trends indicate increasingly more frequent and intense marine heat wave events (Salat, Pascual et al. 2019). The impacts of these changes on marine biota are already being seen: 1) a meridionalisation of taxa reflecting thermophilic species faring better than temperate ones; 2) mass mortality events of sessile invertebrates in coralligenous communities; 3) increases in small sized of phytoplankton; 4) proliferation of gelatinous carnivore plankton, including jellyfish ; and (5) ocean acidification impacting many calcifying organisms. These effects, combined with other anthropogenic impacts such as high exploitation, are expected to ultimately affect local ecosystem services, especially the production of living resources (Ramírez, Pennino et al. 2021).

Overexploitation of fishing resources is among the most important pressures in the region, along with biodiversity and habitat loss. Yet fisheries, aquaculture and tourism are key economic activities in the area (Fernandes, Ralph et al. 2017, Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations 2023). This context suggest there is a pressing need to develop climate resilient approaches to marine conservation in the Western Mediterranean Sea, that may support biologically important local biodiversity and economically important dependant fisheries, into coming decades.

4.2.2 Modelling data used

The modelling datasets analysed within the context of this storyline, as well as the expected climate-driven trend for each modelling variable analysed in the climate signal detection spatial meta-analysis algorithm (section 2.4), are summarised below in Table 4.2.1. This dataset includes future projections under all five scenarios (section 2.2) for 34 species or species groups for which clear climate-driven trends could be extracted from the peer review literature (necessary to setup the climate signal detection algorithm, section 2.4). These projections derive from model runs for the regionally parameterised Western Mediterranean Sea EwE food web model described in Coll, Lynam et al. (2024), and which included a total of 93 functional groups. The model was validated against observations (catch or biomass trends) for 24 of those functional groups and in the majority of those it was found to have good skill at the basin level (species or species groups, Figure 48 in Coll, Lynam et al. (2024)).

Modelling projections were generated employing not only different degrees of possible climate change, in line with different greenhouse gas emissions trajectories, but also different degrees of spatial management measures implemented in scenarios (section 2.2). These scenarios simulated the implementation of new conservation sites with different degrees of restrictions, as well as fisheries closures (with restrictions imposed on different types of gears, Figure 4.2.1). They also included the effects of nature-based solutions, that is, specific targets for restoration and conservation of seagrass

beds and coralligenous communities. Scenarios further included different degrees of fishing effort simulated. Both status quo scenarios (RCP2.6 and 8.5) employed baseline fishing mortality. Contrastingly, under the Global Sustainability (SSP1.2.6) scenario, fishing effort was imposed to ensure mortality was consistent with Maximum Sustainable Yield for multiple species, and across multiple fleets when they targeted the same individual species, both of which then drove compensatory mechanisms between species across the food web, including predator prey dynamics (Coll, Lynam et al. 2024). In projections employing the National Enterprise and World Markets scenarios (SSP3.8.5 and SSP5.8.5 respectively), fishing effort increased annually by 0.44% and 0.88%, respectively, representing technological development, per Damalas, Maravelias and Kavadas (2014).

In each cell of the common model domain, and for each scenario and each 20 year period between the present and the final part of the 21st century (section 2.4), the climate signal detection algorithm then built one spatial meta-analysis model that analysed all modelling layers together (Table 4.2.1), testing the null hypothesis that change between the present 20 year period and each future 20 year period is zero. Please see section 2.4 for a detailed description of the analysis methodology employed.

Table 4.2.1: Description of modelling data analysed here for the Western Mediterranean Sea storyline group. "latmin": lowest value of latitude in the model domain; "latmax": highest value of latitude in the model domain; "lonmin": lowest value of longitude in the model domain; "lonmax": highest value of longitude in the model domain. "CC" climate change. "SST" sea surface temperature.

Variable	Model	Spatial extent (latmin - latmax; lonmin-lonmax)	Resolution	Time slice	Data provider	Expected climate trend
Anglerfish (<i>Lophius budegassa</i>, <i>Lophius piscatorius</i>) - biomass	Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace	34.39 to 44.89; -5.64 to 16.36	0.15*0.15	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Marta Coll, ICM-CSIC	<i>Lophius budegassa</i> expected to decrease.. <i>L. piscatorius</i> possibly stable (Pita, Mouillot et al. 2021)
<i>Aristaeomorpha foliacea</i> (giant red shrimp) - biomass	Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace	34.39 to 44.89; -5.64 to 16.36	0.15*0.15	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Marta Coll, ICM-CSIC	Increase (Maiorano, Capezzuto et al. 2022)
<i>Aristeus antennatus</i> (blue and red shrimp)- biomass	Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace	34.39 to 44.89; -5.64 to 16.36	0.15*0.15	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Marta Coll, ICM-CSIC	Decrease. Likely due to warming and increasing salinity in deep Med waters (Cartes, López-Pérez and Carbonell 2018). Salinity and temperature changes recorded in (Schroeder, Chiggiato et al. 2016). Considered to be fairly vulnerable to climate change in several regions of the Mediterranean (Aragão, López-López et al. 2021)
<i>Balaenoptera physalus</i> (Fin whale)- biomass	Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace	34.39 to 44.89; -5.64 to 16.36	0.15*0.15	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Marta Coll, ICM-CSIC	Decrease. (Chatzimentor, Doxa et al. 2023). Climate driven changes in distribution of key prey species <i>Meganyctiphanes norvegica</i> likely to be a problem (Gambaiani, Mayol et al. 2009)
<i>Caretta caretta</i> (Loggerhead turtle)- biomass	Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace	34.39 to 44.89; -5.64 to 16.36	0.15*0.15	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Marta Coll, ICM-CSIC	Decrease. (Chatzimentor, Doxa et al. 2023).
<i>Conger conger</i> (European conger eel)- biomass	Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace	34.39 to 44.89; -5.64 to 16.36	0.15*0.15	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Marta Coll, ICM-CSIC	Increase. (Aragão, López-López et al. 2021)

<i>Corallium rubrum</i> (red coral)- biomass	Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace	34.39 to 44.89; -5.64 to 16.36	0.15*0.15	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Marta Coll, ICM-CSIC	Decrease. (Cerrano, Cardini et al. 2013).
<i>Delphinus delphis</i> (Short-beaked common dolphin)- biomass	Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace	34.39 to 44.89; -5.64 to 16.36	0.15*0.15	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Marta Coll, ICM-CSIC	Decrease. (Chatzimentor, Doxa et al. 2023)Table S2 in supplementary info)
<i>Dentex dentex</i> (common dentex)- biomass	Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace	34.39 to 44.89; -5.64 to 16.36	0.15*0.15	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Marta Coll, ICM-CSIC	Decrease. (Garcia, Pasqualini et al. 2022)
<i>Diplodus vulgaris</i> (common two-banded seabream)- biomass	Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace	34.39 to 44.89; -5.64 to 16.36	0.15*0.15	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Marta Coll, ICM-CSIC	Decrease. (Raventos, Torrado et al. 2021)
<i>Engraulis encrasicolus</i> (European anchovy) - adult- biomass	Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace	34.39 to 44.89; -5.64 to 16.36	0.15*0.15	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Marta Coll, ICM-CSIC	Decrease egg abundance and spawning habitat for this species both decreased in the Med (Maynou, Sabatés and Raya 2020)
<i>Galeus melastomus</i> (blackmouth catshark)- biomass	Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace	34.39 to 44.89; -5.64 to 16.36	0.15*0.15	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Marta Coll, ICM-CSIC	Decrease. (Pita, Mouillot et al. 2021)
Groupers (<i>Epinephelus aeneus</i>, <i>Epinephelus costae</i>, <i>Epinephelus marginatus</i>)- biomass	Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace	34.39 to 44.89; -5.64 to 16.36	0.15*0.15	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Marta Coll, ICM-CSIC	Increase.E. aeneus and E. marginatus expanding range north in the Med due to warming temps (Sbragaglia, Espasandín et al. 2024), Azzurro et al, 2022. Front.Mar.Sci. 9)

<i>Hommarus gammarus</i> (European lobster)- biomass	Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace	34.39 to 44.89; -5.64 to 16.36	0.15*0.15	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Marta Coll, ICM-CSIC	Decrease. (Schmalenbach and Franke 2010, Pere, Marengo et al. 2019).
Mackerels (<i>Scomber scombrus</i>, <i>Scomber colias</i>, <i>Scomberesox saurus saurus</i>)- biomass	Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace	34.39 to 44.89; -5.64 to 16.36	0.15*0.15	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Marta Coll, ICM-CSIC	Decrease <i>Scomber colias</i> optimum habitat has already decreased in Western Med due to CC (Ouled-Cheikh, Coll et al. 2022). <i>Scomber scomber</i> catches have decreased in the Med over the last 20 yrs, at least some of which has been linked to warming (Valente, Moro et al. 2023)
<i>Merluccius merluccius</i> (European hake) - juvenile- biomass	Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace	34.39 to 44.89; -5.64 to 16.36	0.15*0.15	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Marta Coll, ICM-CSIC	Decrease (Sioni, Zupa et al. 2019, Maiorano, Capezzuto et al. 2022)
<i>Micromesistius poutassou</i> (blue whiting) - biomass	Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace	34.39 to 44.89; -5.64 to 16.36	0.15*0.15	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Marta Coll, ICM-CSIC	Decrease (Valente, Moro et al. 2023)
<i>Mullus barbatus</i> (Red mullet)- biomass	Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace	34.39 to 44.89; -5.64 to 16.36	0.15*0.15	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Marta Coll, ICM-CSIC	Increase (Valente, Moro et al. 2023)
<i>Mullus surmuletus</i> (Surmullet)- biomass	Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace	34.39 to 44.89; -5.64 to 16.36	0.15*0.15	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Marta Coll, ICM-CSIC	Decrease. (Pita, Mouillot et al. 2021)

<i>Nephrops norvegicus</i> (Norway lobster)	Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace	34.39 to 44.89; -5.64 to 16.36	0.15*0.15	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Marta Coll, ICM-CSIC	Decrease. (Hernroth, Sköld et al. 2012, Sbrana, Zupa et al. 2019)
Other commercial large demersal fish (<i>Molva dypterygia, Molva macrophthalma, Molva molva, Polyprion americanus</i>)- biomass	Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace	34.39 to 44.89; -5.64 to 16.36	0.15*0.15	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Marta Coll, ICM-CSIC	Decrease. (Lloret, Serrat et al. 2021)
<i>Pagellus erythrinus</i> (common pandora)- biomass	Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace	34.39 to 44.89; -5.64 to 16.36	0.15*0.15	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Marta Coll, ICM-CSIC	Decrease. (Pruckner, Bedford et al. 2022)). Loss in Posidonia may negatively affect occurrences
<i>Parapenaeus longirostris</i> (deep-water rose shrimp)- biomass	Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace	34.39 to 44.89; -5.64 to 16.36	0.15*0.15	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Marta Coll, ICM-CSIC	Increase (Maiorano, Capezzuto et al. 2022)
<i>Sardina pilchardus</i> (European sardine)- adult- biomass	Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace	34.39 to 44.89; -5.64 to 16.36	0.15*0.15	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Marta Coll, ICM-CSIC	Decrease. (Pennino, Coll et al. 2020)
<i>Sardinella aurita</i> (Round sardinella)- biomass	Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace	34.39 to 44.89; -5.64 to 16.36	0.15*0.15	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Marta Coll, ICM-CSIC	Increase (Valente, Moro et al. 2023)
<i>Scorpaena scrofa</i> (Red scorpion fish)- biomass	Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace	34.39 to 44.89; -5.64 to 16.36	0.15*0.15	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Marta Coll, ICM-CSIC	Decrease. (Pruckner, Bedford et al. 2022)). Loss in Posidonia may negatively affect occurrences
<i>Scyliorhinus canicula</i> (Small spotted catshark)- biomass	Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace	34.39 to 44.89; -5.64 to 16.36	0.15*0.15	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Marta Coll, ICM-CSIC	Decrease. (Pita, Mouillot et al. 2021)

<p><i>Stenella coeruleoalba</i> (Striped dolphin)- biomass</p>	<p>Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace</p>	<p>34.39 to 44.89; -5.64 to 16.36</p>	<p>0.15*0.15</p>	<p>2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)</p>	<p>Marta Coll, ICM-CSIC</p>	<p>Decrease. Key species in diet matrix are anchovy, sardine, hake, Molva sp. and Sparids, All of which may decline with CC (see refs for those species in this table) (Gambaiani, Mayol et al. 2009)</p>
<p><i>Strongylocentrotus purpuratus</i> (Purple sea urchin)- biomass</p>	<p>Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace</p>	<p>34.39 to 44.89; -5.64 to 16.36</p>	<p>0.15*0.15</p>	<p>2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)</p>	<p>Marta Coll, ICM-CSIC</p>	<p>Decrease. (Leach, BuyanUrt and Hofmann 2021, Zhang, Li et al. 2022)</p>
<p>Terns (<i>Sterna albifrons</i>, <i>Sterna caspia</i>, <i>Sterna hirundo</i>, <i>Sterna nilotica</i>, <i>Sterna sandvicensis</i>)- biomass</p>	<p>Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace</p>	<p>34.39 to 44.89; -5.64 to 16.36</p>	<p>0.15*0.15</p>	<p>2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)</p>	<p>Marta Coll, ICM-CSIC</p>	<p>Decrease. Declines of <i>S. hirundo</i> linked to inundation of nesting sites due to sea level rise (Scarton 2010). Warmer temps have been linked to lower prey availability and decreased breeding success in <i>S. albifrons</i>. (Häkkinen, Petrovan et al. 2023). <i>S. sandvicensis</i> nests on low lying coastal ground so could be vulnerable to sea level rise (Hakkinen et al, 2023. Seabirds in NE Atlantic). Caspian tern chicks sensitive to MHW, which have caused mass mortalities in the US. They are also surface feeders so dispersal of prey to deeper waters in response to climate induced warming may prevent effective foraging (Hakkinen et al, 2023. Seabirds in NE Atlantic).</p>
<p><i>Thunnus thynnus</i> (bluefin tuna)- biomass</p>	<p>Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace</p>	<p>34.39 to 44.89; -5.64 to 16.36</p>	<p>0.15*0.15</p>	<p>2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)</p>	<p>Marta Coll, ICM-CSIC</p>	<p>Decrease. (Pita, Mouillot et al. 2021, Ouled-Cheikh, Coll et al. 2022)</p>

<p><i>Tursiops truncatus</i> (bottlenose dolphin)- biomass</p>	<p>Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace</p>	<p>34.39 to 44.89; -5.64 to 16.36</p>	<p>0.15*0.15</p>	<p>2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)</p>	<p>Marta Coll, ICM-CSIC</p>	<p>Decrease. (La Manna, Ronchetti et al. 2023). Hake a key prey species in diet matrix which might decline in the Med (see refs for that species in this table). Also "other commercial large demersals" (mostly Molva) which are also likely to decline</p>
<p><i>Xiphias gladius</i> (Swordfish)- biomass</p>	<p>Ecosim with Ecopath and Ecospace</p>	<p>34.39 to 44.89; -5.64 to 16.36</p>	<p>0.15*0.15</p>	<p>2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)</p>	<p>Marta Coll, ICM-CSIC</p>	<p>Decrease. (Ouled-Cheikh, Coll et al. 2022)</p>

Figure 4.2.1: Configuration of MPAs and Fisheries Closures (FC) implemented in Western Mediterranean Sea scenarios used in model projections. Fully Protected Areas (FPAs) and Highly Protected Areas (HPAs): a) Status Quo; b) Global Sustainability, c) National Enterprise, and d) World Markets. Fisheries Restriction Areas (FRA) and Essential Fish Habitat (EFH) closures: e) Status Quo; f) Global Sustainability, g) World Markets. The National Enterprise scenario does not include additional closures after the 2021. Reprinted with permission, from Coll, Lynam et al. (2024).

4.2.3 GIS datasets used

Table 4.2.2: GIS datasets used to frame the modelling analysis results in the context of the region's blue economy.

Dataset	Data provider	Available at
Designated marine conservation areas	UNEP-WCMC and IUCN	https://www.protectedplanet.net/en/search-areas?geo_type=site
Power and communications cables	EMODnet	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geoviewer/
Offshore wind infrastructure	EMODnet	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geoviewer/
Ocean energy sites	EMODnet	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geoviewer/
Capital and maintenance dredging	EMODnet	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geoviewer/
Sewage outfall	EMODnet	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geoviewer/
Demersal fishing	Global Fishing Watch	https://globalfishingwatch.org/data-download/datasets/public-fishing-effort
Pelagic fishing	Global Fishing Watch	https://globalfishingwatch.org/data-download/datasets/public-fishing-effort
Aggregate extraction	EMODnet	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geoviewer/

4.2.4 Results

The spatial data resulting from these analyses, identifying long-term climate change refugia and hotspots in the Western Mediterranean Sea, is freely available in Talbot and Queirós (2024). The most notable message resulting from the analysis of food web modelling projections this area is the extensive emergence of climate change refugia, under both possible emissions futures considered (RCP2.6 and 8.5), and without further management actions (status quo scenarios, Figure 4.2.2a and 4.2.3a). These results emerge even though 28 out of 34 species and species groups analysed were expected to experience climate-driven declines (Table 4.2.1). The modelled biomass of several species reflected changes expected based on climate change literature analysis (Table 4.2.1). Those included several species with high commercial and conservation value, including (e.g. under status quo RCP8.5) blue fin tuna (*Thunnus thynnus*, declines), groupers (*Epinephelus spp.* increase except in the Alboran Sea), loggerhead turtles (*Caretta caretta*, biomass declines across the region), and swordfish (biomass declines over most areas, though it increases coastally). The model validation work described in Coll, Lynam et al. (2024) indicates that projections for those species (excluding groupers) had moderate to good skill at the basin scale.

Much sub-regional variability in species trends was however observed, leading to unexpected overall trends in food web climate sensitivity in some areas (i.e. refugia emergence, Figure 4.2.2). Some species which are already declining in the wild were here projected to increase in several areas even under higher emissions (Figure 4.2.2 a and 4.2.3a) including mackerels (*Scomber scomber*, biomass decline in the Alboran Sea and increases everywhere else cf. Valente et al. 2023), bottlenose dolphin

(*Tursiops truncatus*, biomass increases everywhere *cf.* La Manna et al. 2023), fin whale (*Balaenoptera physalus*, biomass increases everywhere *cf.* Chatzimentor et al., 2022), and Norway lobster (*Nephrops norvegicus*, biomass only projected to decline in the Ligurian and the Tyrrhenian Seas *cf.* Sbrana et al. 2019), red mullet (*Mullus barbatus*, biomass declines in most areas, but increases coastally and in the Alboran Sea), among others, even under RCP8.5 (data not shown). In turn, the biomass of several species which are projected to thrive in a warmer Mediterranean Sea appeared to fair less well in several areas, including the European conger eel (*Conger conger*, only increases in the Balearic Sea *cf.* Aragao et al. 2022) and round sardinella (*Sardinella aurita* only increases in the Balearic Sea *cf.* Valente et al. 2023), even under RCP8.5.

These results may have several explanations. First, they may occur if environmental projections used as input in the food web model represent milder, or different, environmental conditions than what is expected to occur based on observations (Table 4.2.1). Results from Figure 11 in Butenschön and Kristiansen (2023) suggests this is not the case at the regional scale, with correlation found (lower in Summer) between the CMIP6 ensemble used to drive the food web model, and observations (CORA 5.2 dataset, Szekely, Gouillon et al. 2019, Coll, Lynam et al. 2024). However, as sub-regional trends varied, it is possible different trends in species may occur in areas where environmental thresholds (especially for temperature and salinity) were not exceeded, relative to species preference profiles extracted from the Aquamaps model and used here to setup the food web model (Kaschner, Kesner-Reyes et al. 2019, Coll, Lynam et al. 2024). For instance, the Alboran Sea has a projected lower warming rate than other areas of the Mediterranean Sea (Figure 17 in Butenschön and Kristiansen 2023), which may explain why some warming sensitive species cited above declined elsewhere but not there. This may also explain why some more warming resilient species did not thrive there. Sub-regional variability in environmental drivers, however, cannot explain why several species were found to have projected trends in the Balearic sea that are different to those expected based on literature review (Table 4.2.1). It is possible, in those cases, that food web interactions or fishing effort impacts (leading to compensatory food web dynamics across species, Fig.4.2.2) may have led to the projected departure from trends expected based on climate change literature review (Table 4.2.1). For instance, the projected increase in Norway lobster biomass (*Nephrops norvegicus*) contrary to its expected climate-driven trend (table 4.2.1) could have derived from a release from competition and predation due to the effect of trawling on predators and competitors, as noted in Coll, Lynam et al. (2024).

The simulation of further changes to management actions, introduced in the other three scenarios, affected this widespread pattern of climate resilience at the ecosystem level (Figure 4.2.2 b and d; Figure 4.2.3). For instance, Highly Protected Areas and Fully Protected areas (with implicit effects on simulated conservation and restoration of seagrass and coralligenous habitats) substantially improved overall climate outcomes for the food web, with areas initially classified as refugia under RCP2.6 status quo scenario now becoming bright spots. This was observed throughout coastal areas in the Alboran, Balearic, Ligurian and Tyrrhenian Sea and the coast of Corsica, though not in West coast of Sardinia (status quo Figure 4.2.2a *cf.* Global Sustainability scenario Figure 4.2.3a). In some areas, it is more apparent that bringing fishing effort to MSY across species had positive effects on the food web outside of simulated new conservation sites (e.g. in the Alboran, Balearic and Tyrrhenian Seas, RCP2.6 *cf.* SSP1-2.6, Figure 4.2.2a *cf.* b). Furthermore, some open sea areas which emerged as refugia without additional management measures under RCP2.6 (especially in the Balearic Sea, Figure 4.2.2a and b) oscillated between this classification and bright spots over time, leading to no long-term classification of these areas as one or the other. This is despite generally positive responses of the food web to climate over time under this scenario (white areas in Figure 4.2.2b and d).

The exception to these spatial patterns were small patches where climate change hotspots emerged in coastal areas throughout the basin, under RCP2.6 (status quo) but not under the Global Sustainability scenario (Figure 4.2.2a cf. b, e.g. west coast of Sardinia, Aeolian Islands and Ligurian sea). These areas are likely the most sensitive to climate change across the basin, as they also emerge as climate change hotspots under the RCP8.5 status quo scenario (Figure 4.2.3a). Under RCP2.6, these and other hotspots disappeared (becoming refugia) due to positive effects across the food web related to: 1) increased efforts in the restoration of habitat forming species like seagrass and coralligenous habitat (e.g. NE coast of the Majorca and Minorca Balearic Islands); and 2) improved multiple species and multiple fleet fisheries management simulated in the Global Sustainability scenario (e.g. Algerian coast, Figure 4.2.2a). These results also suggest that management measures have the potential to limit climate change effects, because for climate sensitive species further impacted by activities such as fisheries, reducing the latter can create sufficient positive effects at the population level, which may propagate across the food web (even under higher emissions e.g. int Balearic islands, Figure 4.2.3a cf. b). Under the Global Sustainability scenario, new climate change hotspots emerged instead in areas adjacent to Fully Protected Areas in the west coast of Sardinia, the Ligurian Sea, and the north coast of Tunisia. This finding possibly expresses the concurrent impacts of changes in fishing pressure and increased competition for resources and predation on some species (Figure 4.2.2.b and d). Species declining in these areas, consistently with trends found in the climate change literature (Figure 4.2.1), included predominantly demersal species of commercial value or bycatch species: anglerfishes (*Lophius* spp.), the blackmouth and small-spotted catsharks (*Galeus melastomus* and *Scyliorhinus canicula*), hake (*Merluccius merluccius*), European and Norway lobster (*Hommarus gammarus* and *Nephrops norvegicus*), red mullet and surmullet (*Mullus barbatus* and *Mullus surmuletus*); but also mackerels (*Scomber* spp.) and striped dolphin (*Stenella coeruleoalba*, individual species data not shown).

In addition to climate change hotspots that emerge under both status quo scenarios, the Ligurian Sea and the NW coast of Corsica emerge as particularly sensitive **across all scenarios simulated under higher emissions** (Figure 4.2.3 (Figure 4.2.3, scenarios RCP8.5 (status quo), SSP3-8.5 (National Enterprise) and SSP5-8.5 (World Markets)). These hotspots reflect declines in climate-sensitive species alongside increased fishing pressure in this specific area: mackerels (*Scomber* spp.) and their predators, which include several dolphin species; as well as swordfish (*Xiphias gladius*), several breams with commercial value (*Pagellus erythrinus*, *Dentex dentex*, *Diplodus vulgaris* (Figures 4.2.3 b and c, individual species data not shown). Climate change bright spots also emerged under high emissions, and those were predominantly located along the East coast of Spain and into the Western portion of the Balearic Sea, and had greater extension as fishing pressure increased offshore (Figure 4.2.3, left to right), emerging also at the highest fishing pressure along the west coast of Sardinia (Figure 4.2.3c and f). This occurred because several species emerged with biomass trends contrary to those expected from the climate change literature, in this area in those scenarios (Table 4.2.1). Such species include conger eel (*Conger conger*, strong decline), mackerels (*Scomber* spp, increase), anglerfishes (*Lophius* spp., increase), Norway and European lobsters (*Nephrops norvegicus* and *Hommarus Gammarus*, increase), red coral (*Corallium rubrum*, increases), several shrimp species, loggerhead turtle (*Caretta caretta*, increases) and terns (*Sterna* spp., increase; individual species data not shown). Environmental patterns in these areas do not seem to explain these changes (Butenschön and Kristiansen 2023), suggesting food web dynamics. Other areas emerge consistently as climate change refugia despite high emissions.

Fig.4.2.2: Long-term classification of the Western Mediterranean Sea ecosystem with regard to climate change sensitivity, between 2026-2069, under the RCP 2.6 Status Quo scenario (left) and the Global Sustainability scenario (RCP2.6 and low barriers to climate change adaptation and mitigation, right). GIS data representing the current distribution of maritime activity sectors overlaid (keys in figures), including those that may provide some degree of protection from extractive uses (a and b) or those that represent additional sources of impacts (c and d).

Figure. 4. 2. 3. Long-term classification of the Mediterranean ecosystem regarding climate change sensitivity, between 2026-2069, under RCP 8.5: Status Quo scenario (a and d); National Enterprise scenario (b and e); and World Markets scenario (c and f). GIS data representing the current distribution of maritime activity sectors overlaid (keys in figures), including those that may provide some degree of protection from extractive uses (top) or those that represent additional sources of impacts (bottom).

Discussion

Two main messages emerge from the analysis of food web modelling for the western Mediterranean Sea. First, modelling analyses suggest that there is ample opportunity for climate-resilient conservation of this ecosystem within the explored possible futures. Some trends could be explained directly by sub-regional differences in the magnitude of climate change expressed by different scenarios; many results were otherwise explained by species interactions across the food web; and some further were due to the simulation of different management scenarios, that included restoration, conservation, and fishing sustainability measures. As noted by others (Lawlor, Comte et al. 2024), these results illustrate that understanding, and managing, the impacts of climate change on marine communities and ecosystems is substantially more complex than understanding patterns in physical climate change, such as its velocity. Here, we illustrate the importance of food web modelling in this context. Accounting for species interactions may be a vital step towards projecting the climate resilience of individual species as well as that of assemblages in nature, and thus an important step toward informing future-proofed conservation and/or exploitation plans. Indeed, complex biological effects associated with changing species fitness under climate change were found to propagate upwards and downwards through the food web. Observational studies on such interactions under climate change are less common (Queirós, Fernandes et al. 2015). But those data are required to ensure that projections from models such as the one used here are meaningful and well-grounded in real-world evidence about complex food web interactions in a changing ocean landscape.

Our second key finding suggests that ecosystem-based management requires the consideration of food web interactions under climate change especially in areas where populations and communities are additionally impacted by human activities, such as fishing. It is recognised that that climate change can act synergistically with fisheries to impact individual species life-history, population dynamics and, ultimately, evolutionary processes (e.g. Waples and Audzijonyte 2016). In contrast, food web wide interactions resulting from those synergies are much less well understood. Our findings are consistent with those of others, suggesting that climate-fisheries synergies have the potential to determine management outcomes, especially the climate-resilience of whole communities and the effectiveness of adaptation policy design for sectors such as fisheries and conservation (Queirós, Talbot et al. 2024).

Overall, this study suggests that there is a potential future for climate-resilient management of the Western Mediterranean. It also emphasises how curbing human activities may provide these sensitive ecosystems with important additional resource to sustain the unwavering ecological pressure imposed by human-driven climate change.

5 Sub-regional nature-based solutions: Conservation of commercially valuable marine and estuarine opportunistic fish species (Storyline group 16, 17)

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5.1 Regional context

Marine-estuarine opportunist (MEO) fish, which occur on the continental shelf and use estuaries and shallow coastal areas as nurseries. These species are highly valuable for commercial and recreational

fisheries. In the North-East Atlantic region, where the majority of Northern European fisheries operate, key MEO fish stocks face changes in continental, estuarine and marine environmental drivers, due to climate change and other human-related activities. These changes in environmental conditions are likely to result in changes in distribution of these species as they move to track suitable habitat conditions (Maltby, Rutterford et al. 2020). An understanding of the magnitude of these (at sea) distributional range-shifts by these functionally important species will be crucial in order to ensure that these species can be managed effectively and sustainably across the land-sea continuum, and to guarantee the long-term delivery of ecosystem services they support (Semmens, Diffendorfer et al. 2011).

5.2 Biological modelling datasets used

Modelling layers used in this analysis were environment suitability distribution projections for six of the main benthic-demersal marine-estuarine opportunist fish species contributing to coastal fisheries and seafood production within the Northeast Atlantic Ocean (Table 5.1, Janc, Dambrine et al. *In review*). Species were classified as either ‘sub-boreal’ (sea bass, *Dicentrarchus labrax*; flounder, *Platichthys flesus*; plaice, *Pleuronectes platessa*; and common sole, *Solea solea*) or ‘sub-tropical’ (meagre, *Argyrosomus regius*; and Senegalese sole, *Solea senegalensis*) species (see Figure 5.1 for observed distributions of these six species). Methodological choices implemented used the existing framework of hierarchical modelling described in Lasram, Hattab et al. (2020, <https://github.com/TarekHattab/SDM>) incorporating additional improvements and/or adaptations to fit with the MEO species ecology, as well as aspects of climate-driven change in biogeography. The projected distributions were produced employing present day (2001 – 2020), mid- (2040 – 2059) and late (2080 – 2099) 21st century conditions, according to the SSP1-2.6 and SSP5-8.5 scenarios used in the 6th Special Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC 2021), as used elsewhere in this report (section 2.2). Projections were also estimated under the intermediate SSP2-4.5 scenario, the “Middle of the Road” scenario, which simulates medium barriers to climate change adaptation and mitigation, with strong greenhouse gas emissions curbs from 2050 onwards. These projections were produced using the ‘hierarchical filters’ concept for modelling the potential species distributions that allows for consideration of the appropriate spatial extent and resolution at which environmental drivers are expected to influence the underlying ecological processes, particularly for highly mobile species (Guisan, Thuiller and Zimmermann 2017, Melo-Merino, Reyes-Bonilla and Lira-Noriega 2020). This approach combined the predictions of both bioclimatic and habitat components of the potential species niche. Specifically: bioclimatic variables used included large-scale and time-variant variables, such as bottom temperature, bottom dissolved oxygen level, and surface chlorophyll-a, which were retrieved from bias-adjusted, statistically downscaled, high-resolution climate ensemble projections (Kristiansen, Butenschön and Peck 2024); habitat components used included fine-grained and supposedly time-invariant variables such as bathymetry (EMODnet Bathymetry) and seabed type (EMODnet Geology), which were considered representative of use conditions of the bottom habitat. Modelling of the potential species distributions used international databases of biodiversity occurrences (GBIF, OBIS, VertNet, iNaturalist), research samplings and/or monitoring of professional fisheries (MigrenMer database - Elliott et al. 2023; DATRAS database) and the Biomod2 platform allowing ensemble forecasting which produced consensual predictions (Thuiller, Lafourcade et al. 2009). Ensemble forecasting produces a robust view of potential futures, given variations in the skill of nine statistical techniques (Generalized Linear Models – GLM; Generalized Additive Models – GAM; Multivariate Adaptive Regression Splines – MARS; Recursive Partitioning – CTA; Flexible Discriminant Analysis – FDA; Artificial Neural Networks – ANN; Random Forest – RF, Boosted Regression Trees – GBM; Maximum Entropy formalism – MaxEnt).

Table 5.1: Description of modelling data analysed here for the marine-estuarine opportunist storyline group (SL16-17). "latmin": lowest value of latitude in the model domain; "latmax": highest value of latitude in the model domain; "lonmin": lowest value of longitude in the model domain; "lonmax": highest value of longitude in the model domain. "CC" climate change. "MHW" marine heatwave.

Species	Model	Spatial extent (latmin - latmax; lonmin-lonmax)	Resolution	Time slice	Data provider	Expected climate trend based on a literature review
<i>Argyrosomus regius</i> (meagre)	Marine environment suitability distribution	36° to 61°N; -8° to 13°	0.01° x 0.01°	2001-2020 (reference); 2040-2059; 2080-2099	Anaïs Janc; Géraldine Lassalle; Henrique Cabral; Mario Lepage (INRAE)	Decrease in present range. Possibly vulnerable to MHW, (Stavrakidis-Zachou, Lika et al. 2021). Lower salinities are optimal for growth in nursery areas, so CC-driven decreased rainfall in southern part of range may negatively affect recruitment (Ruiz-Jarabo, Tinoco et al. 2019). Reproductive behaviour decreases in water temps >18°C (Vieira, Amorim et al. 2022)
<i>Dicentrarchus labrax</i> (seabass)	Marine environment suitability distribution	36° to 61°N; -8° to 13°	0.01° x 0.01	2001-2020 (reference); 2040-2059; 2080-2099	Anaïs Janc; Géraldine Lassalle; Henrique Cabral; Mario Lepage (INRAE)	Decrease in at least some part of current range. Abundance in nurseries is positively associated with lower salinities caused by higher river drainage, which in turn is linked to rainfall (Vinagre, Santos et al. 2009). Therefore, CC-driven lower precipitation in southern Europe could lead to decreases in recruitment, higher rainfall in N. Europe could cause increases in recruitment
<i>Platichthys flesus</i> (European flounder)	Marine environment suitability distribution	36° to 61°N; -8° to 13°	0.01° x 0.01	2001-2020 (reference); 2040-2059; 2080-2099	Anaïs Janc; Géraldine Lassalle; Henrique Cabral; Mario Lepage (INRAE)	Decrease (Hermant, Lobry et al. 2010, Amorim, Ramos et al. 2016)
<i>Pleuronectes platessa</i> (common plaice)	Marine environment suitability distribution	36° to 61°N; -8° to 13°	0.01° x 0.01	2001-2020 (reference); 2040-2059; 2080-2099	Anaïs Janc; Géraldine Lassalle; Henrique Cabral; Mario Lepage (INRAE)	Decrease (Hermant, Lobry et al. 2010, Engelhard, Lynam et al. 2015, Thompson, Couce et al. 2023)
<i>Solea senegalensis</i> (Senegalese sole)	Marine environment suitability distribution	36° to 61°N; -8° to 13°	0.01° x 0.01	2001-2020 (reference); 2040-2059; 2080-2099	Anaïs Janc; Géraldine Lassalle; Henrique Cabral; Mario Lepage (INRAE)	Decrease in current range. Southern European populations vulnerable to increased summer temps (e.g. heatwaves) in European nursery grounds, possibly

						negatively affecting recruitment (Vinagre, Narciso et al. 2013). Catches in Portugal decrease with increased temps (Teixeira, Gamito et al. 2014)
<i>Solea solea</i> (common sole)	Marine environment suitability distribution	36° to 61°N; -8° to 13°	0.01° x 0.01	2001-2020 (reference); 2040-2059; 2080-2099	Anaïs Janc; Géraldine Lassalle; Henrique Cabral; Mario Lepage (INRAE)	Decrease in at least some parts of current range (Baudron, Brunel et al. 2020)

5.3 GIS datasets used

Table 5.2: GIS datasets used to frame the modelling analysis results in the context of the region's blue economy.

Dataset	Data provider	Available at
Designated marine conservation areas	UNEP-WCMC and IUCN	https://www.protectedplanet.net/en/search-areas?geo_type=site
Offshore wind infrastructure	EMODnet	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geoviewer/
Capital and maintenance dredging	EMODnet	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geoviewer/
Spoil dumping	EMODNet	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geoviewer/
Sewage outfall	EMODnet	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geoviewer/
Offshore fishing effort distribution – benthic/demersal gears	ICES for OSPAR	https://ices-library.figshare.com/articles/report/OSPAR_request_on_the_production_of_spatial_data_layers_of_fishing_intensity_pressure/18639182
Oil/gas infrastructure	EMODNet	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geoviewer/
Aggregate extraction	EMODnet	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geoviewer/

5.4 Results

The spatial data resulting from these analyses, identifying long-term climate change refugia and hotspots for marine estuarine opportunistic species across Western European waters, is freely available in Talbot and Queirós (2024). While literature review led to the expectation that all species considered here were expected to fare negatively though climate-driven pressures in the region (Table 5.1), trends were found to be strongly variable across the analysed geographical area, and between species. Specifically, meagre, seabass, Senegalese and common sole were found to moderately increase in biomass across the central and southern North Sea, the Skagerrak and at least some parts of the Kattegat, even under the most extreme climate conditions simulated (SSP5-8.5), by the end of the century (individual species data not shown). In some cases, these species also fared well in the English Channel and the southern coast of Ireland, the Irish Sea and the Bristol Channel, and these species generally fared moderately poorly from the Portuguese coast, along to the Bay of Biscay, and the French coast. In turn, European flounder and Plaice biomass decreased in general, in line with expected trends, though they increased moderately in some coastal areas (at least by mid-century), including in the southern coast of Ireland, the Bristol Channel, some parts of Northern Scotland (south of Aberdeen), and even in the Danish coast. Contrastingly, an increase in biomass of European flounder was estimated across the Portuguese coast in most scenarios and time periods (individual species data not shown). These patterns were generally consistent across scenarios and time-frames, despite the wide range of potential climate change futures considered (sections 2.2 and 5.2).

When the overall assemblage was considered, we estimated the long-term classification of areas with regard to climate change sensitivity, taking all scenarios together (section 2.5). We found that many areas covered by the analyses did not appear consistently in any of the three possible categories with regard to climate change sensitivity (white spaces in Figure 5.2), potentially due to differences in the geographic range of species. However, large climate change refugia and some climate change bright-spots appeared consistently in all three SSPs considered (SSP1-2.6, SSP2-4.5 and SSP5-8.5) in the northern/central North Sea and the Kattegat, reflecting the increase in biomass of 4 out of 6 individual species, as described (Figure 5.2). Those refugia encompassed protected areas particularly off of the coast of the UK by mid-century (Fig. 5.2), although by the end of the century larger refugia emerged elsewhere (covering many more areas) but predominantly due to increases in meagre and bass biomass (Fig. 5.3).

Climate change hotspots, in turn, emerged consistently over the Irish Sea, the west coast of Scotland, and the northwest coast of France (Figure 5.2), suggesting that habitat suitability in these areas may decrease for most of the six species considered in these analyses. A stronger agreement across emissions scenarios was evident in projections for the end of the century (2080-2099), when refugia appeared consistently across the three SSPs in the North Sea, English Channel and the inner shelf of the Celtic Sea, potentially reflecting patterns in meagre, seabass, common and Senegalese sole. Hotspots emerging consistently around the coasts of southern Spain and Portugal, and in the Bay of Biscay, were consistent with declines in biomass found in most species (Figure 5.3). These affect many conservation sites across the latitudinal range.

A small extent of bright spots was also found when all species and scenarios were considered together. These emerged in southern Ireland, the central North Sea and the Danish coast primarily, but also in many other coastal areas by the end of the century. These bright spots likely reflect strong increase in biomass in a small number of species (namely bass and meagre (Fig.5.4)), and are likely not reliable.

5.5 Discussion

An important aspect that stands out in these analyses is the geographical heterogeneity of individual species responses to drivers. Modelled differences between species responses to drivers did not reflect their sub-boreal or sub-tropical groupings. In general, meagre (*Argyrosomus regius*) and Senegalese sole (*Solea senegalensis*), which are generally associated with warmer waters, expand their ranges north, while bass (*Dicentrarchus labrax*) and common sole (*Solea solea*) which are classified as sub-boreal, appeared to tolerate a wide range of environmental conditions (even by the end of the century under SSP5-8.5), finding increased habitat suitability in some areas. These results indicate how the response of assemblages, and of species within them, may not necessarily exhibit trends predicted based on large scale drivers alone – localised resilience was found in these assemblages based on more drivers. Indeed, despite the scale of warming in the North Sea, refugia could be found in this area, reflecting heterogeneity in drivers, and the distribution of both sub-boreal and sub-tropical species. Those refugia encompass protected areas, particularly off the coast of the UK, which could bring benefits to these commercially valuable species (although it should be noted that these species are not designating features for those sites), and well as to mammals and seabirds preying on them.

However, and notably, in habitat currently exploited by all six species in the Western part of the domain (from Scotland to Portugal), environmental thresholds appeared to be exceeded in many cases, with habitat becoming less suitable in the future, and leading to the emergence of hotspots across the latitudinal range. These occurred in areas currently hosting conservation sites, by mid-

century, in the Scottish Isles, Irish Sea and Brittany, and by the end of the century, in the offshore regions of Ireland and France. This result could be attributable to temperatures exceeding thermal tolerance limits, or perhaps to the decrease in productivity projected for the Atlantic margin (Chust, Allen et al. 2014) and reflected in the forcing of the habitat suitability model from which these projections were drawn.

Overall, our results suggest that existing conservation sites may present opportunities to deliver climate-resilient conservation for these commercially valuable species, and that more areas are likely available for their conservation, especially in the North Sea. Although the models considered here do not include other critical variables defining the range of these species particularly in estuarine areas, such as salinity, they present important findings with regard to broader responses to climate change and local habitats. Furthermore, these findings agree with a recent paper assessing the adequacy of existing MPAs for commercially valuable species, including the European flounder analysed here, which considered that 40% of their core habitats during the reference period was calculated to be within MPAs, but only 15% of these core habitats have specific measures to protect the group of diadromous species (Elliott, Dubost et al. 2024). That study, combined with the present results, could help the identification of opportunities for the location of new MPAs, or expansion of existing MPAs, to assist in the spatial management of these important species under climate change.

- *Solea senagalensis*
- *Platichyths flesus*
- *Solea solea*
- *Pleuronectes platessa*
- *Argyrosomus regius*
- *Dicentrarchus labrax*

Figure 5.1. Observed distributions of the six modelled species. Observations were recorded from the MigrenMer (Elliott, Deleys et al. 2023) and DATRAS scientific surveys, and the GBIF, OBIS, iNaturalist and VertNet databases (1993-2020).

Figure. 5.2. Climate change hotspots, refugia and bright-spots that appear consistently across all three SSPs (SSP1-RCP2.6; SSP2-RCP4.5; SSP5-RCP8.5) in the period 2040-2059. GIS data representing maritime sectors overlaid (keys in figures), including those that provide some degree of protection from extractive uses to these habitats (left) or those that represent additional sources of impacts (right).

Figure. 5.3. Climate change hotspots, refugia and bright-spots that appear consistently across all three SSPs (SSP1-RCP2.6; SSP2-RCP4.5; SSP5-RCP8.5) in the period 2080-2099. GIS data representing maritime sectors overlaid (keys in figures), including those that provide some degree of protection from extractive uses to these habitats (left) or those that represent additional sources of impacts (right).

Figure 5.4. Individual responses of the six species considered in this analysis in SSP1 2.6 (top row) and SSP5 8.5 (bottom row) in 2080-2099. (Janc et al., under review). Green shading indicates a decrease in habitat suitability driven by climate change, while pink shading indicates the reverse.

6 Sub-regional nature-based solutions: Conservation of vegetated coastal habitats and associated communities

6.1 The Balearic Islands (Storyline 25)

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6.1.1 Regional context

Posidonia oceanica is a seagrass endemic to the Mediterranean. It forms underwater meadows which support multiple ecosystem services: carbon sequestration (up to 1.6 tCO₂/ha yr; (Mateo, Díaz-Almela et al. 2018)), climate change mitigation (Duarte, Losada et al. 2013, Lavery, Mateo et al. 2013, Serrano, Lavery et al. 2014); it serves as a nursery to species targeted by commercial and recreational fisheries (Jackson, Rees et al. 2015); and cultural services (Vassallo, Paoli et al. 2013, Campagne, Salles et al. 2015). *P. oceanica* is slow growing (Marbà and Duarte 1998) with low and highly variable sexual reproduction (Díaz-Almela, Marbà et al. 2006) and a limited capacity to recover from disturbance (Kendrick et al, 2004). In recent decades, between 13% and 38% of the area extent of meadows has been lost mostly due to local impacts of climate change and anthropogenic activities (Marbà, Díaz-Almela and Duarte 2014, Telesca, Belluscio et al. 2015, de Los Santos, Krause-Jensen et al. 2019). In the Balearic islands, a small archipelago in the western Mediterranean sea, *P. oceanica* meadows have been the target of restoration activities (Cardona, López et al. 2007). Maximising the potential for success of ongoing restoration and conservation efforts for this species and associated communities in the Balearic Islands (Castejón-Silvo and Terrados 2021) thus requires an understanding of their response to climate change into the coming decades.

6.1.2 Modelling data used

Mechanistic species distribution modelling projections for *Posidonia oceanica* analysed here are described in Wilson, Maar et al. (2023). The model is a modification of the Baird, Adams et al. (2016) model, to include published, experimentally derived and species-specific relationships between temperature and growth. Additional modelling datasets were also analysed, for species and species groups associated with *P. oceanica* during all or part of their lifetime in the Balearic Islands. Those species are targeted by both commercial and recreational fisheries (6 species in total, Table 6.1.1), though trawling in water shallower than 50m (in which the majority of *Posidonia* meadows occur) is banned across the Mediterranean (EC 1967/2006) and enforced effectively in the Balearics. The projections for those associated fauna derive from model runs for the regionally parameterised Western Mediterranean Sea EwE food web model, described in detail in Coll, Lynam et al. (2024), and which included a total of 93 functional groups. All datasets include future projections under all five scenarios described in section 2.2, and climate-driven trends could be extracted for these species from the peer review literature (necessary to setup the climate signal detection algorithm, please see 2.4). The datasets are summarised in Table 6.1.1 below. In each cell of the common model domain, and for each scenario and each 20 year period between the present and the final part of the 21st century (section 2.4), the climate signal detection algorithm builds one spatial meta-analysis model that analyses all modelling layers together, testing the null hypothesis that change between the present 20 year period and the future 20 year period is zero. Please see section 2.4 for a detailed description of the analysis methodology employed.

Table 6.1.1: Description of modelling data analysed here for the Balearic Islands storyline. "latmin": lowest value of latitude in the model domain; "latmax": highest value of latitude in the model domain; "lonmin": lowest value of longitude in the model domain; "lonmax": highest value of longitude in the model domain. "CC" climate change

Variable	Model	Spatial extent (latmin - latmax; lonmin-lonmax)	Resolution	Time slice	Data provider	Expected climate trend
<i>Dentex dentex</i> (common dentex)	Ecopath with Ecosim and Ecospace	34.39 to 44.89; -5.64 to 16.36	0.15*0.15	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Marta Coll, ICM-CSIC	Decrease. (Garcia et al, 2022. IJMS, 79(9))
<i>Diplodus vulgaris</i> (common two-banded seabream)	Ecopath with Ecosim and Ecospace	34.39 to 44.89; -5.64 to 16.36	0.15*0.15	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Marta Coll, ICM-CSIC	Decrease. (Raventos et al, 2021. J. Anim. Ecol. 90(6))
Groupers (<i>Epinephelus aeneus</i> , <i>Epinephelus costae</i> , <i>Epinephelus marginatus</i>)	Ecopath with Ecosim and Ecospace	34.39 to 44.89; -5.64 to 16.36	0.15*0.15	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Marta Coll, ICM-CSIC	Increase <i>E. aeneus</i> and <i>E. marginatus</i> expanding range north in the Med due to warming temps (Sbragaglia et al, 2024. MEPS 728: 103–114, Azzurro et al, 2022. Front.Mar.Sci. 9)
<i>Mullus barbatus</i> (Red mullet)	Ecopath with Ecosim and Ecospace	34.39 to 44.89; -5.64 to 16.36	0.15*0.15	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Marta Coll, ICM-CSIC	Increase (Valente et al, 2023. Mar.Env.Res. 191)
<i>Mullus surmuletus</i> (Surmullet)	Ecopath with Ecosim and Ecospace	34.39 to 44.89; -5.64 to 16.36	0.15*0.15	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Marta Coll, ICM-CSIC	Decrease. (Pita et al, 2021. GCB 27(22))
<i>Posidonia oceanica</i>	Adapted from Baird et al. (2016)	34.39 to 44.89; -5.64 to 16.36	0.15*0.15	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Rob Wilson, PML	Decrease (Marba & Duarte, 2010, GCB 16(8)).

<p><i>Scorpaena scrofa</i> (Red scorpion fish)</p>	<p>Ecopath with Ecosim and Ecospace</p>	<p>34.39 to 44.89; -5.64 to 16.36</p>	<p>0.15*0.15</p>	<p>2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)</p>	<p>Marta Coll, ICM-CSIC</p>	<p>Decrease. (Pruckner et al, 2022. Est. Coast. Shelf.Sci 272(5)). Loss in Posidonia may negatively affect occurrences</p>
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6.1.3 GIS datasets used

Table 6.1.2: GIS datasets used to frame the modelling analysis results in the context of the region's blue economy.

Dataset	Data provider	Available at
Designated marine conservation areas	UNEP-WCMC and IUCN	https://www.protectedplanet.net/en/search-areas?geo_type=site
Power and communications cables	EMODnet	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geoviewer/
Offshore wind infrastructure	EMODnet	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geoviewer/
Capital and maintenance dredging	EMODnet	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geoviewer/
Sewage outfall	EMODnet	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geoviewer/
Demersal fishing	Global Fishing Watch	https://globalfishingwatch.org/data-download/datasets/public-fishing-effort
50 depth contour	EMODnet	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geoviewer/

6.1.4 Results

In this section, we present the long-term classification of the coastal waters around the Balearic Islands with regard to the long-term sensitivity to climate change of *Posidonia oceanica* and associated fish fauna. The spatial data resulting from these analyses, identifying long-term climate change refugia and hotspots in the region, is freely available in Talbot and Queirós (2024).

The results under the decreasing emissions scenario in which no additional management measures are implemented (RCP2.6 status quo scenario, Figure 6.1.1 a and c) suggest that the majority of seagrass habitats around the islands (i.e. those areas lying within the 50m depth contour) may fall into climate change refugia, including areas currently located within conservation sites. However, some hotspots are apparent on the northern coasts of Mallorca and Menorca. Those hotspots, where the biomass of species decreases relative to present, disappear under the Global Sustainability scenario (section 2.2), which includes additional management measures such as reduced fishing effort, habitat restoration, introduction of highly (HPA) and fully (FPA) protected areas) at the same emissions trajectory (RCP2.6, Figure 6.1.1 b and d). This suggests that reductions of species biomass in these areas were driven by fisheries impacts, not environmental change. Under this same scenario, some areas around the south of all the islands which had appeared as refugia in the unmanaged RCP2.6 scenario are no longer appearing as such. This is the result of these areas transitioning from one classification to another over the course of the time series (not shown) – in this case from bright

spots to refugia - suggesting that species' biomass increases under this scenario, at least in the short-term (white areas, Figure 6.1.1). Indeed, a closer look at species specific responses indicates that biomass of common dentex (*Dentex dentex*) and surmullet (*Mullus surmulletus*) both increase (against the expected climate trend, Table 6.1.1) in this scenario. These new refugia and "transitional" areas appear to coincide with the locations of newly designated FPAs and HPAs around the coasts of the islands. Taken together, these results suggest that emissions reductions (relative to present day, simulated by RCP2.6) and fisheries restrictions implemented in the scenario through various mechanisms (chapter 4.2) would benefit *Posidonia* meadows and associated fauna.

Under the RCP8.5 status quo scenario, climate change refugia also emerge throughout the islands, although a climate change hotspot emerges across most of the north coast of Menorca (Figure 6.1.2 a and d), suggesting biomass declines in the majority of species considered in the analysis. While *Posidonia* itself is projected to decline around much of the coastlines of the islands (individual species data not shown), projections of biomass for some of the fish species associated with that habitat in nature appear to increase in biomass, despite their expected decline due climate change (Table 6.1.1). Specifically, biomasses of surmullet (*Mullus surmulletus*), red scorpionfish (*Scorpaena scrofa*) and, to a lesser extent, the common two-banded seabream (*Diplodus vulgaris*) all increase (data not shown). The strong divergence from the expected climate trend by these species appears to drive the emergence of climate change refugia around the islands, even under this high emissions scenario. It is likely, in this case, that environmental thresholds for these fish species are not significantly exceeded even in this scenario, and that release from competition from other, more sensitive species may also drive this effect within the foodweb model. This may also be related to the use of projections for *P. oceanica* analysed resulting from a separate model from that used to simulate fish biomass (section 6.1.2) and that projections for these species may thus be somewhat optimistic.

A similar pattern is seen in the other RCP8.5 scenarios which introduce new management measures, National Enterprise (Figure 6.1.2 b and e) and World Market (Figure 6.1.2 c and f). In these scenarios, the spatial extent of new fully and highly protected areas around the islands is smaller, there is no habitat restoration, and fishing effort increases year on year (0.44% annually in National Enterprise, 0.88% annually in World Market). In both of these scenarios, the majority of the refugia that emerge in the RCP8.5 status quo scenario remain, although parts of the Menorcan coast still seem vulnerable to climate change. Interestingly, the climate change hotspot on the north coast of Menorca which emerged under the RCP8.5 status quo scenario has become a climate change refuge in both the National Enterprise (Figure 6.1.2 b and d) and World Market (Figure 6.1.2 c and f) scenarios. This reversal may be a consequence of the area being brought within a newly designated fully protected area in both of these scenarios, which benefits biomasses of several species across the assemblage, including seabream, red mullet and scorpion fish (all expected to decline under climate change, whilst groupers decline contrary to expectation (Table 6.1.1). These patterns potentially result from foodweb interactions and increased fishing pressure. Under the World Markets scenario, the white areas evident on the southwest coast of Mallorca (Figure 6.1.2 c and f) are representative of locations that begin the time series as climate change hotspots, but which transition to refugia in the 2030s (data not shown). The timing of the transition from one classification to the other could be attributable to the fact that FPAs located along this section of coast in the World Market scenario take effect in 2030. The sensitivity of *P. oceanica* to climate change is illustrated in Figure 6.1.3, reflecting projections by Wilson, Maar et al. (2023), where loss of habitat suitability is estimated across all areas, across all scenarios, though that study suggests that losses are perhaps overestimated in some areas.

6.1.5 Discussion

The widespread and consistent appearance of climate change refugia under the two lower emissions (RCP2.6) scenarios, and particularly under the Global Sustainability scenario, which introduces habitat restoration and much greater protection for species in MPAs, are perhaps unsurprising. More broadly, however, the emergence of refugia so consistently in all of the RCP8.5 scenarios runs counter to our expectations, as the majority of species considered in this analysis were believed to be relatively vulnerable to climate change (Table 6.1.1). In some cases, those patterns could be explained by the introduction of new protected areas around the islands - this is particularly clear in those instances where areas transition from climate change hotspots at the beginning of the time series to climate refugia after 2030 (data not shown). This result highlights how managing human pressures on marine foodwebs may have the potential to improve climate change adaptation especially in areas where environmental thresholds are not crossed. The importance of the interaction between removal of fishing pressure and consequential changes to competition and predation patterns within the foodweb was also apparent. For example, in the foodweb simulations that generated modelling data analysed here, under all the RCP8.5 scenarios, invertebrate biomass generally increased or remained stable (Coll, Lynam et al. (2024), data not shown here), suggesting that prey resources remain readily available despite climate change pressure, and perhaps allowing for a certain amount of resilience to climate pressures for their predators included in the analysis, such as surmullet (*Mullus surmulletus*). These interactions are likely to be exacerbated under the scenarios employing RCP8.5 (higher emissions), whereby the biomass of more climate sensitive species, such as the common dentex (*Dentex dentex*), decreased, thereby potentially freeing up food resources for more resilient species.

A further explanation for the projected widespread emergence of climate change refugia in these scenarios is that the foodweb model used to generate fish biomass projections analysed here used only surface and bottom water temperature and primary production as the environmental drivers. In contrast, much of the literature we reviewed when setting the expected climate trend for each species in the analysis algorithm considered a wider range of climate variables (e.g. salinity, precipitation, Table 6.1.1, section 2.4). It is also possible that species sensitivities that were projected at the basin level based on that literature may not be replicated in smaller scaled, local analyses such as the one presented here, as critical thresholds for responses may not be reached in this region (section 4.2). Taken together, this may have resulted in an mischaracterisation of the climate-driven trend of species analysed in this region, when setting up the meta-analysis algorithm, and highlights the importance of potentially different exposure of species to climate change at this scale, that may be capitalised upon in conservation and restoration programs.

A key limitation of this study is that fish biomass projections were modelled employing a foodweb model which included seagrasses but which had not been validated at the scale of the Balearic islands (Coll *pers. comm.*). For this reason, we used instead *P. oceanica* projections which had been developed in more detail, and validated at this scale (Wilson, Maar et al. 2023). Validation work done with that model had led to current additional development which is underway to reduce sensitivity in some areas where the species is known to occur at present, especially in small bays. Furthermore, none of the fish species analysed here were modelled as depending on *P. oceanica* for their life cycle in a model that included many other species, many of which were modelled as dependent on the seagrass (Coll, Lynam et al. 2024). Is therefore possible that the interactions between fish species considered here and the seagrass are captured only through indirect (though important) foodweb linkages, and that projected losses of seagrass habitat in this area may, in time, lead to more striking impacts on those assemblages than we were able to capture. This result highlights the need for caution when extrapolating for complex modelling tools developed for basin-scale applications to local focused studies. Continued development of these modelling tools is essential to inform real life

examples of restoration and conservation in sites harbouring sensitive and important biodiversity, such as the Balearic islands, in decades to come.

Figure. 6.1.1. Long-term climate change refugia and hotspots around the Balearic Islands 2026-2069 in the lower emissions Status Quo scenario (RCP 2.6, a and c), and the Global Sustainability scenario (which has the same climate projection but includes low barriers to climate change adaptation and mitigation such as the introduction of new MPAs, plotted in panel b). GIS data representing maritime sectors overlaid (keys in figures), including those that provide some degree of protection from extractive uses to these habitats (top) or those that represent additional sources of impacts (bottom).

Figure. 6.1.2. Long-term classification of the Balearic islands ecosystem regarding climate change sensitivity, between 2026-2069, under the RCP 8.5: Status Quo scenario (a and d); National Enterprise scenario (b and e); and World Markets scenario (c and f). GIS data representing the current distribution of maritime activity sectors overlaid (keys in figures), including those that may provide some degree of protection from extractive uses (top) or those that represent additional sources of impacts (bottom). Newly designated FPAs and HPAs are also plotted in panels b and c.

Figure. 6.1.3. Long-term sensitivity of seagrass *Posidonia oceanica* in the Balearic islands ecosystem (Hedge's g contrasting 2050-2069 with 2006-2026) under scenarios: a) Global Sustainability; b) RCP2.6 status quo; c) RCP 8.5 status quo scenario; d) National Enterprise; and e) World Markets.

6.2 The Tuscan archipelago (Storyline 28)

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6.2.1 Regional context

The Tuscan Archipelago, located off the NW coast of Italy in the Mediterranean Sea, spans 150km in latitude and is composed of seven islands. These are granted different levels of protection, ranging from a total (Gorgona, Pianosa and Montecristo), partial (Capraia and Giannutri) to no ban on human activities (Elba, Giglio). These islands host extensive seagrass meadows and macroalgal forests that support diverse invertebrate and fish assemblages and function as the pillars of a thriving economy centred on recreation and tourism, artisanal fisheries and aquaculture. Seagrass meadows and macroalgal forests are currently well-preserved in most areas of the Tuscan Archipelago (Tamburello, Benedetti-Cecchi et al. 2012) but their persistence is jeopardised by local and regional stressors (e.g. enhanced herbivory due to the over-exploitation of predators, nutrient, sediment and pollutant inputs, trawling, invasive species, boat anchoring) and also by global climate change. The conservation of those species playing a key role in sustaining the functioning of marine ecosystems (e.g. foundation species or habitat-formers) is considered a priority by the National Strategy for Climate Change Adaptation developed by the Italian Ministry of Environment. Understanding the response of seagrass and seaweed to climate change, and associated assemblages, in the Tuscan Archipelago is therefore necessary to ensure that their conservation efforts are successful.

6.2.2 Modelling datasets used

The modelling datasets analysed in this storyline (described in detail in Coll, Lynam et al. (2024)), include future projections under all five scenarios (section 2.2) for 8 species for which climate-driven trends could be extracted from the peer review literature (necessary to setup the climate signal detection algorithm, please see 2.4), and which were identified as being strongly associated with vegetated habitats for all or part of their life-cycle in the Tuscan Archipelago. These projections derive from model runs for the regionally parameterised Western Mediterranean Sea EwE food web model, described in Coll, Lynam et al. (2024), and which included a total of 93 functional groups. Two additional biogeochemical datasets were included which described seabed characteristics of the area, and which are documented in (Butenschön and Kristiansen 2023), simulating conditions experienced by seagrass and seaweeds in the region. It should be noted that no datasets for the vegetated habitats themselves were included in these analyses, for two reasons. Firstly, the projections from the *P. oceanica* model, used in the analysis of vegetated habitats in the Balearic Islands (see section 6.2.1), were not considered robust enough for use in the Tuscan Archipelago (Wilson, *pers. comm.*). Secondly, the seaweed groups included in the EwE model contained a large number of species with differing responses to climate change reported in the literature. Consequently, it was not possible to ascertain with any degree of certainty an expected climate trend for the groups as a whole. The 10 datasets selected are summarised in Table 6.2.1 below. In each cell of the common model domain, and for each scenario and each 20 year period between the present and the final part of the 21st century (section 2.4), the climate signal detection algorithm builds one spatial meta-analysis model that analyses all modelling layers together, testing the null hypothesis that change between the present 20 year period and the future 20 year period is zero. Please see section 2.4 for a detailed description of the analysis methodology employed.

Table 6.2.1: Description of modelling data analysed here for the Tuscan Archipelago storyline. "latmin": lowest value of latitude in the model domain; "latmax": highest value of latitude in the model domain; "lonmin": lowest value of longitude in the model domain; "lonmax": highest value of longitude in the model domain. "CC" climate change

Variable	Model	Spatial extent (latmin - latmax; lonmin-lonmax)	Resolution	Time slice	Data provider	Expected climate trend
Bottom salinity	Regionally downscaled CMIP6 ensemble	34.39 to 44.89; -5.64 to 16.36	0.15*0.15	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Trond Kristiansen, NIVA & Momme Butenschön, CMCC	Increase. (Pörtner, Roberts et al. 2022) Cross chapter paper 4, Med region
Bottom temperature	Regionally downscaled CMIP6 ensemble	34.39 to 44.89; -5.64 to 16.36	0.15*0.15	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Trond Kristiansen, NIVA & Momme Butenschön, CMCC	Increase. (Pörtner, Roberts et al. 2022) Cross chapter paper 4, Med region
<i>Conger conger</i> (European conger eel)	Ecopath with Ecosim and Ecospace	34.39 to 44.89; -5.64 to 16.36	0.15*0.15	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Marta Coll, ICM-CSIC	Increase. (Aragao et al, 2022. IJMS, 79(2))
<i>Dentex dentex</i> (common dentex)	Ecopath with Ecosim and Ecospace	34.39 to 44.89; -5.64 to 16.36	0.15*0.15	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Marta Coll, ICM-CSIC	Decrease. (Garcia et al, 2022. IJMS, 79(9))
<i>Diplodus vulgaris</i> (common two-banded seabream)	Ecopath with Ecosim and Ecospace	34.39 to 44.89; -5.64 to 16.36	0.15*0.15	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Marta Coll, ICM-CSIC	Decrease. (Raventos et al, 2021. J. Anim. Ecol. 90(6))
Groupers (<i>Epinephelus aeneus</i> , <i>Epinephelus costae</i> , <i>Epinephelus marginatus</i>)	Ecopath with Ecosim and Ecospace	34.39 to 44.89; -5.64 to 16.36	0.15*0.15	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Marta Coll, ICM-CSIC	Increase <i>E. aeneus</i> and <i>E. marginatus</i> expanding range north in the Med due to warming temps (Sbragaglia et al, 2024. MEPS 728: 103–114, Azzurro et al, 2022. Front.Mar.Sci. 9)

<i>Mullus barbatus</i> (Red mullet)	Ecopath with Ecosim and Ecospace	34.39 to 44.89; -5.64 to 16.36	0.15*0.15	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Marta Coll, ICM-CSIC	Increase (Valente et al, 2023. Mar.Env.Res. 191)
<i>Mullus surmuletus</i> (Surmullet)	Ecopath with Ecosim and Ecospace	34.39 to 44.89; -5.64 to 16.36	0.15*0.15	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Marta Coll, ICM-CSIC	Decrease. (Pita et al, 2021. GCB 27(22))
<i>Pagellus erythrinus</i> (common pandora)	Ecopath with Ecosim and Ecospace	34.39 to 44.89; -5.64 to 16.36	0.15*0.15	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Marta Coll, ICM-CSIC	Decrease. (Pruckner et al, 2022. Est. Coast. Shelf.Sci 272(5)). Loss in <i>Posidonia</i> may negatively affect occurrences
<i>Scorpaena scrofa</i> (Red scorpion fish)	Ecopath with Ecosim and Ecospace	34.39 to 44.89; -5.64 to 16.36	0.15*0.15	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Marta Coll, ICM-CSIC	Decrease. (Pruckner et al, 2022. Est. Coast. Shelf.Sci 272(5)). Loss in <i>Posidonia</i> may negatively affect occurrences

6.2.3 GIS datasets used

Table 6.2.2: GIS datasets used to frame the modelling analysis results in the context of the region's blue economy.

Dataset	Data provider	Available at
Designated marine conservation areas	UNEP-WCMC and IUCN	https://www.protectedplanet.net/en/search-areas?geo_type=site
Power and communications cables	EMODnet	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geoviewer/
Ocean energy site	EMODnet	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geoviewer/
Capital and maintenance dredging	EMODnet	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geoviewer/
Sewage outfall	EMODnet	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geoviewer/
Demersal fishing	Global Fishing Watch	https://globalfishingwatch.org/data-download/datasets/public-fishing-effort
Aggregate extraction	EMODnet	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geoviewer/

6.2.4 Results

In this section, we present the long-term classification of the coastal waters around the Tuscan Archipelago with regard to the long-term climate change sensitivity of fish fauna associated with coastal vegetated habitats. The spatial data resulting from these analyses, identifying long-term climate change refugia and hotspots in the region, is freely available in Talbot and Queirós (2024).

The results under the decreasing emissions scenario in which no additional management measures are implemented (RCP2.6 status quo scenario, Figure 6.2.1 a and c), suggest that climate change refugia may emerge all around the Tuscan Archipelago, including areas already designated as conservation sites. Under the Global Sustainability scenario, which includes additional management measures such as reduced fishing effort, habitat restoration and introduction of highly (HPA) and fully (FPA) protected areas at the same emissions trajectory (RCP2.6, Figure 6.2.1 b and d), refugia are still widespread. However, some areas around Elba which had appeared as refugia under the RCP2.6 status quo scenario are no longer appearing as such (white area in Figure 6.2.1 b). Closer scrutiny of the time series suggests that this area transitions from refuge to bright spot in the 2040s (data not shown), and this “transitional” area, with improved habitat conditions, is located in a newly designated FPA. This result appears to reflect the increase in protection benefiting species such as the common dentex (*Dentex dentex*) and the common two-banded seabream (*Diplodus vulgaris*), both of which increase in biomass (data not shown), contrary to the expected climate trend derived from literature (table 6.2.1). This positive outcome suggests that the cessation of fishing activity may have additional benefits to species biomasses under lower emissions scenarios, but the transition from one classification to another has resulted in the area not appearing consistently enough as either a bright-spot or a refuge in long term. Nevertheless, these results suggest that emissions reductions (relative to present day, simulated by RCP2.6) and fisheries restrictions implemented in

the scenario though various mechanisms (chapter 4.2) would benefit the fauna around the coastal regions of Elba Island.

Widely spread climate change refugia also emerge around the Tuscan Archipelago under RCP8.5 scenarios (Fig.6.2.2), although they appear more consistently in the scenario with no additional management measures (status quo, Fig. 6.2.2. a and d) than in the scenarios in which new management measures are introduced. Under the National Enterprise scenario (RCP8.5), fishing effort increases by 0.44% per year (to account for technological advancement), and only 10% of each country's EEZ is an FPA or HPA by 2030 (Figure 4.2.1). Widespread refugia are still evident under this scenario (Fig 6.2.2 b and e), although a hotspot is present to the east of Corsica, along with two unclassified areas (white areas, Fig. 6.2.2 b and e), which transition from refugia to hotspot as the time series progresses (data not shown). The region in which the hotspot and "transitional" areas emerge both sit outside protected areas, suggesting that increased fishing could be driving decreases in species biomasses in these areas. Under this scenario, the coast of Elba appears as a refuge consistently, as the short-term bright-spots that were evident under the Global Sustainability scenario (not shown) now do not emerge. A closer look at individual level responses shows that biomass of the common dentex (*Dentex dentex*), which increased under the Global Sustainability scenario, and appeared to remain relatively stable in the RCP8.5 status quo scenario(not shown) decreases as expected in this scenario. Under the same conditions, biomass of the two banded-seabream shows moderate increases (against expectation), at least until the mid 2040s, when decreases in biomass become apparent (not shown). This difference between scenarios may be due to the fact that fishing effort increases from the status quo scenario (0.44% per year), and that protection levels around the Tuscan Archipelago in National Enterprise are mostly HPA, rather than FPA, suggesting that in the case of *Dentex*, even moderate levels of fishing with lower impact gears can negatively impact biomasses under higher emissions scenarios. It might also suggests species specific resilience to fishing pressure, with the two-banded seabream better able to withstand the increased fishing effort of this scenario, at least in the short term. Under the World Market scenario (Figure 6.2.2 c and f), conservation and restoration targets are the same as in the National Enterprise scenario, but fishing effort increases by 0.88% per year. The hotspot and unclassified region to the east of Corsica seen under the National Enterprise scenario are both larger here; again, the unclassified (white) area is due to hotspots appearing along this part of coast in the mid-2040s (not shown), resulting in the area not meeting the threshold for either long-term refugia or hotspots. It is possible that the growth of the hotspot and "transitional" area is due to the increase in fishing effort represented by this scenario – as with National Enterprise, the coastal region of Corsica is not protected from fishing. A similar "transitional" area, likely driven by the same increase in fishing effort outside of protected areas, appears between Elba Island and Giglio, where hotspots emerge sporadically between 2030-2050.

6.2.5 Discussion

As with the results of the analysis of vegetated habitats in the Balearic Islands (Section 6.1), the widespread and consistent appearance of climate change refugia, particularly under the higher emissions scenarios, runs counter the expectations of species specific climate driven trends based on literature review (Table 6.2.1). It is possible that the differences between scenarios can be attributed to the different levels of protection offered by the different management measures simulated in scenarios (See Fig. 4.2.1 for locations of all the newly designated FPAs and HPAs in the Western Mediterranean region), and possibly to the different levels of fishing effort represented in the National Enterprise and World Market scenarios (Section 6.2.4). This is particularly clear in those

cases where areas transition from refugia to hotspots, between scenarios, in unprotected areas as fishing effort increases year on year. This result highlights how managing human pressures on marine foodwebs may have the potential to improve or worsen climate change adaptation especially in areas where environmental thresholds may not be crossed. The importance of the interaction between removal of fishing pressure and consequential changes to competition and predation patterns within the foodweb was also apparent. For example, in the foodweb simulations that generated modelling data analysed here, under all the RCP8.5 scenarios, invertebrate biomass generally increased or remained stable (Coll, Lynam et al. (2024), data not shown here), suggesting that prey resources remain readily available despite climate change pressure, and perhaps allowing for a certain amount of resilience to climate pressures for their predators included in the analysis, such as the common pandora (*Pagellus erythrinus*) and surmullet (*Mullus surmulletus*). These interactions are likely to be exacerbated under the scenarios employing RCP8.5 (higher emissions), whereby the biomass of more climate sensitive species, such as the common dentex (*Dentex dentex*), decreased, thereby potentially freeing up food resources for more resilient species.

A further explanation for the projected widespread distribution of climate change refugia is that the foodweb model underpinning these analyses used only surface and bottom water temperature and primary production as the environmental drivers of climate change that the modelled food web responds to. By contrast, much of the literature we reviewed when setting the expected climate trend for the analysis algorithm considered a wider range of climate variables (e.g. salinity, precipitation, Table 6.2.1, section 2.4). It is also possible that species sensitivities that were projected at the basin level based on that literature may not be replicated in smaller scaled local analyses such as the one presented here, as critical thresholds for responses may not be reached in this region (section 4.2). Taken together, this may have resulted in an mischaracterisation of the climate-driven trend of species analysed in this region, when setting up the meta-analysis algorithm, and highlights the importance of heterogeneity in the exposure of species to climate change when considered at this smaller scale, that may be capitalised upon in conservation and restoration programs.

A key limitation of this study is that fish biomass projections were modelled employing a foodweb model which included seagrasses and macroalgae but which had not been validated at the scale of the Tuscan Archipelago (Coll *pers. comm.*). Furthermore, none of the fish species analysed were modelled as depending on vegetated habitats for their life cycle in a model that included many other species, many of which were modelled as dependent on the habitats (Coll, Lynam et al. 2024). It is therefore possible that the interactions between fish species considered here and the habitat are captured only through indirect (though important) foodweb linkages, and that any losses of changes in composition of vegetated habitats in the area may, in time, lead to more striking impacts on those assemblages than we were able to capture. This result highlights the need for caution when extrapolating for complex modelling tools developed for basin-scale applications to local focused studies. Continued development of these modelling tools will be essential to inform real life examples of restoration and conservation in sites harbouring sensitive and important biodiversity, such as the Tuscan Archipelago, in decades to come.

Successful uptake of the information produced through the modelling presented in this chapter for the management of coastal biodiversity strongly relies on the engagement of key social groups and economic sectors. In FutureMARES, as part of the co-development of NBSs, there was the engagement with local artisanal fisheries, one of the sectors mostly affected by the presence of MPAs. These are active along the islands of Elba, Giglio and Capraia. Semi-structured interviews investigated the factors underpinning the perception of MPAs by artisanal fishers, and revealed that some of the artisanal fishers have a positive perception of MPAs on the condition that they could be involved in their spatial planning and management (Di Cintio, Sulanke et al. 2024). Indeed, they

would consider changing fishing gear in areas where MPAs were established, particularly if the MPA helped to deter industrial fishing fleets (Fig. 6.2.3). Thus, projections of future habitat suitability for demersal species of commercial interest could represent a great tool for promoting the engagement with local artisanal fishers and, ultimately, for enhancing the ecological and socio-economic efficiency of climate-smart MPAs.

Figure. 6.2.1 Long-term climate change refugia and hotspots around the Tuscan Archipelago 2026-2069 in the lower emissions Status Quo scenario (RCP 2.6, a and c), and the Global Sustainability scenario (which has the same climate projection but includes low barriers to climate change adaptation and mitigation such as the introduction of new MPAs, plotted in panel b). GIS data representing maritime sectors overlaid (keys in figures), including those that provide some degree of protection from extractive uses to these habitats (top) or those that represent additional sources of impacts (bottom).

Figure 6.2.2 Long-term classification of the Balearic islands ecosystem regarding climate change sensitivity, between 2026-2069, under RCP 8.5: Status Quo scenario (a and d); National Enterprise scenario (b and e); and World Markets scenario (c and f). GIS data representing the current distribution of maritime activity sectors overlaid (keys in figures), including those that may provide some degree of protection from extractive uses (top) or those that represent additional sources of impacts (bottom). Newly designated FPAs and HPAs simulated by the National Enterprise and World Market scenarios are plotted in panels b and c

Fig. 6.2.3. Fishers’ perception of management and MPAs in the Tuscan Archipelago, expressed in a Likert-scale from 1 (absolutely no) to 5 (absolutely yes). From: Di Cintio et al. 2024, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2024.106260>.

6.3 The Portuguese Coast (Storyline group 21, 23)

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6.3.1 Regional context

Marine seaweed forests include habitat-forming primary producers such as large canopy species like kelps (*Laminaria* spp.) and intertidal fucoids (e.g., *Fucus* spp., *Ascophyllum nodosum*) and are found on the northern coastal shores of Portugal. These foundation species, provide food, shelter and habitats for a variety of organisms and support complex food webs in coastal zones, promoting healthy artisanal fisheries (Bertocci, Araújo et al. 2015, Eger, Marzinelli et al. 2023).

In addition to serving as biodiversity hotspots (Franco, Arenas et al. 2020) and critical in the support of climate change-sensitive species (Bulleri, Eriksson et al. 2018), marine forests also provide essential ecosystem services (Eger, Marzinelli et al. 2023) such as food, raw materials for bioactive compounds, coastal protection and nutrient dynamics. Marine forests may also be highly important for climate regulation and climate change mitigation, due to their carbon uptake and contributions to oceanic long term carbon reservoirs (i.e. blue carbon,(Queirós, Stephens et al. 2019, Duarte, Gattuso et al. 2022)).

The Iberian upwelling system is probably crucial in maintaining these seaweed communities in Portugal, due to the provision of cold and nutrient-enriched deep oceanic waters, during the summer season (Franco, Tuya et al. 2018). The Iberian upwelling system is weakening however (Sousa, Ribeiro et al. 2020), and canopy-forming seaweeds in the area are now declining and being replaced by turf-based communities with lower functional complexity (Franco, Tuya et al. 2018, Casado-Amezúa,

Araújo et al. 2019, Vale, Arenas et al. 2021), resulting in the reduced potential of this area as a North Iberian climate refuge. Climate change, particularly seawater temperature, is likely the main driver of seaweed assemblages in this area (Piñeiro-Corbeira, Barreiro et al. 2018, de Azevedo, Franco et al. 2023). Understanding climate change patterns along the Portuguese coast may thus be a key step towards effectively managing and protecting these species and associated communities.

6.3.2 Modelling datasets used

The modelling datasets analysed in this storyline (described in detail in Coll, Lynam et al. (2024)), include future projections under all five scenarios (section 2.2) for 17 species or species groups for which climate-driven trends could be extracted from the peer reviewed literature (necessary to setup the climate signal detection algorithm, please see section 2.4). These projections derive from model runs of the regionally parameterised Portuguese shelf EwE with ECOSPACE food web model, described in Veiga-Malta, Szalaj et al. (2019), Szalaj, Torres et al. (2021), Szalaj, Silva and Coll (*in prep*), and which included a total of 34 functional groups. The datasets selected for analysis are summarised in Table 6.3.1 below. In each cell of the common model domain, and for each scenario and each 20 year period between the present and the final part of the 21st century (section 2.4), the climate signal detection algorithm builds one spatial meta-analysis model that analyses all modelling layers together, testing the null hypothesis that change between the present 20 year period and the future 20 year period is zero. Please see section 2.4 for a detailed description of the analysis methodology employed.

6.3.3 Skill of modelling data in an upwelling region

To determine whether the projections analysed here are meaningful, we assessed the skill of the physical-biogeochemical projections used to force the EwE with ECOSPACE model (CMIP6 ensemble, Butenschön and Kristiansen 2023) in reproducing sea surface temperature (SST) observation patterns along the Portuguese coast. This was seen as important, because the global models used to estimate the CMIP6 ensemble do not necessarily reproduce SST patterns well in Eastern Boundary Upwelling Systems such as the Portuguese coast (Varela, DeCastro et al. 2022). The SST based Upwelling Index (UI) developed by the European Space Agency's PRIMUS (PRIMary Productivity in Upwelling Systems) program, was estimated based on the United Kingdom's Met Office Operational SST and Sea Ice Analysis (OSTIA) system. The OSTIA system uses microwave and infrared satellite products with accompanying uncertainty estimates, as produced by the Group for High Resolution SST (GHRSSST) Regional/Global Task Sharing (R/GTS) framework (Donlon, Martin et al. 2012). The UI was calculated for 0.1° resolution CMIP6 SST monthly means for the period of 1998 and 2020, and for the OSTIA data for the same period, re-gridded to the CMIP6 grid. The UI estimates produced using both datasets were then compared, focusing on seasonality and inter-annual variability

Table 6.3.1: Description of modelling data analysed here for the Portuguese shelf storyline. "latmin": lowest value of latitude in the model domain; "latmax": highest value of latitude in the model domain; "lonmin": lowest value of longitude in the model domain; "lonmax": highest value of longitude in the model domain. "CC" climate change

Variable	Model	Spatial extent (latmin - latmax; lonmin-lonmax)	Resolution	Time slice	Data provider	Expected climate trend
<i>Balaenoptera acutorostrata</i> (Minke whale)	Ecopath with Ecosim and Ecospace	36.79 to 42.04; -10.12 to 7.20	0.08*0.08	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Dorota Szalaj, IPMA	Decrease. Key prey species in diet matrix are sardine, horse mackerel and chub mackerel (in that order). Sardine and horse mackerel both expected to decrease with CC
Benthic cephalopods (<i>Eledone cirrhosa</i> , <i>Octopus vulgaris</i> , <i>Sepia officinalis</i> , <i>Sepiolid sp.</i>)	Ecopath with Ecosim and Ecospace	36.79 to 42.04; -10.12 to 7.20	0.08*0.08	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Dorota Szalaj, IPMA	Increase. (Gamito, Teixeira et al. 2015, Lishchenko, Perales-Raya et al. 2021)).
<i>Delphinus delphis</i> (common dolphin)	Ecopath with Ecosim and Ecospace	36.79 to 42.04; -10.12 to 7.20	0.08*0.08	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Dorota Szalaj, IPMA	Decrease. Sardine key prey in Portugal (Silva 1999), which may decrease with CC. Sardine still key, even with the recent declines in sardine off the Portuguese coast. Chub mackerel and <i>Trachurus</i> species also part of diet (Marçalo, Giménez et al. 2021).
<i>Engraulis encrasicolus</i> (European anchovy)	Ecopath with Ecosim and Ecospace	36.79 to 42.04; -10.12 to 7.20	0.08*0.08	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Dorota Szalaj, IPMA	Increase. ((Pennino, Coll et al. 2020, Gordó-Vilaseca, Pennino et al. 2021). NB - no specific studies for Iberian peninsula found, so used Med instead.

Kelps (<i>Saccorhiza polyschides</i> , <i>Laminaria hyperborea</i> , <i>Phyllariopsis</i> spp., <i>Laminaria ochroleuca</i>)	Ecopath with Ecosim and Ecospace	36.79 to 42.04; -10.12 to 7.20	0.08*0.08	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Dorota Szalaj, IPMA	Decrease in at least some part of their current ranges. <i>L. hyperborea</i> (Assis, Araújo and Serrão 2018, de Azevedo, Franco et al. 2023) and <i>L. ochroleuca</i> are decreasing (D1.1). <i>S. polyschides</i> and <i>Phyllariopsis</i> spp. are warm temperate and occur in deeper water, and are increasing (D1.1).
<i>Merluccius merluccius</i> (European hake)	Ecopath with Ecosim and Ecospace	36.79 to 42.04; -10.12 to 7.20	0.08*0.08	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Dorota Szalaj, IPMA	Decrease. (Mendes, de Fátima Borges et al. 2008).
<i>Phocoena phocoena</i> (harbour porpoise)	Ecopath with Ecosim and Ecospace	36.79 to 42.04; -10.12 to 7.20	0.08*0.08	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Dorota Szalaj, IPMA	Decrease. Key prey species are blue whiting and <i>Trachurus</i> sp. (Begoña Santos, Saavedra and Pierce 2014), all projected to decrease with CC.
Rays (<i>Leucoraja naevus</i> , <i>Raja brachyura</i> , <i>Raja clavata</i> , <i>Raja montagui</i>)	Ecopath with Ecosim and Ecospace	36.79 to 42.04; -10.12 to 7.20	0.08*0.08	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Dorota Szalaj, IPMA	Increase (Teixeira, Gamito et al. 2014, Punzón, Serrano et al. 2016)
<i>Sardina pilchardus</i> (European sardine) ADULT	Ecopath with Ecosim and Ecospace	36.79 to 42.04; -10.12 to 7.20	0.08*0.08	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Dorota Szalaj, IPMA	Decrease - (Santos, González-Quirós et al. 2012, Teixeira, Gamito et al. 2016)
<i>Sardina pilchardus</i> (European sardine) JUVENILE	Ecopath with Ecosim and Ecospace	36.79 to 42.04; -10.12 to 7.20	0.08*0.08	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Dorota Szalaj, IPMA	Decrease (Santos, González-Quirós et al. 2012, Teixeira, Gamito et al. 2016)
<i>Scomber colias</i> (Atlantic chub mackerel)	Ecopath with Ecosim and Ecospace	36.79 to 42.04; -10.12 to 7.20	0.08*0.08	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Dorota Szalaj, IPMA	Increase (Teixeira, Gamito et al. 2016)

<i>Scomber scombrus</i> (mackerel)	Ecopath with Ecosim and Ecospace	36.79 to 42.04; -10.12 to 7.20	0.08*0.08	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Dorota Szalaj, IPMA	Decrease (Baudron, Brunel et al. 2020)
Sharks (<i>Galeus melastomus</i> , <i>Scyliorhinus canicula</i>)	Ecopath with Ecosim and Ecospace	36.79 to 42.04; -10.12 to 7.20	0.08*0.08	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Dorota Szalaj, IPMA	Increase. (Punzón, Serrano et al. 2016)NB - no studies for Portuguese shelf found, so used BoB instead.
<i>Stenella coeruleoalba</i> (striped dolphin)	Ecopath with Ecosim and Ecospace	36.79 to 42.04; -10.12 to 7.20	0.08*0.08	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Dorota Szalaj, IPMA	Decrease. Key prey species are sardine, blue whiting, <i>Trachurus</i> . Sp, hake (Begoña Santos, Saavedra and Pierce 2014) all projected to decrease with CC.
<i>Trachurus trachurus</i> (horse mackerel)	Ecopath with Ecosim and Ecospace	36.79 to 42.04; -10.12 to 7.20	0.08*0.08	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Dorota Szalaj, IPMA	Decrease (Teixeira, Gamito et al. 2016)
Tunas (<i>Auxis rochei</i> , <i>Sarda sarda</i> , <i>Thunnus thynnus</i>)	Ecopath with Ecosim and Ecospace	36.79 to 42.04; -10.12 to 7.20	0.08*0.08	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Dorota Szalaj, IPMA	Decrease based on key prey species. Sardine is a key prey species for this group in model diet matrix, sardine projected to decrease
<i>Tursiops truncatus</i> (bottlenose dolphin)	Ecopath with Ecosim and Ecospace	36.79 to 42.04; -10.12 to 7.20	0.08*0.08	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Dorota Szalaj, IPMA	Possible increase. Some key prey species as per (Santos, Coniglione and Louro 2007) may increase with climate change (e.g. cephalopods, anchovy, sparids)

6.3.4 GIS datasets used

Table 6.3.2: GIS datasets used to frame the modelling analysis results in the context of the region's blue economy.

Dataset	Data provider	Available at
Designated marine conservation areas	UNEP-WCMC and IUCN	https://www.protectedplanet.net/en/search-areas?geo_type=site
Power and communications cables	EMODnet	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geoviewer/
Ocean energy site	EMODnet	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geoviewer/
Capital and maintenance dredging	EMODnet	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geoviewer/
Sewage outfall	EMODnet	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geoviewer/
Demersal fishing	ICES for OSPAR	https://ices-library.figshare.com/articles/report/OSPAR_request_on_the_production_of_spatial_data_layers_of_fishing_intensity_pressure/18639182
Aggregate extraction	EMODnet	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geoviewer/

6.3.5 Results

6.3.5a Simulating climate change in an upwelling region

The CMIP6 based UI was found to underestimate the OSTIA based UI estimate peaks, providing a much lower inter-annual dispersion of UI mean values than that based on satellite observations (Figure 6.3.a). The difference between the two estimates was markedly stronger in the summer months, when UI is highest, leading to a consistent underestimation of the strength of upwelling in the Portuguese coast ($(\text{model UI} - \text{OSTIA UI}) / \text{mean}(\text{OSTIA UI}) = -0.60$, Figure 6.3.b). These results indicate that SST estimated in the CMIP6 ensemble in the Portuguese coast may be somewhat overestimated in the North of Portugal, where upwelling occurs during summer months, leading to a potentially overly pessimistic effect for some of the more thermally sensitive species in the foodweb model. However, it is worth noting that the mean projected temperature difference by mid-century (compared to present day temperatures) on the northern Portuguese coast is still lower than the projected difference on the southern coast (Butenschön & Kristiansen, 2023, Figure 22), suggesting that the dynamics of the upwelling system are, to some extent, still being captured.

6.3.5b Foodweb effects

The spatial data resulting from these analyses, identifying long-term climate change refugia and hotspots in the Portuguese shelf, is freely available in Talbot and Queirós (2024). In all the scenarios considered, climate change refugia are widespread, with no long-term, consistent climate change

hotspots (or brightspots) emerging. This broad scale view emerges as the result of interesting and complex biomass patterns at the individual species level, which change both spatially and temporally between and within scenarios.

Under RCP2.6 (status quo scenario, Figure 6.3.1 a and c), which include the effects of emissions trajectories and current management levels (e.g. fishing pressure), sardine (*Sardina pilchardus*), kelps (*Saccorhiza polyschides*, *Laminaria hyperborea*, *Phyllariopsis* spp., *Laminaria ochroleuca*) and mackerel (*Scomber scombrus*) all increase at the beginning of the time series, against expected climate-driven trends (Table 6.3.1). Furthermore, by the 2040s, the biomass of horse mackerel (*Trachurus trachurus*), tunas (*Auxis rochei*, *Sarda sarda*, *Thunnus thynnus*), harbour porpoise (*Phocoena phocoena*) and common dolphin (*Delphinus delphis*), species also expected to decline, have started to increase (individual species data not shown). Conversely, the biomass of sharks (*Galeus melastomus* and *Scyliorhinus canicula*) and rays (*Leucoraja naevus*, *Raja brachyura*, *Raja clavata* and *Raja montagui*), which were expected to increase based on climate-driven trends (Table 6.3.1), have decreased by mid-century.

Only by mid-century does sardine biomass begin to decline, in line with expected climate driven trends. A similar pattern for sardine can be seen under the Global Sustainability scenario (Figure 6.3.1 b and d), where *S. pilchardus* biomass increases unexpectedly at the beginning of the time series, but conforms to the expected trend by mid-century (Table 6.3.1). In both of these lower emissions scenarios, the temporal dynamics of sardine biomass may be attributable to the slower warming represented by the RCP2.6 scenario, perhaps suggesting that critical thermal limits are reached later in the century for this species. However, there are some differences between the Global Sustainability and the RCP2.6 Status Quo scenario. These can be seen in the changes in biomass of horse mackerel (*Trachurus trachurus*) and tunas (*Auxis rochei*, *Sarda sarda*, *Thunnus thynnus*), which increase unexpectedly along the northern section of the coast (i.e. north of Porto) earlier in the timeseries under the Global Sustainability scenario (RCP2.6 plus additional management measures), with biomass increases progressing south along the coast as the time series progresses (not shown). It is possible that the designation of new fully (FPA) and highly (HPA) protected areas along this section of coast (Figure 6.3.2 b) under this scenario thus benefits these species, with fishing restrictions further reinforcing the positive effects of lowered emissions.

Under the RCP8.5 status quo scenario (Figure 6.3.3 a and d), biomasses of anchovy (*Engraulis encrasicolus*), chub mackerel (*Scomber colias*) and bottlenose dolphins (*Tursiops truncatus*) start to increase by the 2030s (individual species data not shown), in line with the expected climate-driven trends based on literature review (Table 6.3.1). Kelps (as a group) unexpectedly increase in biomass along the southern part of the coast (i.e. south of Lisbon). This trend in kelp biomass persists into the 2030s, but by the 2040s their biomass is decreasing in line with the expected climate-driven trend (individual species data not shown). Additionally, by the 2040s, biomasses of mackerel (*Scomber scombrus*) exhibit unexpected increases (Table 6.3.1) all along the Portuguese coast, while horse mackerel (*Trachurus trachurus*), harbour porpoise (*Phocoena phocoena*) and tuna (*Auxis rochei*, *Sarda sarda*, *Thunnus thynnus*) increase their biomasses against the expected trend along the section of coast north of Lisbon (not shown). The National Enterprise (Figure 6.3.3 b and e, section 2.2) and World Market (Figure 6.3.3 c and f) RCP8.5 scenarios employ the same RCP8.5 emissions trajectory, but simulate the addition of newly designated FPAs and HPAS, and an increase in fishing effort. In these scenarios, changes in species biomass are similar to those observed under the RCP8.5 status quo (climate only) scenario. Anchovy (*Engraulis encrasicolus*), bottlenose dolphin (*Tursiops truncatus*) and chub mackerel (*Scomber colias*) all begin the time series with an unexpected decrease in biomass. As the time series progresses, biomasses begin to increase, thus in line with the expected climate-driven trend (Table 6.3.1), though at different rates for each species (individual species data

not shown). The biomass patterns of kelps, mackerel (*Scomber scombrus*), horse mackerel (*Trachurus trachurus*) and tunas also exhibit the same patterns in both of these scenarios as in the (climate only) RCP8.5 status quo scenario. Biomass of sharks (*Galeus melastomus* and *Scyliorhinus canicula*) and rays (*Leucoraja naevus*, *Raja brachyura*, *Raja clavata* and *Raja montagui*) start to decrease in both scenarios as time progresses, the only place they conform to the expected climate driven trend (i.e. biomass increases, Table 6.3.1) is in the newly designated highly protected (HPA) and fully protected (FPA) areas between Lisbon and Porto (MPA locations in Figure 6.3.2 panels C and D, species biomass changes not shown). However, even these increases are limited to just the FPAs by mid-century. This may suggest that the increased fishing effort represented in these scenarios (0.44% annual increase in effort in National Enterprise, 0.88% increase in World Market) is sufficient to counteract any benefit that warmer waters might confer on these species groups. Interestingly, biomass of minke whales (*Balaenoptera acutorostrata*) increases in opposition to the expected climate-driven trend under all three RCP8.5 scenarios (not shown), despite the reductions in biomass of sardine (*Sardina pilchardus*), which is a key prey species for minke whales in the food web model from which these projections are derived. However, it is possible that minke whale biomass is being maintained due to the increase in biomass of horse mackerel, which also forms part of the diet in the foodweb model

6.3.6 Discussion

The key finding from the analyses presented here is that species along the Portuguese shelf exhibit spatially and temporally complex responses to climate and other pressures leading to a consequential overall climate change resilience of the communities studied. However, this needs to be taken with care when considering individual species, which can still exhibit larger changes in biomass, even when the overall level picture is one of foodweb resilience.

In some cases, there is a difference in response between the northern and southern sections of the coast, which may be a reflection of the presence of the Iberian upwelling system, providing cool, nutrient rich waters to the surface during the summer in the northern region. Although the SST projection used to drive the food web model may be overestimating temperatures in the north of Portugal (see section 6.3.5a), it is possible that the dynamics of this upwelling under climate change may be driving some of the differences in biomass patterns that are apparent between scenarios. For example, under the RCP8.5 scenarios, kelp biomass decreases as expected in the upwelling system, perhaps due to the expected weakening of the system and the reduced influx of cool, nutrient rich water that supports kelp species in the region. In southern Portugal, however, kelp biomass increases, at least until the 2040s when biomasses begin to decrease as expected. This would suggest that warming associated with RCP8.5 would result in the loss of kelp habitats all along the Portuguese coast by mid- century, as expected based on wider literature. While the differences in kelp biomass responses between the northern and southern parts of the coast were not evident in the long-term under the RCP2.6 scenarios, declines in biomass did emerge by mid century (although there were increases in biomass early on in the time series), suggesting that the status of Portuguese kelp forests and associated communities could be threatened, even under lower emissions, due to legacy effects of a altered climate system.

Spatial management measures such as fishing restrictions and designation of FPAs and HPAs make a clear difference to responses of some species, suggesting that fishing pressure may be as important a driver of species biomasses as climate change in some cases. This is particularly evident in the case of sharks and rays, biomasses of which were expected to increase with increased warming (Table 6.3.1). However, biomasses of these two groups decreased under the National Enterprise and World Market RCP8.5 scenarios, except in those areas which were protected from fishing via the designation of new conservation sites. It is therefore likely that the increased fishing effort simulated in the National

Enterprise and World Market scenarios, whether that effort is targeted at these species groups directly or as a result of bycatch in National Enterprise (where gear selectivity is not improved), represents a significant negative pressure on the biomass of sharks and rays, counteracting any benefit that warmer waters may have on these groups. Climate sensitive species also appeared to benefit from increased protection from fishing. For example, hake biomass increased against the expected climate driven trend in HPAs and FPAs under the Global Sustainability scenario, and in FPAs under the National Enterprise and World Market scenarios, despite biomass decreases outside these areas in all scenarios. Taken together, these results highlight how managing human pressures on marine foodwebs may be critical for preserving biodiversity into the future, even for those species which are expected to be fairly resilient to climate change. They also illustrate that for more climate sensitive species, the level of protection offered by a conservation area (e.g. FPA vs HPA) can also be instrumental in determining species resilience to climate pressures, particularly under higher emissions scenarios.

Figure. 6.3.1 Long-term climate change refugia and hotspots along the Portuguese shelf 2026-2069 in the lower emissions Status Quo scenario (RCP 2.6, a and c), and the Global Sustainability scenario (which has the same climate projection but includes low barriers to climate change adaptation and mitigation). GIS data representing maritime sectors overlaid (keys in figures), including those that provide some degree of protection from extractive uses to these habitats (top) or those that represent additional sources of impacts (bottom).

Figure 6.3.2. Configuration of conservation areas in Portugal. A. highly protected (HPA, orange) and fully protected (FPA, red) areas representative of measures in the present day, used in the two Status Quo scenarios; B. HPAs (turquoise) and FPAs (dark blue) in the Global Sustainability scenario; C. HPAs (turquoise) and FPAs (dark blue) in the National Enterprise scenario; D. HPAs (turquoise) and FPAs (dark blue) in the World Market scenario. Reprinted from Coll, Lynam et al, 2024

Figure. 6.3.3 Long-term classification of the Portuguese shelf ecosystem regarding climate change sensitivity, between 2026-2069, under RCP 8.5: Status Quo scenario (a and d); National Enterprise scenario (b and e); and World Markets scenario (c and f). GIS data representing the current distribution of maritime activity sectors overlaid (keys in figures), including those that may provide some degree of protection from extractive uses (top) or those that represent additional sources of impacts (bottom)

6.4 The Archipelago Sea (Storyline 7)

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8.4.1 Regional Context

The Archipelago Sea is a brackish water body located in the Gulf of Finland, part of the northern Baltic Sea. The current ecological status of the Archipelago Sea is usually considered poor or mediocre (HELCOM 2018). It is eutrophicated, with murky waters and large cyanobacteria blooms due to internal nutrient loading and transported nutrient loads from the main Baltic Sea basins. Consequently, hypoxia has been increasing in the past decades (Conley, Carstensen et al. 2011).

Observations also indicate that the Baltic Sea basin has warmed significantly more rapidly than the world ocean. In particular, winter temperatures and ice conditions have become milder over the last 50 years. Additionally, salinity has fluctuated alongside long-term variations in freshwater runoff from the watershed of the north-east Baltic Sea (Lehmann, Myrberg et al. 2022). Furthermore, ocean acidification (OA) has also been observed to have important effects on benthic invertebrates in the region. Therefore, climate change will likely induce further long-term changes in the basic characteristics of the Baltic Sea: temperature and nutrients will continue to increase, salinity may decline, and hypoxia may become more frequent (Viitasalo and Bonsdorff 2022). Conditions for algae, seagrasses, and associated invertebrates and fish in the region will therefore change as a result. Indeed, climate-driven projected range shifts of marine species have been modelled for bladderwrack and red algae species, eelgrass and blue mussel, and up to 50 other accompanying species (Vuorinen, Hänninen et al. 2015, Torn, Peterson and Herkül 2020). Such studies suggest that a decline in bladderwrack may have large effects on the biodiversity and functioning of the shallow water communities of the northern Baltic Sea (Jonsson, Kotta et al. 2018, Kotta, Vanhatalo et al. 2019).

8.4.2 Modelling datasets used

The food-web model generating projections used in this analysis was driven by Projections analysed here derive from model runs for the sub-regionally parameterised Archipelago Sea EwE food web model, described in Coll, Lynam et al. (2024), and which included a total of 28 living functional groups. Due to the poor representation of the Baltic Sea ecosystem in CMIP6 data, environmental data used to force the foodweb model derive from the coupled Rossby Centre Ocean -Swedish Coastal and Ocean Biogeochemical model (RCO-SCOBI) regional ecosystem model. The datasets selected for the current analysis are summarised in Table 6.4.1 below. These data include future projections under all five scenarios (section 2.2) for 12 species or species groups for which clear climate-driven trends could be extracted from the peer review literature (necessary to setup the climate signal detection algorithm, please see 2.4).

In each cell of the common model domain, and for each scenario and each 20 year period between the present and the final part of the 21st century (section 2.4), the climate signal detection algorithm builds one spatial meta-analysis model that analyses all modelling layers together, testing the null hypothesis that change between the present 20 year period and the future 20 year period is zero. Please see section 2.4 for a detailed description of the analysis methodology employed.

Table 8.4.1: Description of modelling data analysed here for the Archipelago Sea storyline. "latmin": lowest value of latitude in the model domain; "latmax": highest value of latitude in the model domain; "lonmin": lowest value of longitude in the model domain; "lonmax": highest value of longitude in the model domain. "CC" climate change

Variable	Model	Spatial extent (latmin - latmax; lonmin-lonmax)	Resolution	Time slice	Data provider	Expected climate trend
<i>Perca fluviatilis</i> (European perch) ADULT	Ecopath with Ecosim and Ecospace	59.58 to 60.77; 20.14 to 23.51	0.03*0.03	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Riikka Puntila - Dodd, Syke	Increase - warmer water and lower salinity may favour freshwater fish. (Svensson, Karlsson et al. 2017, Viitasalo and Bonsdorff 2022).
<i>Perca fluviatilis</i> (European perch) JUVENILE	Ecopath with Ecosim and Ecospace	59.58 to 60.77; 20.14 to 23.51	0.03*0.03	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Riikka Puntila - Dodd, Syke	Increase - warmer water and lower salinity may favour freshwater fish. (Svensson, Karlsson et al. 2017, Viitasalo and Bonsdorff 2022)
<i>Sander lucioperca</i> (Zander) ADULT	Ecopath with Ecosim and Ecospace	59.58 to 60.77; 20.14 to 23.51	0.03*0.03	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Riikka Puntila - Dodd, Syke	Increase - warmer water and lower salinity may favour freshwater fish. (Pekcan-Hekim, Urho et al. 2011, Viitasalo and Bonsdorff 2022, Olin, Heikinheimo et al. 2023).
<i>Sander lucioperca</i> (Zander) JUVENILE	Ecopath with Ecosim and Ecospace	59.58 to 60.77; 20.14 to 23.51	0.03*0.03	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Riikka Puntila - Dodd, Syke	Increase- warmer water and lower salinity may favour freshwater fish. (Pekcan-Hekim, Urho et al. 2011, Viitasalo and Bonsdorff 2022).
<i>Cercopagis pengoi</i> (Fishhook water flea)	Ecopath with Ecosim and Ecospace	59.58 to 60.77; 20.14 to 23.51	0.03*0.03	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Riikka Puntila - Dodd, Syke	Increase (Rowe, Guleikova et al. 2016, Viitasalo and Bonsdorff 2022).
<i>Clupea harengus</i> (Atlantic herring)	Ecopath with Ecosim and Ecospace	59.58 to 60.77; 20.14 to 23.51	0.03*0.03	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Riikka Puntila - Dodd, Syke	Decrease, (Casini, Bartolino et al. 2010, Pekcan-Hekim, Gårdmark et al. 2016, Viitasalo and Bonsdorff 2022).
<i>Fucus vesiculosus</i> (Bladderwrack)	Ecopath with Ecosim	59.58 to 60.77; 20.14 to 23.51	0.03*0.03	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for	Riikka Puntila - Dodd, Syke	Decrease, (Takolander, Leskinen and Cabeza 2017, Kotta, Vanhatalo et al. 2019, Viitasalo and Bonsdorff 2022).

	and Ecospace			20 year rolling means)		
<i>Gadus morhua (Cod)</i>	Ecopath with Ecosim and Ecospace	59.58 to 60.77; 20.14 to 23.51	0.03*0.03	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Riikka Puntila - Dodd, Syke	Decrease (Casini, Hansson et al. 2021, Viitasalo and Bonsdorff 2022).
<i>Gasterosteus aculeatus (Three spined stickleback)</i>	Ecopath with Ecosim and Ecospace	59.58 to 60.77; 20.14 to 23.51	0.03*0.03	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Riikka Puntila - Dodd, Syke	Increase (Lefébure, Larsson and Byström 2011, Viitasalo and Bonsdorff 2022)-
<i>Mytilus trossulus (Bay mussel)</i>	Ecopath with Ecosim and Ecospace	59.58 to 60.77; 20.14 to 23.51	0.03*0.03	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Riikka Puntila - Dodd, Syke	Decrease (Jaatinen, Westerbom et al. 2021, Åkermark, Liénart et al. 2022, Viitasalo and Bonsdorff 2022)
<i>Sprattus sprattus (European sprat)</i>	Ecopath with Ecosim and Ecospace	59.58 to 60.77; 20.14 to 23.51	0.03*0.03	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Riikka Puntila - Dodd, Syke	Increase (Peltonen and Weigel 2022, Viitasalo and Bonsdorff 2022).
<i>Neogobius melanostomus (Round goby)</i>	Ecopath with Ecosim and Ecospace	59.58 to 60.77; 20.14 to 23.51	0.03*0.03	2006-2025 (reference); 2026-2079 (start years for 20 year rolling means)	Riikka Puntila - Dodd, Syke	Increase (Kotta, Nurkse et al. 2016, Holmes, Kotta et al. 2019).

8.4.3 GIS datasets used

Table 8.4.2: GIS datasets used to frame the modelling analysis results in the context of the region's blue economy.

Dataset	Data provider	Available at
Designated marine conservation areas	UNEP-WCMC and IUCN	https://www.protectedplanet.net/en/search-areas?geo_type=site
Capital and maintenance dredging	EMODnet	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geoviewer/
Sewage outfall	EMODnet	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geoviewer/
Demersal fishing	Global Fishing Watch	https://globalfishingwatch.org/data-download/datasets/public-fishing-effort
Pelagic fishing	Global Fishing Watch	https://globalfishingwatch.org/data-download/datasets/public-fishing-effort
Wind farms	EMODnet	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geoviewer/

8.4.4 Results

The spatial data resulting from these analyses, identifying long-term climate change refugia and hotspots in Archipelago Sea, is freely available in Talbot and Queirós (2024). In all the scenarios considered here, patterns in biomass changes in the Archipelago Sea are spatially heterogenous, with no long-term, consistently appearing climate change hotspots (or brightspots). The majority of areas are classified as refugia, suggesting that biomass at the community level is relatively climate resilient. Some areas appear as unclassified (white spaces in figures), suggesting that there is a dynamic, or variable, effect of climate pressures over the region, over the course of time series (section 2.5).

Looking closely at results from the RCP2.6 status quo scenario (2.2) in which there are no additional management measures (status quo, Figure 6.4.1 a and c) it appears that emergence of refugia here is largely driven by decreases in biomass of the freshwater fish species perch (*Perca fluviatilis*) and zander (*Sander lucioperca*), and increases in biomass of *Fucus* (not shown), all in opposition to the expected climate-driven trend based on literature review (Table 6.4.1). It is possible that these responses can be attributed to the higher salinity regime in the lower emissions scenarios, which benefits *Fucus* (Rinne and Salovius-Laurén 2020), but disadvantages the freshwater fish. Further unexpected responses are seen under the Global Sustainability scenario (Figure 6.4.1 b and d), which expresses the same level of greenhouse gas emissions and additional management measures. In this scenario, only small scale coastal and recreational fisheries are permitted; and this appears to benefit herring (*Clupea harengus*), which increases in biomass, contrary to the expected climate-driven trend (individual data not shown, Table 6.4.1). This is likely due to the fact that herring is a large component of the trawl fishery that is banned in the Global Sustainability scenario, and once fishing pressure from this fleet is removed, herring biomass increases quickly in the foodweb model from which these projections were taken (data not shown.) Biomass of the fishhook waterflea (*Cercopagis pengoi*) and three-spined stickleback (*Gasterosteus aculeatus*) also decrease against expectation

based on climate change literature review (individual species data not shown, Table 6.4.1), perhaps as a consequence of the increase in herring (*Clupea harengus*), which is a key predator of both species in the foodweb model. *Fucus* biomass also increases further in this scenario (individual data not shown), likely due to the higher salinity regime generally represented by the RCP2.6 emissions scenario, but also by the decreased nutrient loads simulated by Global Sustainability, in which the Baltic Sea Action Plan target of “nutrient concentrations being close to natural ;levels” has been met. This results in fewer phytoplankton blooms and better water clarity, possibly benefitting *Fucus* growth (Rinne and Salovius-Laurén 2020) in the foodweb model.

In this case study, there are two different scenarios under the RCP8.5 emissions trajectory with no additional management measures (status quo), but they have different nutrient regimes (see Coll, Lynam et al. (2024) for full details). One scenario simulates nutrient regimes at a present day reference level (Figure 6.4.2 a and e) while the second simulates nutrient concentrations at a level equivalent to those represented by the World Market scenario (e.g. increased from the present day reference, Figure 6.4.2 b and f). In both of these status quo scenarios, refugia in the Archipelago Sea are still widespread, with similar patterns in species biomass responses emerging. Biomasses of the two freshwater fish (*Perca fluviatilis* and *Sander lucioperca*) decrease across much of the Archipelago Sea (data not shown) in opposition to the expected climate driven trend (Table 6.4.1). It is possible that these decreases are caused by increased predation from seals (Olin, Olsson et al. 2022). While seals were not included in this analysis as a clear climate trend for them could not be discerned from the reviewed literature, they were part of the original foodweb model used to generate these projections, and in that model, seal biomass increased in all scenarios analysed here (Coll, Lynam et al. (2024)). The impact of seal predation in the foodweb model could therefore override the expected climate driven benefits to *Perca fluviatilis* and *Sander lucioperca* biomass, as key prey. Sprat (*Sprattus sprattus*) biomass also decreases in these scenarios, contrary to expected climate-driven trends derived from the literature (Table 6.4.1) that slightly warmer winters and fresher water would benefit this species by decreasing modelled biomass of cod, which is a main predator of sprat (Ojaveer and Kalejs 2010).

The National Enterprise (Figure 6.4.2 c and g) and World Market (Figure 6.4.2 d and h) scenarios simulate the RCP8.5 emissions trajectory, but also include further changes in human activities. Under the National Enterprise scenario, there is no restoration in terms of water quality or nutrient loads, although new fully (FPA) and highly (HPA) protected areas are designated (Figure 6.4.3 B). In this scenario, fishing effort increases, although the focus is on small scale rather than industrial fleets, and trawling is banned. Under the World Market scenario, nutrient concentrations increase, the spatial extent of HPAs and FPAs are smaller (Figure 6.4.3 C), and generally focus on essential fish habitat for commercial species. Fishing effort also increases in this scenario, but trawling is prioritised (Coll, Lynam et al, 2024). Under both of these scenarios, long-term climate change refugia also emerge across much of the model domain, with the unexpected decrease in biomass of perch (*Perca fluviatilis*) and zander (*Sander lucioperca*) noted above still a contributing factor, possibly driven by predation from seals. In general, species biomass patterns in each scenario are slightly different from the status quo scenarios (data not shown), and appear to be responding to other factors beyond climate drivers. For example, in the National Enterprise scenario, which bans all trawling, herring (*Clupea harengus*) biomass increases (data not shown), likely in response to release from fishing pressure. Consequently, *C. pengoi* and *G. aculeatus* biomass decreases (data not shown) as predation from herring on these two species increases. Conversely, under the World Market scenario, which simulates the prioritisation of trawling, *C. harengus* biomass decreases, as herring is a major component of the catch in the Baltic trawl fishery and, released from predation as a result, *C. pengoi* and *G. aculeatus* biomass increases (data not shown).

6.4.5 Discussion

The key finding in this analysis is that whilst the widespread emergence of long-term climate change refugia in the Archipelago Sea may suggest some resilience to climate change at the community level, changes in biomass are spatially heterogeneous and complicated by interactions between species response to climate drivers, foodweb interactions, and simulated changes in direct and indirect human activities in different scenarios. This is perhaps unsurprising given the hydrographic complexity of this part of the Baltic Sea, and the significant non-climatic pressures (e.g. eutrophication) in this area. In this analysis, species often appeared to respond strongly to changes in fishing pressure and associated effects on food-web interactions such as predation and competition. This result highlights how spatial management measures to reduce additional human pressures on the system, such as fishing, may substantially increase the climate resilience of this community into the future. This may, in turn, help ensure that the small scale fisheries in the area remain sustainable, and help control populations of invasive or problematic species such as waterflea (*Cercopagis pengoi*) and stickleback (*Gasterosteus aculeatus*) by ensuring biomasses of predatory species remain high.

Figure 6.4.1. Long-term climate change refugia and hotspots in the Finish Archipelago Sea 2026-2069 in the lower emissions Status Quo scenario (RCP 2.6, a and c), and the Global Sustainability scenario (which has the same climate projection but includes low barriers to climate change adaptation and

mitigation). GIS data representing maritime sectors overlaid (keys in figures), including those that provide some degree of protection from extractive uses to these habitats (top) or those that represent additional sources of impacts (bottom).

Figure 6.4.2. Long-term classification of the Archipelago Sea ecosystem regarding climate change sensitivity, between 2026-2069, under RCP 8.5: Status Quo scenario with nutrient concentrations at the reference level (a and e); Status Quo scenario with nutrient levels equivalent to the World Market scenario(b and f); National Enterprise scenario (c and g); and World Markets scenario (d and h). GIS data representing the current distribution of maritime activity sectors overlaid (keys in figures), including those that may provide some degree of protection from extractive uses (top) or those that represent additional sources of impacts (bottom).

Figure 6.4.3. Locations of Fully Protected (FPA) and Highly Protected (HPA) areas in the Archipelago Sea under the three different managed scenarios. A – Global Sustainability (RCP2.6), B – National Enterprise (RCP8.5), C – World Market (RCP8.5). Reprinted with permission from Coll, Lynam et al, 2024.

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